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MS driven energy system management and power/gas grid integration solutions

SALTOpower

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1 INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D2.1 - MS driven energy system management and power/gas grid integration solutions, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

Based on the Joint Research Activity foreseen in SALTOpower that aims to develop Excellence Research further exploiting the use of MS technologies, the T2.1 is concerned with the development of a flexible interconnection of power and gas energy distribution systems, by means of flexible power and/or gas conversion of medium/high temperature renewable heat; the T2.2 aims at the development of a higher penetration of renewable energy sources in the energy system, by means of stand-alone flexible energy storage systems.

In the following D2.1, an outline of Molten Salt mixtures is introduced, pointing out their thermophysical properties and their conventional use in a spectrum of industrial and energy applications in different sectors, mainly: chemical industry, nuclear power industry, concentrating solar power, and waste treatment. In addition, an overview of the suitable electrochemical, thermochemical and hybrid processes for hydrogen and/or syngas production is presented. Considering the available MS mixtures and their corresponding operating temperature ranges, as a “beyond State-of-Art” the feasibility of matching processes for gas production and MS mixtures is evaluated, where MS technologies can provide heat and electricity to processes for hydrogen and syngas production. Moreover, a techno-economic assessment of two specific approaches, used as references, to the concept of “beyond State-of-Art” is conducted.

A general review of energy storage systems is also presented in this deliverable D2.1, highlighting the importance of considering also “Carnot Batteries” in the range of eligible options, where Molten Salts display a promising role in the storage ecosystem for electricity and heat. An overview of suitable thermodynamic cycles for charging and discharging the Molten Salt storage system or the Carnot Batteries is reported. Moreover, as a part of ongoing assessments studies, a techno-economic assessment is conducted to provide an initial evaluation of a 100 MW_e Carnot battery, incorporating defined boundary conditions and assumptions. The proposed model further encompasses an assessment of impacts over the power system, based on various scenarios of competing technologies (e.g. pumped hydro storage, Li-ion batteries) by means of the software Artelys Crystal Super Grid, a modeling tool for the electricity production distribution system.

2 SUMMARY OF SALTOPOWER PROJECT

The use of Thermal Energy Storage (TES) in combination with the thermal conversion of solar irradiation – Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) – has long been regarded as an important technological solution for the production of dispatchable electricity. Whereas thermal oil-based systems have set the standard in the first generation of commercial CSP Plants, the use of Molten Salts as heat transfer and storage media has been gathering research efforts and it is regarded, by the industry, as the foregoing standard for new commercial plants.

Molten Salt (MS) research has been deployed along the past decade in Germany and Italy, alongside with the erection of dedicated Research Infrastructure (RI) enabling the study and experimental test of e.g. materials, components or O&M procedures suiting this innovative technological approach.

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

With the recent commissioning of a full-fledged Molten Salt Solar system emulating a commercial MS-CSP Plant in Évora (Évora Molten Salt Platform²), Portugal has joined this research effort with a new outstanding RI in this field.

Gathering the unique experience of two non-Widening partners in the development and operation of the most important MS-RI at European level with the incumbent new RI capacity available in a Widening country, the present proposal aims at enhancing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity of the Consortium in the foregoing exploitation of this outstanding RI. SALTOpower has a strong focus on an enhanced capacity building of researchers going beyond purely scientific capacities, strengthening the research management and administration skills of the Widening RI.

By means of enhanced cooperation duly framed on a common research strategy aiming at further developing MS technologies, SALTOpower aims at creating the reference European facility for the development and testing of Molten Salt based technologies for energy storage and dispatchable power production solutions, for the integration of different renewable energy sources, power and gas grids.

Including support measures aimed at the development of Joint Research Activities (WP2), at the implementation of an enhanced Career Building framework (WP3) and at the strategic alignment with relevant stakeholders in its field (WP4), maximisation of SALTOpower impacts (WP5) follows an outreach matrix defined by two axes: target audience - the 4Helix level (A)cademia, (P)olicy makers, (I)ndustry and Civil (S)ociety – and outreach level - (R)egional, (N)ational and (I)nternational.

² EMSP – www.emsp.uevora.pt

3 MOLTEN SALTS MIXTURES AS HEAT TRANSFER FLUID AND STORAGE MEDIUM

Molten Salts (MS), with their properties of high thermal stability, excellent heat transfer capabilities, and wide operational temperature ranges, are used across a spectrum of industrial and energy applications (Figure 1). In the chemical industry, they catalyse a variety of processes, enabling high-temperature reactions that are otherwise challenging to manage. Within the realm of nuclear reactors, molten salts are used in coolant systems and as the medium for nuclear fuel in advanced reactor designs, promising safer and more efficient energy production. Their role extends to the field of renewable energy, where they are integral to the storage and transfer of thermal energy, particularly in Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants, facilitating the generation of electricity even when solar irradiance is absent. Beyond energy production, molten salts offer innovative solutions in waste treatment processes, where their chemical properties enable the detoxification, recovery, and recycling of valuable materials from industrial residues.

Figure 1. Main applications of molten salts, adapted from [1].

The choice of salt types hinges on an understanding of the chemical and thermodynamic properties required by different energy technologies. Salts must exhibit high chemical and radiolytic stability at elevated temperatures, favourable melting and boiling points, significant specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, and maintain low vapor pressure to ensure operational integrity [1].

Thermal exchange and storage materials are fundamental components of a CSP plant, affecting both the efficiency and the costs of the generated electric power. Currently, MS are the most used materials in CSP for temperatures above 100 °C as Heat Storage Medium (HSM) and Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF); they are attractive candidates having high heat capacity, high density, high thermal stability, relatively low cost, no flammability, and very low vapor pressure, which leads to a storage design without pressurized vessels. In general, MS are defined as ionic liquids, and classified according to anions and cations. In practice, the operating temperature is defined by liquidus temperature, that is the initial solidification onset. Clearly, it is necessary to avoid freezing inside the piping, the heat exchanger, and the storage tanks. For this reason, an auxiliary back-up heating system is required in MS-CSP plant.

Nitrate/nitrite mixtures are studied and developed for low and medium temperature of Parabolic Trough Concentrating Solar Plant (PT-CSP). Chloride salts and their mixtures are particularly relevant as working fluids for high temperatures (>400 °C) applications in solar power tower plants [2]. CSP with other anhydrous oxyanion salts (e.g., **carbonates**) and halides salts (e.g., **fluorides, chlorides**) are currently strongly limited: they are present only in theoretical studies and thermal analysis

measurements, not as real commercial application [3]. Indeed, the main shortcomings are a relatively very high freezing point presented by the salts and their mixtures and compatibility with containment materials, the latter problem being especially relevant for molten carbonates. However, a few molten mixtures of inorganic salts were presented in the literature as TES for high temperatures, such as sodium hydroxide which operates at temperature between 320 °C and 800 °C.

3.1 Molten Salt mixtures Applications

3.1.1 Nuclear reactors

The **Molten Salt Reactor** (MSR) emerges as a pivotal advancement in nuclear reactor technology, designated as one of the six advanced reactor configurations for future generations by the Generation IV international forum. This recognition is attributed to its superior safety features and operational efficiency. Characterized as a subset of nuclear fission reactors, MSRs uniquely employ a high-temperature molten salt mixture that serves dual roles: as a coolant and, innovatively, as the reactor's fuel medium. The MSR distinguishes itself as a promising reactor model, a distinction owed to the MS advantageous properties. These include an elevated boiling point, minimized vapor pressure, substantial heat capacity, and robust resistance to radiation effects. The versatility of MS facilitates the classification of MSRs into two principal categories based on their operational application: one variant operates with MS as a fuel solution, incorporating fissile materials in dissolution, and the other one utilizes MS as a coolant, paired with solid fuel. The latter configuration is more commonly known as the Fluoride Salt-Cooled High-Temperature Reactor (FHR) [4]. In MSRs, MS are utilized both as coolant fluids and as carriers for nuclear fuel, offering significant advantages over traditional water-cooled reactors. MS possess the thermal properties of high heat absorption capacity without undergoing phase changes at standard atmospheric pressures, allowing the reactor to operate at higher temperatures while maintaining lower system pressures. This capability enhances the efficiency of the reactor, leading to more efficient energy conversion. In MSRs, nuclear fuel, typically uranium or thorium, is dissolved directly in the molten salts, facilitating easy modification of fuel composition during operation and extraction or addition of fission products without shutting down the reactor [5,6]. Moreover, the high boiling points of MS reduce the risk of radioactive material release, and some MSR designs incorporate passive safety systems that can automatically halt the chain reaction under abnormal conditions without human or electrical intervention, thereby significantly improving reactor safety [7]. The reduction of nuclear waste through isotope transmutation from long-lived to shorter-lived or stable isotopes is another potential advantage. The MS used in MSRs are typically mixtures of lithium, beryllium, thorium, and uranium fluorides or chlorides, chosen for their chemical stability, high thermal capacity, and good thermal conductivity [8]. Moreover, MSRs require salts that are exceptionally stable, have high boiling points, and low melting points to ensure smooth and efficient thermal transfer and energy production. The fluoride salt mixture known as FLiBe (LiF-BeF₂, 66:34 mol%) stands out as an ideal choice due to its low thermal neutron cross-section and the synergistic properties of beryllium and lithium fluorides, which enhance reactor compatibility and performance. Alternatively, FLiNaK (LiF-NaF-KF, 46.5:11.5:42 mol%) has been developed to replicate FLiBe's beneficial attributes but with significantly lower toxicity levels. Other fluoride salts, such as NaF-ZrF₄ and KF-ZrF₄, present solutions to mitigate tritium generation. However, they pose their own challenges, such as high melting points and vapor pressures, respectively [9].

3.1.2 Chemical industry

In the field of industrial chemistry, MS play a versatile role in catalyzing innovation across a wide range of processes. Their distinctive thermal stability, superior ionic conductivity, and solvent

capabilities contribute significantly to this versatility. Serving as catalytic mediums, MS composed of $\text{NiCl}_2\text{-KCl}$, along with sodium chloride (NaCl) and potassium chloride (KCl), are crucial in enhancing the high activity and long-term stability of $\text{Ni-Fe/Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts, effectively preventing carbon encapsulation without any deactivation [10]. Additionally, MS are integral to electrochemical processes. For example, dissolving steam in molten LiCl electrolyte at $660\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, followed by electrochemical reduction, facilitates hydrogen production at a constant electrolysis voltage [11]. MS also find application in the development of high-temperature MS batteries, which utilize a high-temperature MS electrolyte, such as LiCl-KCl . These batteries, featuring a Li-Al alloy anode and a FeS_2 cathode, and employing electrolytes like LiCl , LiF-LiBr , and LiCl-LiBr , show enhanced performance and expanded application potential. Developed for electric vehicle applications and as thermally activated batteries, or thermal batteries, they are appreciated for their high output power and exceptional stability in long-term storage, among other advantages [12].

3.1.3 Waste treatment

MS mixtures are at the forefront of waste treatment technologies, taking advantage of their high thermal stability and exceptional heat transfer capabilities across diverse applications. In pyrolysis, nitrate-based mixtures, such as sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) and potassium nitrate (KNO_3), operate effectively at temperatures up to $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, enabling the decomposition of organic materials into bio-oil. An example of the gasification process is the utilization of MS ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-K}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-Li}_2\text{CO}_3$) with CO_2 for cotton stalk gasification at temperatures ranging from 750 to $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [13]. For detoxification from hazardous materials, mixtures with an equimolar composition of NaCl-KCl , ranging from a few to about 10% by weight of fluorine additives such as CaF_2 , NaF , Na_3AlF_6 (cryolite), or KF , are used. These additives customize the coagulation process and thereby the fusion process, ensuring the complete decomposition of toxic substances and thus neutralizing their harmful effects [14]. The recovery of precious metals from electronic waste or exhausted catalysts makes use of mixtures of MS, specifically the eutectic KOH-NaOH , to dissolve glass, oxides, and plastic in the waste at around $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ without oxidizing the more valuable metals, thus enabling their subsequent separation and recovery [15]. Additionally, the production of biochar through low-temperature conversion processes involves the use of carbonate mixtures such as potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3), sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), and lithium carbonate (Li_2CO_3) to prepare carbon-based adsorbents from biomass waste [16]. Finally, the treatment of fly ash, a by-product of the combustion of municipal solid waste, involves using mixtures of carbonates and chlorides that are melted at moderate temperatures, ranging from $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These mixtures can effectively extract alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides and sulphates from the fly ash, significantly mitigating its potential environmental impact [17].

3.1.4 Heat storage and Heat Transfer medium

MS are predominantly utilized for heat storage, presenting a sustainable method for capturing and storing thermal energy. Their main application is found in CSP plants and nuclear facilities, where their capacity to store vast amounts of heat at elevated temperatures facilitates the generation of electricity and/or heat. Nitrates and nitrites are among the most commonly used heat transfer fluids in contemporary applications. However, the production of these salts is geographically and quantitatively limited, with the majority of global reserves located in Chile and Peru [9].

In nuclear facilities, an instance of application is the Nuclear Energy System (NES), comprising two primary components: a MS loop that transfers heat through a secondary coolant from the nuclear reactor to a storage tank, and a power cycle loop, which includes various power cycles converging at

the point of common coupling. These cycles might use the Rankine, Brayton, or combined Air-Brayton configurations, utilizing different working fluids to generate power [18]. A variant of the NES is its hybrid version, which combines various energy generation systems to enhance efficiency. This includes incorporating nuclear reactors, renewable energy sources, process heat applications, and different energy storage solutions [18].

Regarding CSPs, they transfer the thermal energy by collecting solar radiation using an array of mirrors or heliostats to concentrate it onto a receiver, which then transfers the heat, directly or indirectly, to the MS. Technologies such as parabolic troughs, solar power towers, and linear Fresnel reflectors are instrumental in this process. Each varies in its method of concentrating solar energy but is unified in its objective to maximize the capture of thermal energy and its transfer to the MS.

A prime example of MS use in CSP systems is “Solar Salt”, a binary mixture of 60% sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) and 40% potassium nitrate (KNO_3) by weight. Its ability to remain thermally stable in a liquid state at temperatures up to 600 °C enables efficient heat transfer and energy storage, exemplified in the Solar Two central receiver system in California and numerous solar thermal plants in Spain [19]. First demonstrations in Europe of MS deployment in linear CSP configurations include projects like the experimental facility PCS of ENEA Casaccia Research Centre (Italy) and the direct MS loop located at Priolo Gargallo (Sicily, Italy), addressing the integration challenges in CSP technology [20].

For the storage of MS, sophisticated containment systems are employed, designed to minimize heat loss, and ensure the longevity and safety of the stored thermal energy. These systems typically involve insulated storage tanks that can maintain the high temperatures of the MS without significant thermal degradation over time. The storage tanks are engineered from materials specifically chosen for their resistance to the corrosive properties of MS and their ability to endure the thermal stresses arising from temperature fluctuations [9]. There are two primary types of MS thermal storage options utilized in CSP plants: the thermocline system and the two-tank system. The two-tank system operates on a principle where a hot tank and a cold tank separately store the salt, akin to conventional storage schemes in CSP plants. Conversely, the thermocline system employs a single tank that houses both the cold and hot salt layers. In a thermocline tank, the salt layers are divided by a thermocline - a sharply defined layer where the temperature changes dramatically. This layer acts as a barrier, preventing the hot and cold salts from mixing, thereby maintaining distinct thermal zones within a single storage vessel. When charging, cold salt moves from the tank's colder region, passes through a heat exchanger, and enters the warmer section, effectively storing thermal energy. During discharge, the process reverses, with hot salt flowing out through the heat exchanger back to the colder part of the tank. A significant challenge in MS thermal energy storage systems is the risk of the salt freezing, given its high melting point. To mitigate these issues several strategies are essential to maintain the salt in a liquid state and ensure its effective circulation. First, thermal insulation of storage tanks and piping is crucial to retain heat within the system. Additionally, auxiliary heating systems can prevent the salt from freezing by activating when the salt's temperature approaches its melting point. Continuous circulation of MS prevents solidification by maintaining uniform heat distribution. Active temperature control systems that monitor and adjust the MS temperature can prevent temperatures from falling below the freezing point. Drainage systems are also beneficial; they allow for the salt to be drained from receivers and pipes during downtime, storing it in thermally insulated tanks to prevent freezing. Pre-heating the system before startup after a period of inactivity is necessary to ensure the salt returns to a liquid state. Implementing thermal tracing on piping, using heating cables or tapes, can maintain the salt's temperature above its melting point. Operational strategies, such as pre-heating the system during colder hours or maintaining a minimum temperature overnight, are employed to prevent freezing. These measures, individually or in combination, play a critical role in the operational reliability and efficiency of CSP systems, addressing the challenges associated with MS thermal management [9].

3.2 Molten Salt Mixture Thermophysical Properties

The use of **nitrate** mixtures both as heat transfer fluids (HTF) and sensible heat storage materials (HSM), and less frequently as phase change material (PCM) [21], has been investigated since the 80's [22,23] with a particular focus on the so-called Solar Salt, a binary composed of NaNO_3 and KNO_3 in a weight percentage ratio of 60-40. This composition presents several favourable characteristics, including upper temperature limits (around 600 °C), lower unit cost, better safety aspects and low environmental impact. Even though it is not the eutectic composition for this couple of nitrates, it is preferable to use a greater percentage of sodium nitrate to reduce the material costs to an acceptable level, and at the same time to not increase the liquidus temperature value. Unfortunately, its operating temperature range is restricted by two characteristics: an initial solidification temperature of about 240 °C, and an upper working temperature limit of 590-600 °C [24,25]. To date, no methods have been proposed for increasing the upper temperature stability limit of molten nitrates, barring "short terms" effects [26] that are not useful for a CSP plant where the maximum temperature is to be maintained over long periods of time. Moreover, the experimental results show that the use of cations different from those of first group metals leads to a decrease in the nitrate chemical stability [27,28].

For all the above reasons, recent research has focused on studies aiming to decrease the initial solidification temperature of the mixtures. Such a decrease might lead to a cost reduction in the CSP plant pipelines' thermal insulation and backup heater, as well as making the start-up and maintenance operations easier.

With the aim to mitigate the drawback of the relatively high freezing temperature of the Solar Salt, MS mixtures with lower melting temperatures (<150 °C) were proposed in the scientific literature.

In general, the addition of other cations such as lithium and calcium, and different anions, such as nitrite as NaNO_2 , has been considered, with the use of other metals cations, such as silver, cesium and rubidium [29,30] being deemed unrealistic. The mixtures containing AgNO_3 , TlNO_3 , RbNO_3 are only academically studied [30,31]

The ternary Na/K/Ca//NO_3 (commercialized as Hitec XL[®]) presents practically the same safety advantages as the Solar Salt, along with good thermophysical properties, a freezing point around 120 °C but a lower thermal stability [27,32]. Given its low price, comparable with the one of Solar Salt, this mixture can be used both as a HTF and a HSM in an active, direct storage system.

An interesting option could be the use of lithium containing mixtures. Given lithium relative high price, its use was only considered convenient as HTF (with the Solar Salt as HSM), in an indirect storage system with an intermediate heat exchanger between the two fluids [33]. Literature results showed that the cost reduction for the thermal insulation and the back-up heater is totally offset by expenditure for the intermediate heat exchanger and, as such, no viable economic advantages were present.

The ternary Li/K/Ca//NO_3 additive systems were also studied. Unfortunately, they do not present any improvement with respect to the properties of Na/K/Ca//NO_3 and are likely to be more expensive, given the presence of lithium in place of sodium.

Fluids containing nitrites, such as the Hitec[®] mixtures, present an initial solidification point and a chemical stability like ternaries like the Hitec XL[®]. However, they are more costly and more toxic.

Regarding quaternary mixtures, such as Ca/Li/Na/K//NO_3 , their freezing point and expected price are just slightly lower than those of lithium containing ternary materials. However, their upper

temperature limit would be decreased by the presence of calcium [34] leading to worsening efficiency in the thermal-electric power conversion.

Also, quaternary and quinary reciprocal mixtures (such as, respectively, Li/Na/K//NO₂/NO₃ and Ca/Li/Na/K//NO₂/NO₃) were proposed [35] and their complexity is apparently not matched by a significant improvement in their thermophysical features. Novel, senary mixture have been studied, with low melting temperatures down to 56 °C.

Molten **chloride salts** can be used as HTF, and as HSM for both sensible [36] and latent heat storage [37]. Other metal halides such as **fluorides** and bromides are expectably more expensive, and the former present particularly severe issues regarding corrosion [38].

Chlorides present the advantages of low cost and high thermal stability and, for this reason, suitable for the next generation (Gen3) of CSP [39]. On the other hand, their freezing point is generally higher than for molten nitrates [40], and they can be extremely corrosive and require costly containment materials [41–43].

Among the several possible formulations, the chlorides of first and second group are of particular interest, given their relative low cost and high availability. For instance, the Na/K/Mg//Cl eutectic (with a molar percentage of around 47/23/30 for MgCl₂/KCl/NaCl, respectively) presents a quite advantageous price, below 0.35 \$/kg, and a melting point of 385 °C [44]. Villada et al. [44] reported an acceptable volatility below 800 °C, density and thermal conductivity comparable (but at higher temperatures) to the Solar Salt and a dynamic viscosity ranging from about 2 cP (at 800 °C) to around 5 cP near the freezing temperature. A problem using this mixture derives from the high hygroscopicity of MgCl₂, which leads to corrosion issues and also affects the salt stability in presence of air [45].

Similar consideration can be made for the Na/K/Ca//Cl additive eutectic (51.7/7.5/40.8 mol% for CaCl₂/KCl/NaCl, respectively), with a price estimated as the half of the one for the Solar Salt and a melting point of 497 °C [46].

Several mixtures of the Na/K/Zn//Cl system were evaluated by NREL [47], they exhibit a significantly high density (up to 2.4 g/ml) and acceptable price (0.8 \$/kg), but present high volatility especially above 700 °C.

Molten carbonates can be potentially employed at higher temperature than nitrates, but costly cations are to be used in order to obtain mixtures with an acceptable freezing point.

The Na/K/Li//CO₃ ternary eutectic has a melting temperature of 398 °C, an estimated cost of 2.5 \$/kg and it was proposed to be used as HTF up to 650-700 °C [47,48]. This temperature increase might increase the overall solar-to-electric conversion efficiency until 18.5% more with respect to systems operating at 565°C with molten nitrates [49].

As well as molten chlorides, also molten carbonates present substantial issues about materials compatibility, also depending on the gas atmosphere [43].

Mixed anions (reciprocal) mixtures have mainly been proposed for thermal storage as phase change materials [50,51]. However, the solubility of carbonates and chlorides in molten nitrates is limited [23]: some recent scientific paper reports a sizable increase regarding the chemical stability (i.e. the maximum operating temperature), if chlorides are added to nitrate mixtures [52].

In Table 1 the composition and the thermophysical properties of the main MS mixtures are showed.

Table 1. Molten Salt mixtures: composition and thermophysical properties.

Mixture	System	Composition	Melting Temperature [°C]	Decomposition Temperature [°C]	Density ³ [kg m ⁻³]	Specific Heat Capacity ³ [J kg ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹]	References
Nitrate-based							
Solar Salt	Binary	60 NaNO ₃ –40 KNO ₃	240	565	1834	1512	[25,53]
Hitec	Ternary	7 NaNO ₃ –53 KNO ₃ –40 NaNO ₂	142	450	1721	1560	[54–56]
Hitec XL	Ternary	15 NaNO ₃ –43 KNO ₃ –42 Ca(NO ₃) ₂	130	450	2000	1449	[32,57,58]
LiNaK//NO ₃	Ternary	30 LiNO ₃ –18 NaNO ₃ –52 KNO ₃	118	550	1884	1580	[59–61]
LiNaKCa//NO ₃	Quaternary	15.5 LiNO ₃ –8.2 NaNO ₃ –54.3 KNO ₃ –22 Ca(NO ₃) ₂	93	450	1803	1518	[62–64]
LiNaKNO ₃ NO ₂	Quaternary	9 LiNO ₃ –42.3 NaNO ₃ –33.6 KNO ₃ –15.1 KNO ₂	97	450	1877	1155	[65]
Chloride-based							
KMgCl	Binary	62.5 KCl–37.5 MgCl ₂	430	>700	1857	999	[66–68]
NaKMgCl	Ternary	20.5 NaCl–30.9 KCl–48.6 MgCl ₂	383	>700	1669	1024	[39,66]
NaMgCaCl	Ternary	39.6 NaCl–39 MgCl ₂ –21.4 CaCl ₂	407	650	2557	1104	[69–71]
NaKZnCl	Ternary	7.5 NaCl–23.9 KCl–68.6 ZnCl ₂	204	>700	2207	901	[67,71,72]
KMgZnCl	Ternary	49.4 KCl–15.5 MgCl ₂ –35.1 ZnCl ₂	356	>700	1857	866	[66,67,71]
Fluoride-based							
LiNaKF	Ternary	29.2 LiF–11.7 NaF–59.1 KF	454	>700	2109	1590	[73,74]
NaBF	Binary	3 NaF–97 NaBF ₄	385	>700	1866	1506	[55]
KBF	Binary	13 KF–87 KBF ₄	460	>700	1792	1305	[75]
KZrF	Binary	32.5 KF–67.5 ZrF ₄	420	>700	2680	1000	[55]
Carbonate-based							
LiNaKCO ₃	Ternary	32.1 Li ₂ CO ₃ –33.4 Na ₂ CO ₃ –34.5 K ₂ CO ₃	397	670	2038	1610	[76]

³ Mean value in the operating temperature range.

Among several fluid compositions proposed as HTF and HSM for CSP applications, to present a comparative assessment of their thermophysical properties, four molten nitrate/nitrite mixtures, among the ones mostly employed, have been selected and studied [77,78]. In the following, results of this study are reported and discussed.

Table 2 summarizes the thermo-physical properties of the MS mixtures here considered for the comparison; the Solar Salt properties can be compared with those of three alternative MS mixtures.

Table 2. Thermo-physical properties of the Solar Salt, Hitec®, Hitec XL® and lithium containing ternary MS mixtures (source: [77]).

Solar Salt	
Chemical composition (%wt)	NaNO ₃ / KNO ₃ (60 / 40)
Density [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$\rho = 2090 - 0.63 \cdot T$
Dynamic Viscosity [cP] vs. temperature [°C]	$\mu = 71645 \cdot T^{-1.763}$
Thermal conductivity [$\frac{W}{\circ C \cdot m}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$k = 0.3804 + 3.452 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot T$
Heat capacity [$\frac{kJ}{\circ C \cdot kg}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$c_p = 1.5404 + 3.0924 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot T$
Thermal stability (max operation temperature)	600 °C
Liquidus temperature (initial solidification point)	238 °C
Hitec® (Na/K nitrate/nitrite)	
Chemical composition (%wt)	NaNO ₃ / KNO ₃ / NaNO ₂ (7 / 53 / 40)
Density [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$\rho = -0.9 \cdot T + 2269.4$
Dynamic Viscosity [cP] vs. temperature [°C]	$\mu = 146452 \cdot T^{-1.903}$
Thermal conductivity [$\frac{W}{\circ C \cdot m}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$k = 0.5843 \mp 0.0006 \cdot T$
Heat capacity [$\frac{kJ}{\circ C \cdot kg}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$c_p = 1.55 - 0.0001 \cdot T$
Thermal stability (max operation temperature)	450 °C under air; 530 °C under inert gas
Liquidus temperature (initial solidification point)	141 °C
Hitec XL® (Na/K/Ca nitrate)	
Chemical composition (%wt)	NaNO ₃ / KNO ₃ / Ca(NO ₃) ₂ (15 / 43 / 42)
Density [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$\rho = 2240 - 0.827 \cdot T$
Dynamic Viscosity [cP] vs. temperature [°C]	$\mu = 509611 \cdot T^{-2.072}$
Thermal conductivity [$\frac{W}{\circ C \cdot m}$]	$k \cong 0.519$ (constant in the operative range)
Heat capacity [$\frac{kJ}{\circ C \cdot kg}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$c_p = 1.542 - 0.000322 \cdot T$
Thermal stability (max operation temperature)	≤ 425 °C
Liquidus temperature (initial solidification point)	~ 125 °C
Na/K/Li nitrate	
Chemical composition (%wt)	NaNO ₃ / KNO ₃ / LiNO ₃ (18 / 45 / 37)
Density [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$\rho = 2051 - 0.6639 \cdot T$
Dynamic Viscosity [cP] vs. temperature [°C]	$\mu = 58725 \cdot T^{-1.69}$
Thermal conductivity [$\frac{W}{\circ C \cdot m}$]	$k = 0.0005 \cdot T + 0.4$

Heat capacity [$\frac{kJ}{\text{°C}\cdot\text{kg}}$] vs. temperature [°C]	$c_p = 1.5395 + 0.0003 \cdot T$
Thermal stability (max operation temperature)	600 °C
Liquidus temperature (initial solidification point)	120 °C

Figure 2 shows a comparison between the thermo-physical properties of the HTFs considered within their respective operating temperature ranges; moreover, the volumetric densities have been estimated, considering sensible heat release and average values for densities and heat capacities in the respective operation ranges: 290-550 °C for the Solar Salt; 200-530 °C for Hitec®; 200-425 °C for Hitec XL®; 200-550 °C for Na/K/Li nitrate.

Figure 2. Comparison between the densities a), the dynamic viscosities (b), the heat capacities (c) and the volumetric energy densities (d) of the four salts, in the respective operation ranges: 290-550 °C for the Solar Salt; 200-530 °C for Hitec®; 200-425 °C for Hitec XL®; 200-550 °C for Na/K/Li nitrate (source: [77]).

Besides thermo-physical properties, an assessment of different HTF solutions includes the assessment of **corrosion issues** towards steel components of the CSP plant such as pipes, valves, tanks, welding joints, etc. Specifically, molten nitrates show some drawbacks linked to the degradation of nitrates into nitrites, with possible oxygen generation, when the fluid is heated 295 °C [79]

Studies carried out so far on steel corrosion with mixtures of molten nitrates are not adequately systematic. Furthermore, these tests sometime provide contradictory results; there are no validated/shared methods for carrying out the corrosion tests.

From the results available in the open literature, it can be concluded that less expensive carbon steels may be employed for mixtures operating at low temperatures (200-400 °C), while for higher temperatures (400-600 °C), special stainless steels or alloys containing nickel, which have a higher corrosion resistance, should be considered [80].

Toxicity and environmental compatibility are clearly major issues for large-scale utilization of heat transfer materials. MS are safe and in general not toxic. However, nitrites and lithium can also be harmful for the humans and the environment, and the thermal decomposition of nitrates and nitrites can lead to the formation of nitrogen oxides [78].

From the comparison proposed in this document, it is possible to assess that [77]:

- the commercial MS mixture Hitec[®] is characterized by the presence of sodium nitrite and shows a relatively low freezing point together with good features concerning specific heat, density and viscosity. However, this material is toxic and less thermally stable than the solar salt under air [78];
- an interesting alternative is represented by the MS mixture composed by calcium, potassium, and sodium nitrates, Hitec XL[®] [81]. However, the viscosity is much higher than the one of the Solar Salt, especially at temperatures approaching the freezing point, while its thermal stability in presence of air is similar to the one of Hitec[®] [78];
- The addition of lithium nitrate significantly decreases the freezing point of the MS mixture while, at the same time, similar thermo-physical properties and stability of the solar salt can be obtained [78]. However, cost and availability of lithium can represent an issue for its utilization in CSP plants with large-scale TES capacity.

4 THERMO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES FOR PRODUCTION HYDROGEN AND SYNGAS

For several decades, the use of hydrogen as an energy carrier, and not only as a raw material in the process industry, has been considered as a potential key element in facilitating the transition process towards the decarbonisation of energy systems. This interest is motivated by the fact that the combustion of hydrogen is not associated with the production of carbon dioxide and the same gas can be used in fuel cells to produce electrochemically electricity, with much higher efficiencies than thermal combustion.

Currently, most hydrogen is used in industrial process and is produced from fossils, with an associated huge amount of CO₂ emission (about 8 tons per 1 ton of obtained hydrogen) [82]. These emissions are due both to the chemical reactions that characterise the hydrogen formation process, and to the combustion of carbonaceous sources, which is necessary to thermally support the process. For the use of hydrogen as an energy vector to be fully sustainable, carbon dioxide emissions must be reduced, and the integration of renewable sources into production processes is a fundamental requirement to achieve this. In particular, the use of solar energy is one of the main options currently being considered.

Figure 3 shows a diagram of the main processes for producing hydrogen and syngas using water and/or a carbon source (fossil or biological) as the primary source and can be operated with high-temperature heat and/or electricity, depending on the type of process considered.

Figure 3. Processes for hydrogen and syngas production.

Currently, there are two main approaches for the hydrogen production, depending on the primary source used. In a first case, conventional production processes based on the **transformation of carbonaceous feedstock** (e.g., steam reforming of natural gas) with the renewable source used to thermally support the process. Unless the carbon source is of renewable origin (e.g., biogas or biomethane) and a CO₂ capture system is provided, this approach does not completely solve the emissions problem, but it does, however, allow for important environmental sustainability benefits. First, emissions are significantly reduced by replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy; furthermore, by carrying out fuel decarbonization at the centralized level, where it is easier to achieve CO₂ capture, distributed emissions at the level of individual utilities are avoided. Another key aspect is related to the possibility of using processes widely established in the chemical industry, which are suitable for large-scale production. In this way, the use of renewable sources in industrial

hydrogen production can be encouraged with a view to more radical process transformation. A second approach is based on the **production of hydrogen from water** using, exclusively, renewable energy sources, to obtain a totally carbon-free fuel, i.e., free of carbon dioxide emissions, both in the production and use phase.

Another classification is based on the type of process involved:

- **Thermochemical processes**, which demand thermal energy at temperature, generally between 500 and 1000 °C. Most conventional production processes from carbonaceous feedstock, such as steam reforming and gasification, belong to this category. Another very interesting and potentially quite promising thermal route is represented by the so-called water splitting thermochemical cycles (WSTC), developed since the 70's.
- **Electrochemical processes**, which mainly use electrical energy. These are essentially the electrolysis of (liquid) water, a process that has long been used in industry, although currently insignificant in terms of overall installed production capacity. Nowadays alkaline electrolysis and PEM cells are the most commercialized options, generally directly or indirectly coupled with PV systems.
- A third alternative represented by **hybrid processes**, which use a non-negligible share of both electricity and heat. These processes can be coupled with PV and CSP. Interesting examples are hybrid WSTC cycles and high temperature electrolysis (with solid oxides cells, SOEC), which is potentially more efficient than alkaline or PEM processes.

4.1 Steam electrolysis and Thermo(-electro-)chemical Cycles

Nowadays, the most widespread technology is water electrolysis, preferably integrated in a renewable energy production grid. Currently, the electrolysis plants installed in Europe account for 24 MW from solar sources and 500 MW from wind energy. Regarding a further development of this methodology, some problems are still present and, in particular, it would be necessary to reduce investment cost and increase the electrolyser lifetime [83]. Moreover, another issue is the resistance under numerous start and stop cycles.

Regarding the other routes, pilot plants up to a TRL of 5-6 have been developed for thermochemical and hybrid water splitting cycles, and also for steam reforming [84]. Almost always the renewable source is from CSP, and, in this respect, the integration with high temperature storage systems represents a major challenge.

Regarding water electrolysis, the production costs can be evaluated at about 5-6 €/kg, for plants connected to electric grid, with a target of 1-3 €/kg [85]. Off-grid productions present instead significant higher costs, of around 8-10 €/kg.

Regarding thermochemical cycles, given the absence of industrial plants, their production costs can be just estimated through techno-economic analyses. FCH-JU reported 10 €/kg in 2017, with the target to reach 8 e 6 €/kg for, respectively, 2020 and 2023 [MAWP] [86]. Similar values are also expected for high temperature electrolysis.

Steam reforming coupled with CSP presents more promising results, in fact, from the data obtained with a pilot plant, it was possible to establish costs below 4 €/kg for hydrogen and electric-power co-production [85].

The following is a brief description of the main processes.

4.1.1 High-Temperature Electrolysis

In high temperature electrolysis, water is heated by an external heat source, entering the electrolytic cell in the form of steam, to promote the decomposition of the water molecule (see Figure 4):

Figure 4. Schematic representation of HT-Electrolysis process.

One possible heat source is Concentrated Solar Power. The high radiative fluxes allow operation at desired temperatures (600-800 °C). Figure 5 shows a schematic representation of a possible P&ID of the process.

Figure 5. Schematic P&ID of a CSP-HTE process, adapted from [87].

As a reference, it is possible to obtain efficiency⁴ values in the order of 52.6% at 0.4 MPa and 800 °C [87]. More recently, some companies with “Sunfire” reported conversion values of 84% in practical tests (PCI H₂ to AC current) [88]

In comparison with conventional electrolysis, HTE can present the following benefits:

- This process requires lower working voltages (<1 V vs standard 1.23 V) due to the energy contribution of the thermal component ($\Delta H = \Delta G + T\Delta S$) (see Figure 6);

⁴ The hydrogen production efficiency is defined as the ratio between the higher heating value of hydrogen and the sum of the gross electrical energy and the thermal energy to produce the hydrogen.

- This process allows the combination with feedstock (e.g., biomass) at high temperature to react with oxygen ions. In practice, part of this energy from this feedstock is used to “assist” the electrolysis process and thus reduce hydrogen production costs [89].

Figure 6. In HTE process the ΔH value has a contribution from $T\Delta S$ hence reducing the working voltages necessary when compared to conventional electrolysis.

4.1.2 Water splitting thermochemical cycles (WSTC)

Water splitting thermochemical cycles (WSTC) are multi-step processes where chemical intermediates are cyclically consumed and regenerated, water is the only inlet species, and hydrogen and oxygen the only products [90].

Each of the cycle step occurs at a different temperature, with a maximum level between 800 °C and 1500 °C. The processes with a maximum temperature below 1000 °C are of particular interest, given their feasibility to be coupled with CSP and IV generation nuclear reactor, like HTGR (High Temperature Gas Reactor).

The research on WSTC was focused on processes compatible with the temperatures available from concentrating solar plants and the MS mixtures. In particular, ENEA was directly involved in the investigation of 3 thermochemical cycles (Table 3), developing both lab scale experimental facilities and simulation models. The **sulfur-iodine** and the **modified sulfur-iodine** processes were studied in the national project FISR-TEPSI (Tecnologie e Processi innovativi per affrontare la transizione e preparare il futuro del Sistema Idrogeno) and in the EU HyCycles (Materials and components for hydrogen production by sulphur based thermochemical cycles) [91–93], while **ferrites** were considered within Project INNOHYP (Innovative high temperature routes for Hydrogen Production) [94].

Table 3. Main characteristics of thermochemical cycles for hydrogen production.

Process	No. of steps ⁵	Reactions ⁶	Pros (+) & Cons (-)	Ref.
Sulfur-iodine	3	$2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2 + \text{SO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{HI}$ <p>(Bunsen reaction, 20-120 °C)</p> $2\text{HI} \rightleftharpoons \text{I}_2 + \text{H}_2$ <p>(300-500 °C)</p> $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{SO}_2 + 1/2 \text{O}_2$ <p>(800-1000 °C)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Liquid or gaseous intermediates (easily manageable in chemical plants) + Use of commonly available chemical species - Complex and numerous separation steps - High corrosive intermediates - Presence of iodide and iodide based compounds - The second and third reaction generally requires catalysts 	[91,92]
Modified sulfur-iodine (NIS)	5	$2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2 + \text{SO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{HI}$ <p>(Bunsen reaction, 20-120 °C)</p> $\text{Ni} + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{NiSO}_4 + \text{H}_2$ <p>(20-100 °C)</p> $\text{NiSO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{NiO} + \text{SO}_2 + 1/2 \text{O}_2$ <p>(≈900°C)</p> $\text{NiO} + 2\text{HI} \rightarrow \text{NiI}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ <p>(≈100 °C)</p> $\text{NiI}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni} + \text{I}_2$ <p>(≈600 °C)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Less corrosive intermediate + All reactions with high rates, near to 100%, without the necessity of catalysts + Possibility to easily store, if necessary, intermediate compounds - Numerous separation steps - Toxic compounds if Nickel is used 	[93]
Mixed-ferrites	2	$2\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4 (\text{s}) + 3\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 (\text{s}) + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons 6\text{Na}(\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{Fe}_{2/3})\text{O}_2(\text{s}) + 3\text{CO}_2(\text{g}) + \text{H}_2(\text{g})$ $6\text{Na}(\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{Fe}_{2/3})\text{O}_2(\text{s}) + 3\text{CO}_2(\text{g}) \rightleftharpoons 2\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4 (\text{s}) + 3\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 (\text{s}) + 0.5\text{O}_2$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + In principle, only gas-solid reactions, with easy separation processes + Reactions temperature below 800°C if ferrites nano-particles (2-20 nm) are used - Costly materials preparation - Necessity to operate with water excess in the first step, leading to high energy consuming operations for recovering pure hydrogen (unless proper separation membranes are developed) 	[94]

⁵ Excluding separation steps.⁶ In all cases, summing up all steps it is obtained water splitting: $\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2 + 1/2 \text{O}_2$.

The **sulfur-iodine cycle** has the advantage to be based on liquid or gaseous intermediates, which are readily transportable in a chemical reaction plant. The major drawbacks are complex separative processes and the issues regarding corrosion. In particular, the *Bunsen reaction* needs to be performed with a large excess of iodine in order to separate sulfuric acid and hydriodic acid solutions; the former is still purified and concentrated by heating [95] and the latter undergoes to another separation process (typically, an energetically expensive distillation [96]) to remove iodine from HI. In the most common schemes, sulfuric acid resulted at a concentration of around 80wt% [91], while hydriodic acid is obtained at the azeotropic composition (57wt%) [91]. Both acids are then thermally decomposed [97–99], and in both cases a heterogeneous catalyst is needed in order to operate with acceptable temperatures and reaction rates. Another problem is represented by the limited thermodynamic conversion for HI cracking [91].

Some of the concerns presented by the sulfur-iodine process may be overcome employing oxides, sulfates and iodides as intermediates (**modified sulfur iodine**) [93,100] This alternative route was validated using nickel compounds, as described in Table 3. Hydrogen is quantitatively produced reacting metallic nickel with sulfuric acid, avoiding the necessity of catalysis. The obtained sulfate is decomposed at around 900 °C into nickel oxide, sulfur dioxide (to be reused in the Bunsen section) and oxygen. Then, it is necessary to retrieve metallic nickel, and that can be done forming nickel iodide (from NiO plus HI) and decomposing that salt into iodine (recycled into the Bunsen reactor) and elemental nickel. Overall, there are clear advantages regarding the thermodynamic yield of each phase, the use of acids only at low temperatures (improving corrosion issues), the absence of catalysts and the possibility to store intermediate products also for long times. On the other hand, the number of steps is increased, and nickel compounds are quite toxic.

A totally different approach is exemplified by the **mixed-ferrite cycle**; in the example reported in Table 3 both steps can be carried out below 800 °C [94,101]. While in the routes like sulfur-iodine or similar commonly available chemicals are employed, in these processes nanostructured mixed oxides are a posteriori synthesized. As a result, only gas solid reactions are present, thus simplifying the necessary equipment and the separation processes. The disadvantages are the high preparation cost for ferrites and the necessity, in the first step, to operate with a large excess of steam with respect to the stoichiometry; this leads to the problem of separating the produced hydrogen from a substantial amount of water and, unless proper separation membrane will be developed, to a drastic decrease of the global cycle efficiency.

4.1.3 Hybrid thermochemical cycles

In these processes water is split into hydrogen and oxygen using different types of energy sources, such as solar, electricity, biomass combustion and so on.

Likely, the most investigated hybrid method is the so-called **Westinghouse cycle**, which is a simplification of sulfur-iodine where nothing changes regarding oxygen production, while hydrogen is formed by electrolysis of a SO₂ aqueous solution (SO₂ depolarized electrolysis, SDE), where sulfuric acid is produced at the anode and hydrogen at the cathode. With respect to a direct water electrolysis, the oxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide is thermodynamically more favourable than O²⁻ oxidation and, actually, the SDE process can be carried out saving from 40 to 75% of electric power with respect to alkaline H₂O electrolysis [102,103]. In this contest, ENEA was a partner in the SOL2HY2 (Solar To Hydrogen Hybrid Cycles) EU project, where it was mainly involved in developing a proper catalyst to be used in a solar reactor present at the DLR Centre of Juelich [104]. An important aspect of the project was to study the feasibility of using SO₂ from industrial wastes to feed the cycle in periods with insufficient solar irradiation. In this regard, ENEA developed simulation tools to

investigate the coupling of the process with storage systems based on molten nitrates, and the possibility to use contemporary a central tower receiver and a parabolic trough plant in order to ensure the continuity of hydrogen production.

Another, and very peculiar, alternative hybrid route is represented by the **sulfur-ammonia cycle**, where the disproportionation of the ammonium sulfite intermediate, thermodynamically spontaneous under the reaction conditions, is catalysed with the energy of light photons and the presence of photocatalytic materials. ENEA participated in the validation of this cycle, in particular regarding the thermal part of the process, in the framework of the national funding scheme PRIN2019 [105].

Both processes are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Main characteristics of hybrid thermochemical cycles for hydrogen production.

<i>Process</i>	<i>No. of steps⁷</i>	<i>Reactions⁸</i>	<i>Pros (+) & Cons (-)</i>	<i>Ref.</i>
Westinghose process	2	$\text{SO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2$ <p>(electrochemical, T < 100 °C)</p> $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{SO}_2 + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$ <p>(T ≈ 850 °C)</p>	<p>+ No iodide and iodide compounds are present</p> <p>+ Easier separation procedures than the “sulfur-iodine” process</p> <p>- Issues regarding the efficiency of the electrolysis step</p>	[102,103]
Sulfur-ammonia cycle	3+1 (SO ₂ , NH ₃ absorption in water)	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2$ <p>(photocatalytical, T < 100 °C)</p> $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \rightleftharpoons 2 \text{NH}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{SO}_3$ <p>(T≈400 – 500 °C)</p> $\text{SO}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{SO}_2 + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$ <p>(T ≈ 850 °C)</p> $\text{SO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NH}_3 \rightleftharpoons (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_3$ <p>(T < 100 °C)</p>	<p>+ No iodide and iodide compounds are present</p> <p>+ No necessity of electric power</p> <p>- Photocatalytic hydrogen production is quite slow</p>	[105,106]

4.2 Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstocks

4.2.1 Steam reforming

The Methane Steam Reforming (SMR) process is the most widely used industrial process for producing hydrogen [107]. It is a chemical process commonly carried out at temperatures above 850 °C, in furnaces fired by fossil fuels.

SMR consists essentially of two gas-phase catalytic reactions between steam and methane:

⁷ Excluding separation steps.

⁸ In all cases, summing up all steps it is obtained water splitting: $\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2 + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$.

The reaction (1) of steam reforming of desulfurized natural gas is strongly endothermic and is usually carried out at 800-1000 °C in furnaces fired with raw natural gas. In contrast, reaction (2), which maximizes the hydrogen yield, and is known as water-gas shift reaction (WGS), is exothermic and therefore favoured at lower temperatures (200-450 °C). The hydrogen produced is subsequently separated from the gas mixture by pressure swing adsorption (PSA), while CO₂ can be captured by adsorption in aqueous amino-alkali solutions. A process diagram of methane steam reforming is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of the methane Steam Reforming process, adapted from [108].

4.2.2 Gasification

The biomass gasification represents a way to increase the use of biomass for energy production, permitting widespread use of biomass [109–111]. It consists of the conversion of solid/liquid organic compounds, in which partial oxidation of the carbon in the feedstock occurs, leading to the formation of a phase into a gas/vapor phase and a solid phase: the gas phase, otherwise called synthesis gas or syngas, can be used for power generation or can be upgraded for the biofuel production; the solid phase (char) includes the unconverted organic fraction and ash. During gasification process the carbonaceous biomass is converted into syngas, a mixture consisting mainly of hydrogen (H₂), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄). This is generally carried out in the presence of a suitable gasifying agent or oxidants, such as air, oxygen, steam, or carbon dioxide.

In the process, 4 main steps can be distinguished:

- Oxidation (exothermic);
- Drying (endothermic);
- Pyrolysis (endothermic);
- Reduction (endothermic).

The classification of gasification is based on several parameters such as types of gasifiers, gasification temperature, heating (direct or indirect), and gasifying agent. According to the biomass, gasification technology and operating conditions [112–115], the Lowest Heating Value (LHV) of syngas can vary from 4 to 13 MJ/Nm³, while the LHV of char can range from 25 to 30 MJ/kg.

Gasification reactors are classified into three main categories [116]: cross-flow reactors (> 50 MW_{th}), fluidized bed reactors (5-100 MW_{th}) and fixed bed reactors (100-10000 kW_{th}). The former requires a very high temperature (2000 °C), pure oxygen and steam as a gasifying agent in addition to high-quality fuels, so this category does not seem the best solution for a coupling with MS technologies. Regarding the fluidized bed reactors, which is certainly effective when high exchange

coefficients are required and where the fluidization fluid coincides with the heat transfer fluid, the associated technological difficulties and high costs make it convenient for CSPs to apply this solution only to large plants ($> 100 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$). In addition, since fluidized bed reactors have an operating temperature of $700\text{-}800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ throughout the reactor, it would not be feasible to combine them with a commercial CSP plant, which can only supply heat up to a maximum temperature of $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (using MS as the thermal fluid). The fixed bed reactors, on the other hand, works at temperatures between $800\text{-}1400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with low reaction rates, is the most common (78 percent) [116].

Briefly, reactors in this category can be classified into 3 types, differentiated by the modes of gas phase efflux: up-draft, cross-draft and down-draft.

The up-draft reactor ($1\text{-}10 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$) is the simplest type, has a maximum flow rate of about 4 t/h with strict grain size requirements (Figure 8). Biomass enters from the top while the gasification agent inlet is at the base of the reactor. Above the inlet, the gasification agent finds the grid where biomass that has already released volatiles is oxidized. In this zone, it is possible to exceed $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This phase promotes both the formation of ash, which precipitates through the grate and is collected at the bottom, and the production of hot gases. Moving upward, heat is transferred to the zone where the reduction process takes place. Further up, the hot gases meet the pyrolysis zone, where volatile components are released, and then the drying zone, where the biomass is dehydrated. At this point, the gases exit at $200\text{-}300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This type of reactor has a high thermal efficiency, but a syngas with a high tar content is obtained because pyrolysis occurs in the part of the reactor where the volume is not large enough to guarantee contact times at high and adequate temperatures to ensure the reduction and thermal cracking reactions, also due to the lowering of temperature due to the evaporation of the water in the biomass.

Figure 8. Diagram of up-draft reactor (source: [117]).

In the cross-draft reactor (Figure 9), the air flow crosses the biomass, which is fed from the top of the reactor and exits from the bottom. In the zone where air is injected as the oxidizing agent, some of the oxidation and reduction reactions occur due to the high temperatures reached. Heat received in the proximity passes (mainly by conduction) to the pyrolysis and drying zones, concentric to the central zone, where very high temperatures can be reached ($1500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [118]), while at the gas outlet the temperature is about $800\text{-}900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [116]. Tar production is very low ($0.01\text{-}0.1 \text{ g/Nm}^3$) and ash is collected at the bottom of the reactor. The technical difficulties and small size of this type of reactor, combined with the lower conversion efficiency, limit its widespread use.

Figure 9. Diagram of cross-draft reactor (source: [119]).

The down-draft reactor (Figure 10) is the one most used, especially for small sizes, from a few tens to a few hundred thermal kW. In this case, the gaseous stream, consisting of water and the vapours produced by the drying and initial thermal degradation processes of biomass, coming from the top of the reactor, flows down in the same direction of the solid fuel. The output in the pyrolysis zone, with its high tar content, passes through the zone where part of the fuel is burned and where a temperature of 1200-1400 °C is reached [118]. This area is where thermal cracking occurs and where the chemical reactions of many reactants begin, which also take place in the lower part of the reactor. In fact, char, gaseous hydrocarbons, and tars react with steam at high temperature with endothermic reactions to give CO and H₂, processes also favoured by the presence of alkaline-earth compounds that catalyse reforming reactions. As a result of these thermochemical processes, the tar content present in the syngas can vary in the range of 0.015-3.0 g/Nm³, in contrast to 30-150 g/Nm³ obtained in the up-draft reactors. On the other hand, the amount of particulate in the syngas at the outlet is much higher than in the other configurations. This is because the gas, as it leaves the reactor through the bottom, passes through the support grid along with ash and dust, which remain suspended in the gaseous stream. The gas stream, which is heated by the oxidation zone, in this case does not pass through the drying and pyrolysis zones, which result in lower thermal efficiency (in addition to the need to use biomass with low moisture content). In this configuration, drying, pyrolysis and gasification zones are well separated, so the gas does not heat the pyrolysis reactions, which can be powered by solar energy up to a temperature of 500 °C. This aspect will be important for matching with the solar system under consideration.

Figure 10. Diagram of down-draft reactor (source: [120]).

4.2.3 Hydrothermal Gasification

Unlike the reforming and dry gasification, hydrothermal gasification is a biomass conversion process where relatively lower temperatures (around 600 °C versus 800-1200 °C) and significantly higher pressures (above 25 MPa) are used [121–123]. The water is used as reaction medium, and this technology is suitable for wet biomasses and organic wastes, avoiding the costly drying step of the feedstock.

Hydrothermal gasification processes can be classified, according to the reaction temperatures, into:

- **Aqueous phase reforming**, with temperatures ranging from 215 °C to 265 °C, if the feedstock concentration is very low (about 1%), it is thermodynamically possible to obtain hydrogen. The main output products are H₂ and CO₂. Subcritical conditions are not suitable for gasifying high molecular weight constituents like lignin or cellulose [124–126].
- **Near critical gasification**, with temperatures ranging from 350 °C to 400 °C. Biomass is gasified at near critical gasification conditions to obtain high degrees of carbon conversion to methane [127].
- **Supercritical water gasification (SCWG)**, with temperature higher than 374 °C (usually higher than 500 °C) to obtain H₂ and CO₂ as main products. This process shows high conversion rates; however, it is highly dependable on factors like operation conditions, feedstock, the nature of the catalyst (if used) or the reactor design. In the gasification, supercritical water has a twofold role as a reactant and medium of biomass. Under supercritical conditions, an optimal environment is created for hydrolysis and pyrolysis reactions due to the generation of H⁺ and OH⁻ ions [126]. In addition, free radicals are generated enhancing the gas formation, leading to the high gas yield [127]. Due to the higher solubility and reactivity of organic compounds in supercritical water, SCWG produces less tar and char as a byproduct, in comparison with conventional dry gasification. This has a dual benefit: tar and char are difficult to gasify; on the other hand, they cause a reduction in the energy efficiency of the process by means of reactor plugging, heat exchanger fouling, and catalyst deactivation [128].

4.2.4 Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is a thermochemical process (see Figure 11) that transforms material such as wood, agroforestry, or plastic waste, in gaseous, liquid and solid compounds, without the presence of oxygen. Depending on the operating conditions, pyrolysis process can occur at temperatures between 200 °C and 1000 °C and pressures up to 100 bar.

Figure 11. A schematic representation of pyrolysis thermochemical process.

Outputs vary with process and feedstock conditions. In general, it can be said that there are three main outputs [129]:

- Biochar (10-30%);
- Bio-oil (20-50%);
- Syngas (20-30%).

Pyrolysis process can occur under three major operating conditions: slow pyrolysis, intermediate pyrolysis and fast/flash pyrolysis [130]. Table 5 shows a summary of the features of each operating condition.

Table 5. Operating conditions for pyrolysis processes.

Operating condition	Operating temperature	Residence time	Main output	Compatibility with use of MS
Slow pyrolysis	200-400 °C	5-30 min	Biochar	Yes, if above 290°C
Intermediate pyrolysis	400-600 °C	1-5 min	Bio-oil	Yes, if up to 565°C
Fast/flash pyrolysis	600-1000 °C	1-2 s	Syngas	No

CSP technologies can be coupled to such processes as through their concentration factor such operating temperatures can be achieved and, eventually, increase the Lower Heating Value of the produced syngas by a factor of 1.4-1.9 [131].

Operating costs are relatively difficult to identify in the literature as they depend on the intended output and operating conditions. However, it is possible to state costs between €75-300 per ton of oil (12-54 €/MWh), assuming a feedstock cost between 0-100 €/t (0-1.9 €/GJ) [129].

On the other hand, a recent NREL study for a 550 metric ton/day dry wood fast/flash pyrolysis plant, producing 106 million liters of bio-oil per year, concluded that the capital cost is 46M€ and the operating cost will be 9.1 M€/year (based on product value of 0.16€/l) [132].

It is also important to note that pyrolysis process can be combined with other thermochemical processes, as shown in Figure 12 [133]. The advantage of such combination is to diversify and/or increase the efficiency of biomass waste conversion in multiple outputs such as hydrogen, fuels, heat power, etc.

Figure 12. Pyrolysis process can be combined with other thermochemical processes for the production of multiple outputs. In this case, a flow-chart of a possible thermochemical conversion process for lignocellulosic biomass is presented (source: [133]).

Regarding methane containing mixtures (e.g. natural gas, biogas, biomethane), pyrolysis methodologies can be considered as ways to produce hydrogen with zero CO₂ emissions, without the necessity to use systems for carbon dioxide capture [134]. Actually, these processes allow a straightforward coupling with HTF and TES used in CSP, and lead to a direct separation of carbon and H₂, where the former can be stored in the solid state, and, if valuable products are obtained, placed on the market. This way, the usual “carbon sequestration” route can be replaced by “carbon valorisation” methods [135,136].

Among the different possible approaches, a very innovative and interesting one is to perform the pyrolysis reaction directly in molten bath, made of liquid metals or MS (typically chlorides) [137]. It is so avoided the employment, and possible poisoning, of catalysts, and the carbonaceous products can be readily recovered from above the surface of the melt [138].

In this contest, the C-zero consortium realized a TRL 6 plant utilizing the KCl/MnCl₂ mixture at 1000 °C and 1 bar and obtaining graphite-like carbon as a co-product [139]. Molten metals were instead used at 1120 °C and 1 bar by Ember-TNO, with the formation of carbon black [140].

4.2.5 Hydrothermal Liquefaction

Hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) is a thermochemical conversion process that transforms wet biomass in liquid biofuel, known as bio-oil. The process takes place at temperature and high pressure, in the presence of water [141]. Figure 13 shows the operating temperature range of HTL process.

Figure 13. HTL process occurs in temperature range of 250–400 °C. After the critical point the process enters in a gasification zone where higher gas yields are achieved (source: [142]).

Hydrothermal processes may be carried out under a wide range of conditions. At low temperatures (75 °C, 15 bar), a process known as steam explosion occurs, which produces an increment in chemical reactivity and can be seen as a pretreatment step to separate biomass into its major components for further bioprocessing. As the temperature increases the macromolecules of biomass (cellulose and lignin) break up to produce shorter molecules. This leads to hydrothermal carbonization, which occurs at temperatures of 180–250 °C and under pressures of 20–100 bar. However, some fragments polymerize to produce oily substances, which is known as hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL). At pressures from 50 to 200 bar and temperatures in the range of 200–374 °C, this is the dominant process. Finally, above the critical point of water, the gaseous products like methane, carbon dioxide and hydrogen predominate in a process called supercritical water gasification (SCWG). If the main interest is to produce hydrogen, temperatures and pressures above 600 °C and 300 bar, respectively, are needed.

Due to the high thermal capacity of the biomass-water mixture, Hydrothermal processes (HTPs) have higher energy requirements than other transformation processes, like pyrolysis of dry biomass (when the drying heat is not accounted for). Therefore, the possibility of providing this heat through solar energy is very attractive. A few small-scale experimental studies have been carried out with solar reactors for steam explosion, hydrothermal carbonization, HTL, and SCWG. Solar technologies include parabolic troughs, parabolic dishes, and solar furnaces, utilized to irradiate the high-pressure reactors' walls. From the point of view of scalability, however, theoretical studies have emphasized a different option, indirect heating, where a thermal fluid is first heated in the solar field and then used to heat the reactor. No practical demonstrations of this concept have been reported.

Among the hydrothermal processes described above, HTL and SCWG are well suited to the operation temperature of solar MS. In fact, CSP technologies can be used as heat source of the process, but the use of MS requires a minimum temperature of 290 °C.

Likewise, pyrolysis process, cost assessment is not totally clear in the literature. However, it is possible to claim that MFSP (Minimum Fuel Selling Price) of bio-oil is around 2.07 €/kg [143].

5 TECHNO-ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT FOR MS-DRIVEN PROCESSES OF RENEWABLE GAS PRODUCTION

5.1 Identification of MS-driven processes of renewable gas production

In CSP plants for electricity generation, direct solar radiation is reflected, concentrated, and converted into high-temperature heat. The thermal energy is then converted to electricity through the use of thermodynamic cycles: in most of the plants nowadays, solar energy is transferred to a heat transfer fluid (HTF) that feeds a steam generator integrated in a Rankine cycle, similar to conventional thermal power plants. The intermediate step of heat generation allows not only to produce electricity, but also to feed heat-demanding processes, for industrial and civil uses, and to schedule electricity generation through technologically mature thermal energy storage (TES) systems, with a view to dispatchable generation, which to date cannot be pursued through other renewable energy technologies [144]. For this purpose, the MS technologies are well suitable for use in CSP plant in combination with thermal energy storage (TES), since MS can be used both as a heat transfer fluid and as a storage medium.

Although renewable energy sources (RES) are some of the interesting and promising solutions for the transition to sustainable energy systems in the future, their main problem is their intermittent nature and fluctuations of their production, which makes it difficult to control and schedule them. Hence, the use of TES increases the reliability and facilitates the integration of RES, allowing electricity and/or heat release whenever necessary in order to solve the demand–supply problem and to match peak demand. Therefore, MS can act as an interface for the constant supply of renewable (high temperature) heat from multiple sources to industrial processes. In particular, Figure 14 shows a conceptual diagram of integration between RES and a MS-TES system to provide heat and electricity to processes for hydrogen and syngas production, presented in the Section 4.

Figure 14. A conceptual diagram of integration between Renewable Energy Sources and a MS-TES system to provide heat and electricity to processes for hydrogen and syngas production.

The following are brief assessments for the feasibility of MS-driven processes for gas production, giving attention to heat supply. Further details are reported in Table 6.

- **Solid oxide steam electrolysis:** the heat is required almost exclusively for process steam generation (~1 atm, ~100 °C). The electrolysis process itself is carried out in close-to-adiabatic conditions (thermoneutral potential) and the reactants are pre-heated mostly with heat recovered from the products. Co-electrolysis of H₂O and CO₂ may also be carried out with SOEC, which leads to the production of syngas. Quaternary MS mixtures can be used to supply heat for steam generation.
- **Molten carbonate steam electrolysis:** the heat is required almost exclusively for process steam generation (~1 atm, ~100 °C). The electrolysis process itself is carried out in close-to-adiabatic conditions (thermoneutral potential) and the reactants are pre-heated mostly with heat recovered from the products. CO₂ must be fed to the electrolyser but, overall, is not produced/consumed in the process. CO₂ separation and recirculation may be included to produce H₂ and O₂; alternatively, outlet H₂/CO₂ mixtures can be fed to other synthetic fuels production processes (e.g., methanol, methane, etc.). Quaternary MS mixtures can be used to supply heat for steam generation.
- **Sulfur-family cycles:** The highest-temperature step of these cycles (SO₃ decomposition) requires heat at 800-900 °C and cannot be served by current commercial MS mixtures. Direct irradiation is currently used to solarize this step. Chloride salts could be considered in the future. Solar salt and other lower-freezing commercial mixtures can be used to supply heat to other process steps, namely: sulfuric acid concentration and SA vaporization and decomposition. Further integration point can be available for specific cycles of this family.
- **Sulfur-iodine cycle:** All information related to sulfur-family cycles can be applied; furthermore, MS can be used to supply heat to the Hydriodic acid decomposition (endothermic stage, at 300-450 °C): $2\text{HI}(\text{aq}, \text{g}) \rightarrow \text{I}_2(\text{g}) + \text{H}_2(\text{g})$.
- **Non-volatile metal oxide cycles:** due to the very high temperatures of the high-temperature step, no MS mixtures are available for direct heat supply. Currently, only direct irradiation is considered to supply the processes with solar energy. MS could be considered for heat recovery/thermal buffering/reactant pre-heating in some part of the plant.
- **Mixed ferrite:** some processes like mixed ferrites may require CO₂ separation processes, which require heat at ~100-200 °C and could be served with MS.
- **Cu-Cl cycle:** This is a 4-step hybrid cycle. The highest-temperature thermochemical step is carried out at 530 °C and can be served with Solar Salt:
 - $\text{CuOCl}_2(\text{s}) \rightarrow 2 \text{CuCl}(\text{molten}) + 0.5 \text{O}_2(\text{g})$, Thermolysis (endothermic)
- **Steam Reforming:** the conventional high-temperature process is operated at temperature higher than 800 °C by using gas-fired furnaces, consequently no MS mixture is employable; in order to enable its integration, the steam reforming process can be modified. Further details are reported in paragraph 5.3.
- **Gasification:** In the down-draft reactor, the drying, pyrolysis, and gasification zones are well separated. In this case, the reactions in the pyrolysis step can be powered by MS up to a temperature of 500 °C.
- **Supercritical water gasification (SCWG):** in this process, the operating conditions (higher than 374 °C, usually up to 500 °C or above) are compatible with the use of binary Solar Salt.
- **Pyrolysis:** MS mixtures can be used to supply heat in the slow and intermediate pyrolysis process. Biomass can generically be chemically represented by C_xH_yO_z where the components x, y and z can be determined by the Total C/H/O (%m/m) divided by the respective MW_{C/H/O} (g/mol). Slow pyrolysis is characterized by the relatively low operational

temperature and longer heating rates values. In intermediate pyrolysis more connections C-C are broken and, therefore, there is tendency to have more bio-oil and syngas.

- **Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL):** in this process the temperatures are moderate (typically 200–400 °C), compatible with the operating temperatures of some MS mixtures.

For the electrolysis, after a thorough review of the literature, including from previous analyses and based on various works done by ENEA, the heat is required almost exclusively for process steam generation. For the current time this is not considered a priority, but nevertheless the process still has some interest, especially when coupled with CSP. In the future, this process will become interesting if electrolyzers that can operate at high pressure are developed: indeed, if the electrolysis can be carried out under pressure, the temperature required by the process will be higher and a MS-driven process can be envisaged.

The Methane Steam reforming for hydrogen production and olive oil mill wastewater steam reforming for syngas production have been considered as reference processes to carry out the techno-economic analysis.

Table 6. Remarks for the use of MS mixtures in processes for the production of hydrogen and syngas.

Process class	Process family	Process	Feedstock	Main Products	Process Temp.	Conventional Process Interface	MS Mixture ($T_{freeze}-T_{max}$)	MS Interface	Ref.
Steam electrolysis	Solid oxide steam electrolysis	Solid oxide steam electrolysis	H ₂ O (+CO ₂)	H ₂ , O ₂ , (CO)	600-800 °C	Steam generator (~100 °C)	Quaternary mixtures (coupling with CST plants using solar salt requires intermediate HTF)	Steam generator. Possibility to use salts from cold tank.	[145]
Steam electrolysis	Molten carbonate steam electrolysis	Molten carbonate steam electrolysis	H ₂ O (+CO ₂)	H ₂ , O ₂ (+CO ₂)	650 °C	Steam generator (~100 °C). Amine regeneration column reboiler if CO ₂ separation is included	Quaternary mixtures (coupling with CST plants using solar salt requires intermediate HTF)	Steam generator (and amine regeneration column reboiler, if included). Possibility to use salts from cold tank	[146,147]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	Up to >800 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C). In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	Sulfuric acid concentration reboiler (~200 °C), sulfuric acid vaporization and decomposition exchanger-reactor (300-500 °C)	[148]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	Hybrid sulfur (Westinghouse) cycle	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	800-900 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C). In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	Sulfuric acid concentration reboiler (~200 °C), sulfuric acid vaporization and decomposition exchanger-reactor (300-500 °C)	[102,104,149]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	Sulfur-Iodine cycle	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	800-900 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C). In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	Sulfuric acid concentration reboiler (~200 °C), Sulfuric acid vaporization, Decomposition exchanger-reactor (300-500 °C) and Separation of HI from I ₂ followed HI cracking (endothermic, at 300-450°C)	[150]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	S-A cycle	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	800-900 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C). In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	Sulfuric acid concentration reboiler (~200 °C), sulfuric acid vaporization, Decomposition exchanger-reactor (300-500 °C) and Ammonium sulfate decomposition (400-500 °C)	[151]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	Modified S-A cycle	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	800-900 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C).	Dehydration of metal sulfate (350-450 °C), and Ammonium sulfate decomposition (400-500 °C)	[105]

Process class	Process family	Process	Feedstock	Main Products	Process Temp.	Conventional Process Interface	MS Mixture ($T_{freeze}-T_{max}$)	MS Interface	Ref.
							In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used		
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Sulfur-family cycles	Modified Sulphur-Iodine with solid intermediates	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	900 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C). In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	Metal sulfate Pre-heating and dehydration (up to 500 °C) Metal iodide pre-heating and dehydration (up to 500 °C)	[100]-[152]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Non-volatile Metal oxide cycles	Non-volatile metal oxide cycles	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	>1000 °C	Not applicable	Solar Salt (240-565 °C)	MS could be considered for heat recovery/thermal buffering/reactant pre-heating in some part of the plant	[153]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Non-volatile Metal oxide cycles	Mixed ferrites	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	800 °C	Not applicable	In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	MS could be considered for H ₂ /CO ₂ separation from water excess	[154]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Metal halides based hybrid cycles	UT-3	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	760 °C	Not applicable	In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	MS could be considered for pre-heating regarding water splitting with HBr formation and Hydrogen formation from FeBr ₂	[155,156]
Thermo (-electro-) chemical Cycles	Metal halides based hybrid cycles	Cu-Cl Cycle	H ₂ O	H ₂ , O ₂	Up to 500 °C	Not applicable	Solar salt (240-565 °C)	Reactor for oxygen production 530 °C (configuration to be defined, e.g., jacketed reactor; integrated heat exchanger/coil; etc.)	[157]
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Steam Reforming	Low-temperature steam methane (or biogas) reforming	CH ₄ , (CO ₂), H ₂ O	H ₂ + Syngas	500-550 °C	Not applicable (the conventional high-temperature process is operated at T>800 °C by using gas-fired furnaces)	Solar Salt (240-565 °C)	Heat exchangers; Steam generators; integrated membrane reactors/heat exchangers	[158–160]
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Gasification	Gasification	Biomass Waste ⁹	H ₂ + Syngas	800-2000 °C	Fluidized bed and fixed bed reactors	Solar Salt (240-565 °C) In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	MS could be considered for feeding the reactions in the pyrolysis step (temperature up to 500 °C) in the down-draft reactors	[109–111]

⁹ Such as corn stover, sugarcane bagasse, straw, saw mill, etc

Process class	Process family	Process	Feedstock	Main Products	Process Temp.	Conventional Process Interface	MS Mixture ($T_{freeze}-T_{max}$)	MS Interface	Ref.
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Hydrothermal Gasification	Supercritical Water Gasification	Biomass Waste ⁹	H ₂ + CO ₂	374-500 °C Water Pressure > 25 MPa	Heat exchangers	Solar Salt (240-565 °C)	Heat exchangers; Steam generators;	[121,122]
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Hydrothermal Liquefaction	Hydrothermal Liquefaction	Wet Biomass Waste	Bio-oil	75-250 °C Water Pressure 1.5-10 MPa	Heat exchangers	Ternary Mixtures	Heat exchangers	[141,142]
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Biomass pyrolysis	Slow Pyrolysis	Biomass Waste ⁹	Typical output composition: Biochar (50%-70%), Bio-oil (20%-30%), Syngas (10-20%)	200-400 °C	One-stage pyrolysis process characterized by slow pyrolysis process (5 to 30 min)	Solar Salt (240-565 °C)	Heat exchangers; Steam generators; integrated membrane reactors/heat exchangers	[130]
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Biomass pyrolysis	Intermediate Pyrolysis	Biomass Waste ⁹	Typical output composition: Biochar (20%-30%), bio-oil (50%-70%), syngas (10%-20%)	400-600 °C	One-stage pyrolysis process characterized by intermediate pyrolysis process (1 to 5 min)	Solar Salt (240-565 °C)	Heat exchangers; Steam generators; integrated membrane reactors/heat exchangers	[130]
Thermochemical conversion of carbonaceous feedstock	Biomass pyrolysis	Fast or Flash Pyrolysis	Biomass Waste ⁹	Typical output composition: Biochar (15-40%), Bio-oil (15%-20%), Syngas (50%-70%)	600-1000 °C	One-stage pyrolysis process characterized by fast pyrolysis (< 2 seconds) or flash pyrolysis (<1 second)	In the future, Chlorides or other very-high-temperature mixtures could be used	Heat exchangers; integrated membrane reactors/heat exchangers	[161,162]

5.2 Methodology for LCOH estimation

Levelized Cost of Heat (LCoH) is one of the main economic indicators for comparing thermal energy production systems and processes. It includes the cost of capital expenditure (Capital Expenditure - CapEx) and operating and maintenance expenses (Operating Expenses). CAPEX, in this case, includes the cost of plant construction, i.e., the cost of all equipment (solar field, thermal energy storage, etc.), commissioning, engineering and supervision, civil mechanical and electrical works, instrumentation and controls, local services and contingency. In this techno-economic assessment, the costs of different equipment were evaluated from estimates of similar projects and/or specific manuals [], with prices possibly updated through CEPCI tables [163,164], industry reports [165,166] or scientific papers [167,168].

OpEx, on the other hand, is divided into a fixed part and a variable part with production. Fixed costs include all the expenses that the operator must incur to keep the production facility running and in efficient condition, even when it is not in operation. Fixed costs include:

- personnel expenses;
- expenses for routine and extraordinary maintenance;
- costs of insurance against damage to the plant due to internal or external events, including third-party liability coverage.

Variable costs, on the other hand, include the various items of operation and maintenance costs, which generally do not remain constant over the years of plant operation. This occurs mainly for the following reasons:

- as cumulative production increases, some structural components and moving parts are subject to deterioration and wear, requiring increased maintenance (corrosion aspects for example);
- especially in plants using innovative technologies, operational experience leads to progressively optimizing plant management and suggesting those plant modifications that improve overall performance as well as significantly reducing malfunctions and/or failures of critical components;
- need to reduce environmental impacts or restore healthy water or air conditions;
- partial or total replacement of certain consumables;
- consumption of fuels;
- consumption of electrical energy;
- thermal energy consumption.

In general, the variable costs for a CST system can be estimated at 1 €/MWh_{th} produced [166].

In this work, LCoH, calculated by applying the real discount rate, is evaluated through the relationship

$$LCoH = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{I_t + M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}}$$

where:

I_t : expenses due to initial investment at year t ;

M_t : expenses due to operation and maintenance at year t ;

F_t : expenses for fuel;

E_t : thermal energy generated at year t ;

r : real discount rate at year t , i.e., net of inflation;

N : useful life of the plant.

In this case I_t and M_t represent the CapEx and OpEx, respectively. CapEx may vary depending on the size, quality of supply and maturity of the technology. In this work, a Solar Parabolic Through Plant has been considered and the specific cost of the solar field, intended for total aperture reflective area, includes the cost of the mirrors, receiver tubes and structures of the parabolic trough plant and it was assumed as 200 €/m². The other specific costs and main parameters used in this economic assessment are shown in the Table 7. From the LCoH value obtained and expressed in €/kWh_{th}, it is then possible to determine the production cost of hydrogen (€/kg_{H2}) or syngas (€/Nm³), as appropriate.

Table 7. Specific costs and economic parameters used in techno-economic analyses.

Parameter	U.M.	Value
CAPEX		
PTC Solar field	€/m ²	200
Solar Salt	€/kg	1.09
TES	-	Dependent on the specific case
Interface Equipment	-	Dependent on the specific case
Civil Works	% CAPEX	9
Piping	% CAPEX	6
Electrical and mechanical building works	% CAPEX	14
Instrumentation and controls	% CAPEX	7
Land	% CAPEX	2
Engineering and supervision	% CAPEX	10
Local services	% CAPEX	2
Contingencies	% CAPEX	10
OPEX		
Fixed Opex	% del CAPEX	1.5
Variable Opex	€/MWh _t	1.0
DISCOUNT FACTOR		
Real Interest Rate	%	3
Plant Lifetime	years	20
Discount factor	-	14.88
Natural Gas	€/MWh	42.34

5.3 Methane Steam reforming for hydrogen production

Recently, as part of the European CoMETHy Project [108], ENEA has proposed and developed a modified methane steam reforming process in order to enable its integration with concentrating solar technology. In particular, in order to reduce the operating temperatures of the reaction

new catalysts and a "membrane reactor" have been developed that allow the process to be sustained at thermal levels below 565 °C) [108]. The process was engineered and demonstrated through the construction of a pilot plant connected to a MS circuit at the ENEA Casaccia Research Center (capacity: 3.5 Nm³/h of pure hydrogen). In the process hypothesis developed by ENEA, shown in Figure 15, a linear parabolic collector plant provides solar energy capture and transfer using MS as the heat transfer fluid. In addition, a dual-tank thermal storage system makes it possible to stabilize the thermal input to the chemical plant, regardless of fluctuations in solar radiation. MS at a nominal temperature of 550 °C are sent to the steam reforming reactor consisting of a shell-and-tube heat exchanger: MS, contained in the shell, transfer solar heat to the gas passing through the tubes. Inside the tubes, filled with an appropriate catalyst, both the hydrogen production reaction and the product separation operation take place due to the presence of a hydrogen-permeable palladium-based membrane. The extraction of hydrogen from the reaction environment allows, in a single stage, both high yields (despite relatively "low" temperatures for such a process) and purification of the hydrogen produced. Thus, the process produces pure hydrogen (> 99%) and a CO₂-rich gas mixture that can be easily purified. The waste heat of MS from the reactor is used to support other plant services (feed preheating, steam generation, etc.); MS are, finally, collected in the cold tank of the solar plant.

Table 8 summarizes the main integration specifications developed for the thermal coupling between the process under consideration and the CST technology selected for heat supply. In this specific application case, the integration between industrial utility and solar system is at the process level, where solar heat is directly supplied to the process equipment (shell and tube heat exchanger).

Figure 15. Scheme of MS-driven methane steam reforming process integrated with CSP technology, adapted from [108].

Table 8. Specifications of CST plant and TES to supply heat to steam reforming process.

Parameter	Value
Type of Solar Concentrator	Parabolic Trough
Number of SCA for loop	4
Length of a single SCA [m]	100
Aperture width of the SCA [m]	5.8
Reflective Aperture Area for a single SCA [m ²]	545
Type of Receiver Tubes	SCHOTT PTR70
Type of HTF	Binary Solar Salt
Inlet HTF temperature [°C]	430
Outlet HTF temperature [°C]	550
Type of TES	Double Tank
Type of HSM	Binary Solar Salt
Hot Tank Temperature [°C]	550
Cold Tank Temperature [°C]	430

Considering a plant with a hydrogen production of 1500 Nm³/h, the heat duty was estimated to be equal to 2.91 MW_{th} [168]. To determine the operating hours of the plant, a Typical Meteorological Year applicable to the site of ENEA Casaccia Research Center has been considered has been considered from PVGIS database [169] and a parametric study was carried out by varying the size of solar field (the total reflective area) and the TES capacity (expressed in terms of hours). The heat supplied to the plant in a year was evaluated by using the System Advisor Model (SAM) software, developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL - USA) [170].

Figure 16 shows the trend of operating hours as a function of solar collector size and storage capacity: the higher the number of loops and the higher the storage capacity, the greater number of hours the MS-driven process can be fed. In order to identify solutions that minimize the cost of hydrogen production, some design cases have been considered (see Table 9). The Figure 17 clearly identifies the main contributions to capital expenses as basis for further considerations and analysis: the costs for the equipment (Steam Generator, Steam reformers, Hydrogen compression, CO₂ removal) was determined to be equal to 2.617 M€ [168] and they are the same in all cases; while the costs for the solar field and TES (including tanks, Solar Salt and pumps) change for each case. Finally, for the different cases, the Table 9 reports the total CapEx, the obtained hydrogen production (ton_{H₂}/year) and the estimated cost of producing hydrogen (€/kg_{H₂}): the results obtained are in good agreement with the industry studies [86,171–173]. The configuration that minimizes the cost of hydrogen production is one with a solar field consisting of 10 loops and 12-hour TES.

Figure 16. The operating hours for MS-driven steam reforming process integrated with CSP technology as a function of total reflective area of the solar field and of TES capacity.

Figure 17. Breakdown of equipment purchase costs for the MS-driven steam reforming process integrated with CSP technology.

Table 9. Design case configuration and results obtained from techno-economic analysis for MS-driven methane steam reforming process integrated with CSP technology.

Parameter	U.M.	Desing cases						
		a	b	c	d	e	f	g
Number of loops	#	7	7	9	9	10	10	11
Solar field Reflective area	m ²	1144 5	1144 5	1471 5	1471 5	1635 0	1635 0	1798 5
TES Capacity	h	4	8	8	12	12	16	16
MS-driven operating hours	h/y	2092	2376	2722	3006	3183	3288	3457
Hydrogen production	ton _{H₂} / y	280	318	364	402	426	440	463
CAPEX	M€	14.1	15.2	16.8	17.8	18.7	19.6	20.4
Hydrogen Production Cost	€/kg _{H₂}	5.43	5.21	5.09	4.93	4.89	4.95	4.92

5.4 Olive oil mill wastewater steam reforming for syngas production

In the Mediterranean area, in particular the countries from the European Union (EU), the production of the olive oil is extremely relevant and accounts for 67% of world production [174]. The by-products (olive Oil Mill Wastewater, OMW) of this process are highly pollutant, due to the high values of organic loads, biochemical oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, total organic carbon and phenolic compounds that are present in the effluent [175]. It is estimated that 1 ton of olives generates between 600 and 1200 kg of OMW, depending on the process employed [176]. Consistent with the EU long-term strategy of becoming climate-neutral by 2050 with a net zero greenhouse gas-emitting economy [177], the steam reforming process of the OMW (Figure 18) can constitute a feasible solution for the treatment and the valorisation of the effluents producing renewable syngas (mainly hydrogen) [178–180].

Figure 18. Schematic diagram of the Steam Reforming process of the Olive Oil Mill Wastewater, adapted from [180].

The steam reforming process of OMW is complex and the main reactions that occur in the reactor are:

resulting in the formation of the products, mainly H_2 and CO_2 , but also smaller amounts of CO and CH_4 .

Conventionally, a Gas Fired Heater (GFH) is used for the evaporation step of the OMW and to feed the reactor where there is the formation of gaseous products using a catalyst. In this specific case, the integration between the process and the MS technologies occurs at process level, where the system consisting of CST and TES partially replaces the GFH, feeding the reactor and subsequently the final vaporisation step, and the heat is directly supplied to the process equipment (shell-and-tube heat exchangers, HEX4 and HEX3b, as shown in Figure 19), accounting for around 64% of the heat required in the conventional process.

Figure 19. Scheme of MS-driven steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater integrated with CSP technology.

Considering a plant that handles 12601 kg/h of OMW [180], resulting in a syngas yield equal to 0.344 Nm³ per kilogram of feedstock, the heat duty for the CST plant was estimated to be equal to 4.22 MW_{th} [180], according to Table 10. To determine the operating hours of the plant, a Typical Meteorological Year applicable to the site of ENEA Casaccia Research Center has been considered from PVGIS database [169] and a parametric study was carried out by varying the size of solar field (the total reflective area) and the TES capacity (expressed in terms of hours). The heat supplied to the process in a year was evaluated by using the System Advisor Model (SAM) software, developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL - USA) [170]. Table 11 summarizes the main specifications for the CST and TES to supply heat to supply heat to the steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater.

Table 10. Heat Duty for the equipment in the steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater, evaluated from [180].

Equipment	Heat Duty [MW]
HEX1	1.14
HEX2	4.33
HEX3a	2.35
HEX3b	3.52
HEX4	5.21
Reactor	0.70

Table 11. Specifications of CST plant and TES to supply heat to steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater.

Parameter	Value
Type of Solar Concentrator	Parabolic Trough
Number of SCA for loop	6
Length of a single SCA [m]	100
Aperture width of the SCA [m]	5.8
Reflective Aperture Area for a single SCA [m ²]	545
Type of Receiver Tubes	SCHOTT PTR70
Type of HTF	Binary Solar Salt
Inlet HTF temperature [°C]	290
Outlet HTF temperature [°C]	565
Type of TES	Double Tank
Type of HSM	Binary Solar Salt
Hot Tank Temperature [°C]	565
Cold Tank Temperature [°C]	290

Figure 20 shows the trend of operating hours as a function of solar collector size and storage capacity: the higher the number of loops and the higher the storage capacity, the greater number of

hours the MS-driven process can be fed. In order to identify solutions that minimize the cost of hydrogen production, some design cases have been considered (see Table 12). The Figure 21 clearly identify the main contributions to capital expenses as basis for further considerations and analysis: the costs for the equipment (Heat Exchanger, Gas Fired Heater, Reactor, Compressor and Flash-drum) was determined to be equal to 2.525 M€ [180] and they are the same in all cases; while the costs for the solar field and TES (including tanks, Solar Salt and pumps) change for each case. Finally, for the different cases, the Table 12 reports the total CapEx, the obtained syngas production (Nm^3/year) and the estimated production cost: the results obtained are in accordance with those reported in the literature [181–183]. In particular, the configuration that minimizes the cost of hydrogen production is one with a solar field consisting of 8 loops and 12-hour TES.

Figure 20. The operating hours for MS-driven steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater as a function of total reflective area of the solar field and of TES capacity.

Figure 21. Breakdown of equipment purchase costs for the MS-driven steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater.

Table 12. Design case configuration and results obtained from techno-economic analysis for the steam reforming process of Olive Oil Mill Wastewater.

Parameter	U.M.	Desing cases						
		a	b	c	d	e	f	g
Number of loops	#	6	6	7	7	8	8	9
Solar field Reflective area	m ²	19620	19620	22890	22890	26160	26160	29430
TES Capacity	h	4	8	8	12	12	16	16
MS-driven operating hours	h/y	2430	2655	2952	3094	3413	3459	3635
Syngas production	10 ⁶ Nm ³ /y	10.5	11.5	12.8	13.4	14.8	15.0	15.8
CAPEX	M€	17.8	18.6	20.3	21.1	22.7	22.0	23.6
Syngas Production Cost	€/Nm ³	0.165	0.159	0.156	0.155	0.152	0.154	0.156

5.5 Employment of Molten Salt mixtures in further industrial processes

The demand for electricity/thermal energy has been steadily increasing, both due to growing consumption in industrialized countries and population growth in developing countries. Energy consumption by the industrial sector has a crucial impact on the energy balance. Regarding the specific European context, a quarter of total energy consumption is attributable to the industrial sector, which requires 60% electricity and 40% heat [184]. From analyses conducted by the Joint Research Center of the European Commission [185], European industrial heat demand is mostly referable to high-temperature processes (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Final energy consumption and breakdown of useful heat demand by European countries [184].

Currently, thermal energy for industrial processes is produced through the combustion of fossil fuel in boilers and furnaces, causing the release of large amounts of carbon dioxide, accounting for about one-third of global emissions. Adding to the environmental challenge is the problem of fossil

resource procurement, which is becoming increasingly urgent due to geopolitical instabilities and the need to ensure security of energy supply.

The need to implement energy policy measures aimed at curbing energy consumption and using alternative, more efficient and environmentally friendly energy systems is now recognized. From this perspective, especially in the last decade, there has been an important development of scientific and technological initiatives aimed at supporting the process of transition to an energy economy based on clean and renewable sources. Solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal energy represent sustainable alternatives to reduce or, even, eliminate dependence on conventional fossil resources.

A comprehensive study of the thermal consumption of European industry [184] shows that the largest proportion of high-temperature heat demand is accounted for by metallurgical industries (iron, steel, aluminium), non-metallic mining industries (especially the cement industry) and some processes in the chemical industry. Low- and medium-temperature heat demand, on the other hand, refers to the food, beverage, tobacco, paper, painting, and textile industries. Representative endothermic processes, characterized by essentially homogeneous operating conditions, such as thermal levels and heat transfer/process fluids, can be associated with each industry sector, as shown in Table 13. Finally, Figure 23 shows some of the most important unit processes involved with process heating and the MS mixtures, arranged by operating temperature range.

Table 13. Main endothermic processes in industry: operating temperature ranges and process HTF (sources: [186–189]).

SECTOR	PROCESS	TEMPERATURE [°C]	
Food and beverage	Cooking	70–120	Steam, Water
	Pasteurization	60-150	Steam
	Sterilization	100-140	Steam
	Tempering	40-80	Steam
	Drying, dehydration	40-100	Air
	Washing, cleaning	40-80	Steam, Air
	Heat treatment	60-80	Water
	Olive oil deodorization	200-240	Steam
	Cooking of bakery products	150-320	Air
Textile	Malting	80-90	Air
	Blanching	60-90	Water
	Drying, degreasing	100-130	Steam
	Pressing	120-140	Steam
	Fixing	160-180	Steam
Pulp and paper	Printing	40-130	Water, Steam
	Bleaching	120-150	Water
	De-linking	60-90	Steam
	Drying	90-200	Air, Steam
Chemical and pharmaceutical	Pulp preparation	120-170	Pressurized water
	Distillation	100-200	Water
	Evaporation	110-170	Steam
	Drying	120-170	Air, Steam
Automobile	Thickening	130-140	Steam
	Paint pre-treatment	40-50	Water
	Baking of Paints	175-225	Steam
Leather products, rubber, plastic and glass manufacturing	Paint drying	150-175	Air
	Pre-tanning	40-60	Water
	Chrome tanning	60-80	Water
	Drying and finishing	70-100	Air
	Drying (rubber)	50-130	Air
	Pre-heating	50-70	Water
	Preparation	120-140	Steam
	Distillation	140-150	Steam
	Extrusion	140-160	Steam
	Drying (plastic)	180-200	Air
Ceramics	Laminating	100-180	Air
	Drying glass fiber	150-175	Air
Foundries	Annealing float glass	500-600	Air
	Atomization	500-600	Air
Cement and gypsum	Drying	80-160	Air
	Hardening, Annealing, Tempering, Forging, Rolling	700-1500	Air
	Calcination of lime	600-1200	Air
Cement and gypsum	Calcination of gypsum	450-600	Air
	Drying Plasterboard	180-300	Air

Figure 23. Temperature ranges of Industrial Process Heat Demand and Molten Salt mixtures (sources: [186–189]).

In the framework of the national funding scheme Ricerca di Sistema 2019-2021 [189,190], ENEA investigated and elaborated possible integration schemes for medium- and high-temperature industrial processes using MS mixture. Atomization in the ceramic industry and olive oil deodorization in the food industry can be considered unit processes of considerable interest.

In the former case, predominantly thermal energy is consumed in the atomization step for the slurry preparation, which is used to evaporate water from the material: a spray dryer causes instantaneous evaporation of most of the water from the material by a jet of hot air (500-600 °C). The atomizer is usually powered by a combustor, where natural gas is burned, or more rarely it is electrically operated. For the temperatures and powers involved, the atomization process can be thermally supplied by a binary MS mixture operating in the temperature range of 290-550 °C. The salts are heated by a concentrating solar system and the integration occurs at the process level, where the process fluid (air) is heated by the MS through an intermediate heat exchanger (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Schematic diagram of integrating a MS system into the atomization process (sources: [189,190]).

In the second case, deodorization is a food industry process by which bad smells related to substances or treatments are neutralized and this operation is essential for oils and fats intended for human consumption. Deodorization treatment involves bubbling superheated steam through layers of deaerated oil in vacuum vessels. The oil to be treated, previously deaerated in (1), passes into the heat exchanger (2) where it is preheated with the heat released from the oil exiting the vacuum column. Next, the oil passes through steam heater (3) and is introduced into the upper part of column (4) at the top plate. From the top plate, the oil flows down into the plates below, meeting the counter-current steam. The exiting oil, after giving up heat in the heat exchanger (2), is further cooled and then filtered. Deodorization treatment consists of introducing steam (160 °C) into the bubbling column. Typically, deodorization requires that the oil is heated to about 220 °C, and to

reach these temperatures, steam is sent into steam heater (3) at temperatures above 450 °C. A binary MS mixture has been proposed for coupling the deodorization process with concentrating solar technology, with two steam generators placed downstream of the MS TES (Figure 25). Specifically, with the concomitant use of low- and high-pressure steam, integration between industrial process and MS system takes place at two distinct points: first, at the process level, in which steam is directly injected into the process equipment (vacuum desorption column); and second, at the supply level, in which high-pressure steam heats the oil upstream of the desorption column.

Figure 25. Schematic diagram of integrating a MS system into the oil deodorization process with steam generators (sources: [189,190]).

6 ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS/CARNOT BATTERIES

Energy storage systems play an important role towards decarbonization of countries, providing essential support to the progressive requirements of evolving energy systems [191], since they exhibit an increasing share of renewable energy sources, with more active players as well as increased interconnected, decentralized and digitalized systems, requiring more flexibility, stability and reliability [192].

In order to meet Paris Agreement goals, several countries have committed to different decarbonization levels, namely the European Union (EU) member states aiming to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, with an intermediate target of a 55% net reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2030 (compared to 1990 levels). According to the “European Green Deal”, and more recently with the “European Climate Law” and the “European Commission Long-Term strategy”, a multitude of pathways do enable the intended 2050 decarbonisation levels to be reached, with strong impositions on the energy sector (electricity in particular), since they account more than 75% of EU’s GHG emissions. All decarbonisation pathways present a common requirement of flexibility to achieve the desired integration of variable Renewable Energy Sources (RES), in a cost-efficient manner, while adequate levels of security of supply should be met. Amongst the solutions that can benefit the power system in terms of flexibility are networks, demand-response, dispatchable and flexible power generation technologies and energy storage, where the later can indeed provide support to grid dynamics, for all timescales ranging from frequency response to inter-year flexibility [193].

A general review of energy storage systems is presented in the following sections, highlighting the importance of considering also “Carnot Batteries” in the range of eligible options [194], where MS display a promising role in the electricity storage ecosystem.

From a broader perspective, a MS Carnot Battery can operate as an energy hub, a beyond State-of-Art (SoA) concept relies on the integration of electricity and gas grids is also presented in this section.

Moreover, aiming at the economic assessment of different Carnot battery configurations - both SoA and the beyond SoA concept - a model has been developed.

This model conducts an annual assessment on an hourly basis, that provides yield (among other parameters) as output based on specific operation mode and strategies, and in this way use these values in an economic assessment. The focus is on evaluating a 100 MW_e(net) Carnot Battery, simulated and compared with another model representing a 100 MW_e(AC equivalent) Li-ion Battery Energy Storage System (BESS).

The model further encompasses an assessment of impacts over the power system. This assessment is based on various scenarios of competing technologies (e.g. pumped hydro storage, Li-ion batteries) by means of Artelys Crystal Super Grid, modelling tool for the electricity production distribution system.

6.1 Overview of Energy Storage Systems and Carnot Batteries

6.1.1 Energy storage

The technologies definitions, classifications and applications considered here follow the ones considered in [195,196], unless otherwise mentioned. As a general definition (defined by the EU in the “Clean Energy Package” [197]): “ ‘energy storage’ means, in the electricity system, deferring the

final use of electricity to a moment later than when it was generated, or the conversion of electrical energy into a form of energy which can be stored, the storing of such energy, and the subsequent reconversion of such energy into electrical energy or use as another energy carrier”.

Indeed, in the optics of the electricity system, one can identify one-directional flexibility in “Power-2-X”, or bi-directional flexibility in “Power-2-X-2-Power” [195].

Considering the vast energy storage technological solutions pool, they are usually classified into 5 groups [196] based on the type of energy acting as the reservoir:

- **Mechanical** (e.g. Pumped Hydro, Flywheel, CAEs, etc.);
- **Electrochemical** (e.g. Li-ion Batteries, Flow Batteries, etc.);
- **Electrical** (e.g. Supercapacitors, etc.);
- **Chemical** (e.g. Hydrogen, methane, etc.);
- **Thermal** (e.g. Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Thermo-chemical).

Until the end of 2023, a total of 204 GW of installed electricity storage power, with roughly 818 GWh installed capacity (see Figure 26 for power and capacity related shares). Pumped Hydro Energy Storage (PHES) dominates the installed capacity (with 87% of the storage power and 95% of the storage capacity share), followed by other technologies like Lithium ion based battery energy storage (with 3.4% of the storage power and 1.5% of the storage capacity share), amongst others, sensible heat (with 1.4% of the storage power and 2.6% of the storage capacity share), with the remaining technologies (CAES, Flywheel and batteries based on either redox flow, sodium, lead-acid and nickel) representing less than 1% each. It should be noted that there is another category that includes other non-identified chemical and electrochemical storage technologies representing the second largest share in installed power capacity (6.5%) but with a very low share of installed storage capacity (with only 0.1% share) [198].

Figure 26. Global Energy storage installed capacity (in terms of GW and GWh) by technology for the year of 2023 (source: [198]).

Several energy storage technologies present themselves as good candidates to support the decarbonization, power system flexibility and security of supply pathways. Besides these major requirements, other relevant features include, to mention just a few, competitive cost, reliability, resilient supply chains and critical materials autonomy, possible services provided to the power grid, etc [192].

In order to provide comparable terms, there are some indicators or features of such storage technologies that are commonly useful as a selection criterion for a given application [195,196]:

- Technological Readiness Level (TRL);
- Energy Carrier in and Energy carrier out;
- Energy Capacity (in MWh);
- Power installed Capacity (in MW);
- Storage duration at full power (in h);
- Round-Trip-Efficiency (RTE in % of electricity output to electricity input);
- Conversion Efficiency (in % if the output is not electricity);
- Response (ranging from “how fast”, “how much” and “how long”);
- Availability factor;
- Lifetime;
- Number of cycles and degradation;
- CAPEX (in €/kW or €/kWh, or combination of both for given system sizes);
- OPEX (in €/(kW.year) and/or €/(kWh.year) or %CAPEX/year);
- Critical raw materials;
- Front-of-the-meter or behind-the-meter;
- Services provided;
- Technology constraints (e.g. geographical, mobility);
- Levelized Cost Of Storage (LCOS, for given macroeconomic and charging costs considerations).

An electricity storage technology data comparison is presented in Table 14, providing an insight into some indicators from the previous list when comparing different technologies, either well established or some anticipated and promising ones [199].

Table 14. Electricity storage technology data comparison (source: [199]).

Technology Abbrev.	Capital Costs (Energy) (\$/kWh)	Capital Costs (Power) (\$/kw)	Variable O&M (\$/MWh)	Fixed O&M (\$/kW-yr)	Round-trip Efficiency (DOD)	Cycles (at 80% DOD)	# of cycles per year	Depth of discharge (DOD)	Project lifetime (years)	WACC used for LCOS	Approx. LCOS
Flywheel (2018)	11520	0	30	5.60	0.86	200000	660	1	20	0.065	1.832
Ultracapacitors (2018)	74480	0	30	1.00	0.92	1000000	660	1	16	0.065	12.578
LEAD (2018)	352	137	0.5125	5.11	0.72	900	660	1	3	0.065	0.707
LIB -4 hour (2020)	320	246	0.5125	10	0.86	3500	330	0.8	10	0.065	0.254
FLOW (2018)	483	137	0.5125	5.89	0.68	10000	330	1	15	0.065	0.277
Sodium Sulfur (2018)	794	450	0.3	10.00	0.75	4000	330	0.8	13.5	0.065	0.543
Sodium Metal Halide (2018)	815	450	0.3	10.00	0.83	3500	330	1	12.5	0.065	0.425
Zinc-Hybrid Cathode (2018)	438	450	0.3	10.00	0.72	3500	330	1	10	0.065	0.346
CAES (2020)	3.66	1153	0.5125	16.12	0.52	1	330	1	25	0.065	0.096
LAES (anticipated)	450	3500	3.3	48.70	0.60	10000	330	1	25	0.065	0.348
PTES (anticipated)	37	1836	3.3	48.70	0.56	10000	330	1	25	0.065	0.116
PSH (2020)	72.4	1150.8	0.5125	26.62	0.80	15000	52	1	40	0.065	0.237
Gravity (anticipated)	337.00	692	0	6.12	0.80	200000	52	1	25	0.065	0.771
H2 elec-cavern- CC (2020)	3.8	7350.59	9.4	29.7	0.27	10000	52	1	30	0.065	2.486
H2 elec-cavern- FC (Future)	3.8	1675.31	4.9	27.0	0.37	10000	52	1	30	0.065	0.410

Not all technologies present commercial maturity at the present date. Taking the example of lithium-ion batteries evolution, it is now expected that this technology will see its installed capacity share largely increase in the coming years, reducing the long established pumped hydro storage

share [200]. Figure 27 presents several energy storage technologies that are in different levels of development according to their TRL.

Figure 27. TRL for several energy storage technologies (source: [195]).

Not only the efficiency of electricity technologies (comparison presented in Figure 28) and the capital costs (comparison presented in Figure 29) or O&M costs (comparison presented in Figure 30) are the most relevant, since a given technology can present a lower LCOS (comparison presented in Figure 31 and Figure 32 for different macroeconomic and electricity charging cost assumptions) and be more suited to shorter duration storage, intermediate duration storage or long duration storage, as well as being more able to participate and interact in many ways with the electric grid, being more suited to certain applications, given the wide range of possible electricity services (overview of possible storage-related services presented in Figure 33).

Figure 28. Round trip efficiency comparison of several electricity storage technologies (source: [199]).

Figure 29. Comparison of power capacity (\$/kWh) and energy capacity (\$/kWh) component cost for several electricity storage technologies (source: [199]).

Figure 30. Comparison of fixed (\$/(kW.year)) and variable (\$/(kWh.year)) O&M costs for several electricity storage technologies (source: [199]).

Figure 31. Comparison of the LCOS (in \$/kWh) for several electricity storage technologies from NREL report¹⁰ (source: [199]).

¹⁰ Consideration in the NREL analysis [198]: constant charging price (at the US wholesale price of 2.5cents/kwh), WACC of 6.5%, number of cycles per year are 660 for short duration, 330 for 4 and 8-12 hour while the value is 52 for long-duration technologies (which is approximately a 10% capacity factor for long-duration).

Figure 32. Comparison of the LCOS (in €/kWh) for several electricity storage technologies (retrieved from [201], source: [199]).

As illustrated in Figure 31 and Figure 32, LCOS are generally in the same range, despite some differences encountered. For real applications economic assessment, they imply not only most likely different macroeconomic considerations, technology costs (dimensioning, etc.), cost of electricity when charging, but beyond that, also with respect to possible roles and applications (see detailed list in Figure 33 [192]), including:

- Generation-support services;
- Grid-support services;
- Ancillary services;
- Energy-management services for consumers.

Figure 33. Energy storage applications and added value (source: [192]).

Besides individual applications, a given storage technology might be able to take advantage of multiple services, considered as service stacking, and in this way further improve the storage asset economics over time [192]. Also, to the present date, there is no single technology that can fit all the power system application requirements [202], hence a storage technology mix is expected to make part of the storage solution as a whole. Nevertheless, and despite many new storage concepts and systems being developed and demonstrated (with a lack of definitive application suitability for all existing and new storage technologies), attempts have been made to create a suitability matrix, like the one presented in Figure 34.

Application areas		Energy Storage Devices														
		Electrochemical								Electrical		Mechanical		Thermal		
		NaS	NaNiCl ₂	Pb-Acid	Li-ion	Ni-Cd	Ni-MH	VRFB	PSB	Zn Br	SCES	SMES	CAES	PHS	FES	All Thermal
Renewable energy integrations	Time shifting	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Firming capacity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Bulk Energy	Peak Shaving	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Arbitrage of energy	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Ancillary Services	Voltage Support	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Load balancing	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Spinning reserve	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Black Start	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Frequency balancing	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Energy Management	Enhancing Power quality	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Power reliability	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		●	Suitable application					●	Possible application				●	Un suitable application		

Figure 34. Summary of state-of-the-art repartition of energy storage systems (technologies Vs. applications) (source: [202]).

6.1.2 Carnot Batteries

Carnot batteries (CBs) are a type of energy storage allowing electric power to be stored in the form thermal energy, which is then transformed again to electricity [203,204]. It is a feasible system for storing electricity that presents advantages of over some electricity storage systems (such as Pumped Hydro Storage and lithium-ion batteries or CAES) since it has no geographical restrictions and use of potential low-cost and environmental friendly materials [203,204].

CBs definition and classification are still up to debate as to whether some technologies should be considered as CB [205], where a unique and shared CB definition is one of the many expected outcomes stemming from “Annex 36 Carnot Batteries” [206]. According to [205,207] “Power-to-Heat-to-Power” should only be used when the heat reservoirs are hotter than the environment, which are charged by putting the heat inside, since in this case, the direction of heat flow coincides with that of exergy. Since what is stored is thermal exergy, many analogous technological names could be a part of the whole CB family group [205,207]:

- Pumped Thermal Energy Storage (PTES);
- Pumped Heat Electricity Storage (PHES);
- Electro-Thermal Energy Storage (ETES);
- Thermo-Electrical Energy Storage (TEES);
- Compressed Heat Energy Storage (CHEST);
- Pumped Heat/Cold Electricity Storage (PHES, PCES);
- Liquified Air Energy Storage (LAES);
- Cryogenic Energy Storage (CES).

Despite the definition and classification, many agree on the overall technological concept (presented in Figure 35), which is constituted by three main (sub)system [203–208]:

- a **Power2Heat (P2H) System**, responsible of transforming electricity into heat (sometimes using as well low temperature heat from the environment, as it could be in the case of heat pumps):
 - Direct heating (Joule resistive heating);
 - Electric (boiler) heat exchanger;
 - Thermodynamic heat pump cycle;
 - Inductive heating;
 - Microwave and others (including a hybrid concept).
- a **Thermal Energy Storage (TES) System**, enabling to store energy as thermal energy (or thermal exergy) in thermal reservoirs (with a variety of media and temperature levels):
 - Sensible Heat Thermal Storage (SHTS);
 - Latent Heat Thermal Storage (LHTS);
 - Thermochemical Storage (TCS).
- a **Heat2Power (H2P) System**, transforming the heat back to electricity through a suitable power cycle or other appropriate device:
 - Brayton, Rankine, Stirling or absorption-adsorption cycles and their combinations;
 - Direct conversion as thermoelectric, thermo-ionic and thermophotovoltaic systems.

Figure 35. Basic operating principle scheme of a Carnot Battery representing the three major subsystems involved: electricity conversion into heat (heat pump, resistive heating, etc.), heat storage (1-tank, 2-tank, liquid, solid, PCM, etc.), and conversion of heat into electricity.

The possibilities of configurations are quite numerous, as well as the size and possible applications [206]. Figure 36 presents a comprehensive but not exhaustive list of the possible configurations of a CB. It should be noted that some combinations enable the use of reversible turbomachinery heat pump/power cycle, providing relatively high round-trip efficiency, while others do not due to the chosen configuration/equipment limitations [203]. Some systems use thermal reservoirs lower than ambient temperature, so heat must be removed instead of added. In either case, the three main subsystems must be very well matched to each other in order to attain high efficiency [206].

Besides electricity as an energy source, heat from various sources (solar thermal, waste heat, etc.) can be integrated into several CBs configurations, usually named Thermally Integrated Carnot Batteries (TI-CB), which could increase the overall round-trip-efficiencies. Even if it is not a TI-CB (on the input side), it can make use of the waste thermal energy discarded after the power cycle or other equipment, for instance delivering heat/cold into industrial environments/clusters that require heat/cold delivery at several temperature levels, promoting better economic value towards these energy storage solutions.

Figure 36. Possible configurations of a Carnot Battery (source: [206]).

The authors in [208] provide a review of several commercial developments concerning CBs, and they are divided according to the discharge cycle, and hence how they transform heat into power. Using thermodynamic power cycles as the H2P transformation, exhibit the potential of reversibility, which could eventually act as a thermodynamic heat pump cycle on the charging step, enhancing round-trip-efficiency of the CB. Generally, an interesting way of categorising a thermodynamic power cycle is to see whether phase change occurs within the cycle, as well as if the operating pressures are above or below the critical pressure of the working fluid [209] (see Figure 37).

Figure 37. Classification of thermodynamic power cycles: Condensing cycles (on the left) and non-condensing cycles (on the right), adapted from [209].

In this sense it was sought appropriate to organise in the same way as in [208], to address the different CB concepts, according to the discharge cycle:

- **Rankine Cycle** (see Table 15 with list of commercial development projects)

- Employs a dual-phase fluid where a given fluid in a liquid state is pumped and pressurised, then heated to gas phase and later expanded in a turbine producing work, ultimately converting it to electric power. The fluid is then condensed and the cycle can continue. There are a variety of working fluids that suits this thermodynamic power cycle and its associated temperature ranges:
 - **Water/Steam Rankine cycles (SRC):** employ water/steam as the working fluid (employed in many thermal power plants like coal power plants, bottom cycles in Combined Cycle Gas Turbines (CCGT) but also CSP plants as a subcritical cycle [210]). This cycle is more usually employed for operating temperatures (turbine inlet temperature) from 375 to 585 °C [211,212];
 - **Organic Rankine Cycles (ORC):** This cycle employs organic based fluids as the working fluid: siloxane-based ORCs are particularly adapted to load heat from 250-400 °C, while hydrocarbon-based ranges from 175-250 °C and refrigerant based below 175 °C [213];
 - **CO₂ Rankine Cycles:** (usually transcritical or subcritical cycles) [208];
 - Others: Liquid air that expands through the turbine [208].
- **Brayton Cycle** (see Table 16 with list of commercial development projects):
 - This cycle employs a gas (no phase change occurs) as the working fluid to operate the heat engine (This cycle can employ turbines but also reciprocating devices) [208] that could reach temperature >900 °C [191]:
 - **Air Brayton:** Using air as working fluid (closed or open loop);
 - **Argon Brayton:** Using Argon as working fluid (in a close loop);
 - **CO₂ Brayton:** Using CO₂ as working fluid (in a close loop);
 - **Other:** Nitrogen, etc.
- **Other and hybrid systems** (see Table 17 with list of commercial development projects):
 - CB can use other power thermodynamic cycles besides Rankine or Brayton based, such as Stirling, a combination of the above, absorption and desorption cycles, but also systems of direct conversion such as thermophotovoltaic cell, specially modified multi-junction photovoltaic cells or hybrid thermionic photovoltaic converter [208].

Table 15. List of commercial development projects in CB using Rankine cycle discharging (retrieved from [208]). NOTE: for specific projects related information, readers are suggested to go to reference [208].

Company, System	Charging Method	TES	Discharging Method	Power Output	Storage Capacity/Duration	Roundtrip Efficiency	State
Siemens Gamesa, ETES	Resistance heaters to air	Volcanic rock bed ~800 °C	steam Rankine cycle	units to 100s MW	24 h	25% to >40%	Demo
RWE, Store2Power	Resistance heaters	molten salt	steam Rankine cycle	100s MW	hours	~40%	n.a.
E2S Power	Resistance heaters	Graphite-aluminium alloy at 700 °C	steam Rankine cycle	1–100s MW	hours	25–40%	lab proof of concept
Spilling	Steam compression & liquefaction	Saturated water (steam accumulators)	Steam expander (steam engine)	up to MW	hours	n.a.	n.a.
GE, AMSESS	CO ₂ Brayton + el. heating	Molten salt, water tank	Steam cycle with extraction	20–100 MW	8 h	42–62%	Concept
Consortium CHESTER	Heat pump (organic fluid)	PCM and water	ORC	MW scale (8 kW exper.)	hours to days	n.a.	lab proof of concept
Climeon	Heat pump (organic fluid)	water (e.g., district heating system)	ORC	80 kW to MW	hours	25–60%	concept with existing ORC
TC Mach	Heat pump (organic fluid)	Stone dust TES	ORC	kW	hours	n.a.	construction of proof of concept
Future Bay	Heat pump (organic fluid)	water (hot) and PCM (cold)	ORC	10s kW	hours	n.a.	Demo
Highview	Air liquifaction	Liquid air + other TES	Vaporization, expansion turbine	50–350 MW	about 6	60–70%	Pilot, full scale construction
MAN/ABB, ETES	CO ₂ heat pump	120 °C water + cold (ice) storage	CO ₂ Rankine cycle	several MWe	~5 h	~45%	lab demo
Echogen, ETES	CO ₂ heat pump, fluidized bed heat exchange	Sand (hot) and ice (cold)	CO ₂ Rankine cycle	25 MW	250 MWh	~60%	design
Energydome, CO ₂ battery	CO ₂ compression & liquefaction	Liquid CO ₂ + other TES	Vaporization, expansion turbine	10–80 MW modules	20–200 MWh	77%	Pilot construction

Table 16. List of commercial development projects in CB using Brayton cycle discharging (retrieved from [208]). NOTE: for specific projects related information, readers are suggested to go to reference [208].

Company, System	Charging Method	TES	Discharging Method	Power Output	Storage Capacity/Duration	Roundtrip Efficiency	State
247Solar, Heat2Power Turbine	Electric resistance heaters	Silica sand	Gas turbine (Brayton cycle)	200 kWe–100s MW	6–20 h	30%	Concept, design
1414Degrees, TESS	Electric resistance heaters	Silicon based alloy, melting temperature 1414 °C	Gas turbine (also steam turbine, Stirling engine, direct heat)	10 MW-GW	n.a.	n.a.	Demos (done) Planning grid scale pilot
Peregrine Turbine Technologies	Electric resistance heaters	Graphite-aluminium alloy (MGA), 800 °C	CO ₂ Brayton cycle	1 MW	8 MWh	45%	CO ₂ turbine/compressor tests
Isoentropic	Heat pump (Brayton cycle -reciprocating devices)	Crushed rock packed bed	Brayton cycle (reciprocating devices)	2 MW (exper. 150 kW)	16 MWh	72%	Demo (bankruptoy)
Malta, Pumped Heat Energy Storage	Heat pump (reverse Brayton cycle)	Molten salt + hydrocarbon antifreeze	Recuperated Brayton cycle	10–100 MW	80 MWh–1 GWh	n.a.	Concept, design
Stiesdal, GridScale	Heat pump (reverse Brayton cycle)	Crushed basalt rock packed bed	Brayton cycle	2 MW–1 GW	100,000 MWh	35–60%	Pilot construction
Enolcon, OPTES	Heat pump (reverse Brayton cycle), N ₂ or Ar	Silica sand packed bed (silica sand, iron based sand, basalt)	Brayton cycle, N ₂ (or Ar)	~8 MW	~80 MWh	58–66%	Concept, design (Pilot designing/constructing)
WindTP	Heat pump (reverse Brayton cycle)	Gravel bed, indirect heat transfer	Brayton cycle	3–20 MW	up to 100 h	up to 85%	component demo

Table 17. List of commercial development projects in CB in other and hybrid cycle discharging category (retrieved from [208]). NOTE: for specific projects related information, readers are suggested to go to reference [208].

Company, System	Charging Method	TES	Discharging Method	Power Output	Storage Capacity/Duration	Roundtrip Efficiency	State
Azelio	Electric resistance heaters	Aluminium based PCM (800 °C)	Stirling engine	13 kW	13 h	~30%	Multiple pilots, production line, commercial
CCT Energy Storage	Electric resistance heaters	Silicon based PCM (1400 °C)	Stirling engine	5–100 kW	up to 1.2 MWh per module	n.a.	Pilot
TEXEL Energy Storage	Electric resistance heaters	Metal hydrides (MH)/metal carbonates	Stirling engine	30 kW	15–720 kWh	40%	commercial installation effort
Kraftlagenn München	Electric resistance heaters/waste heat	Ceramic system (1000 °C)	Stirling engine and ORC	60 kW (demo)	1.4 MWh _{th} (demo)	n.a.	demo
NREL ENDURING LDES (GE, PEI, Allied)	Electric resistance heaters	Fluidized packed bed with solid materials (1100 °C)	Combined Brayton and Rankine cycle	50–400 MW	10–100 h	50–55%	Components prototypes, demo preparation
Pintail Power, Liquid Salt Combined Cycle	Electric resistance heaters	molten salt	Combustion combined cycle integration	from dozens MW	24 h	82–96% (+ fuel)	Patented concepts
Pintail Power, Liquid Air Combined Cycle	Compressor for air liquefaction	liquid air	Combustion combined cycle integration	from dozens MW	24 h	118% (+ fuel)	Patented concepts
Antora Energy	Electric resistance heaters	Graphite blocks (1500 °C)	Thermophotovoltaic cell	0.1–1 MW	10 MWh _e	40%	Proof of concept
NaCompEx	Compressed heat followed by desorption	NaOH-H ₂ O solutions via concentration difference	Expansion followed by absorption	10–100 MW	60 kWh/m ³ storage	80%	Concept, design

From the information presented in Table 15, Table 16 and Table 17 it can be observed how different approaches are being pursued regarding CB concepts (at different development stages, from concept to pilot full scale construction), linking several charging methods, TES media and discharging methods.

From the perspective of using MS in CB it is important to compare the temperature ranges of different MS mixtures with respect to the power cycles, presented in Figure 38.

Figure 38. Suitability of thermal storage media (highlighting two molten salt mixtures in orange) and CB cycles for different temperature ranges (adapted from [208] with information stemming from this document and from [203,213–215]).

Looking again at the charging cycles, namely thermodynamic heat pump cycles, even though heat pumps are a mature technology, when it comes to high-temperature applications above 300 °C, they are not yet commercially available [216]. Figure 39 presents the most recent developments regarding technology suppliers of heat pumps by maximum supply temperature and capacity [217].

Figure 39. Manufacturers of heat pumps (>100 °C) by maximum supply temperature and capacity (source: [217]).

According to [218], and based on the IEA extended TRL's [219], Figure 40 presents the development stages of heat pumps to the present date.

Temperature range	Technology readiness level (TRL)	Example process
<80 °C	TRL 11: Proof of market stability	Paper: De-inking Food: Concentration Chemical: Bio-reactions
80 °C to 100 °C	TRL 10: Commercial and competitive, but large-scale deployment not yet achieved	Paper: Bleaching Food: Pasteurisation Chemical: Boiling
100 °C to 140 °C	TRL 8-9: First-of-a-kind commercial applications in relevant environment	Paper: Drying Food: Evaporation Chemical: Concentration
140 °C to 160 °C	TRL 6-7: Pre-commercial demonstration	Paper: Pulp boiling Food: Drying Chemical: Distillation Various industries: Steam production
160 °C to 200 °C	TRL 8-9: First-of-a-kind commercial applications for small-scale MVR systems and heat transformers TRL 4-5: Early to large prototype	Various industries: High-temperature steam production
>200 °C	TRL 4: Early prototype	Various industries: High-temperature processes

Readiness level: ● TRL 1 to 5 ● TRL 6 to 7 ● TRL 8 to 11

Notes: MVR = mechanical vapour recompression. TRLs can vary for specific processes or different heat pump capacities.

Figure 40. Heat pump TRL levels according to IEA extended TRL's [219] (retrieved from [218]).

Heat pump technologies can generally be divided into [220]:

- open-loop systems, where the process fluid (like steam) enters the system and get its heat content upgraded:
 - mechanical vapour recompression;
 - thermal vapour recompression.
- closed-loop systems - where the process fluid is interfaced by a heat exchanger:
 - compression heat pumps;
 - sorption heat pumps.

From the Power2Heat approach, mechanical vapour recompression could be an option if using steam is adequate (like CHEST CB concept), as well as compression heat pumps which operates according to the Stirling or Joule-Brayton cycle (most common refrigerants are hydrogen, helium and air) [220]. The use of natural refrigerants like air, CO₂, helium or argon could cover the entire temperature and power ranges.

For even higher temperature heat pumps, concerning the matching of MS temperatures in the thermal storage, concepts like the ones highlighted previously in Table 15 and Table 16 regarding the charging method, mostly reversed Joule-Brayton thermodynamic cycles are employed over a wide range of temperatures (see Figure 41 for an indicative matching between charging cycles, MS mixtures and discharging cycles), working fluids (air, N₂, argon and CO₂) and storage media. In fact, TRL levels are still quite low (apart from the LAES technology, implementing a full-scale installation of several MW at the present) usually TRL<5. To improve efficiency, these concepts (like MALTA Inc.) can employ 2 sets of storage systems, one for high temperature (MS) and another for lower temperature (for instance, methanol).

Figure 41. Indicative matching (by temperature) between some charging cycles, MS mixtures and some discharging cycles (TRL levels based on common TRL maximum of 9).

Based on a study developed by [203] the round-trip-efficiency of several PTES combinations are presented in Figure 42, which could make use of MS as the media in the TES system or higher temperature media such as solids in Brayton cycles.

Figure 42. Round-trip-efficiency comparison of heat pump thermal storage systems with electric heater-based storage as a function of turbine inlet temperature. ST: steam turbine. CCGT: combined cycle gas turbine. EH: electric heater. (retrieved from [203]).

Digging further into LCOS based cost competitiveness, Table 18 provides a comparison of some CB configurations.

Table 18. Cost ranges of CB technologies taken from Literature.

Technology	Storage duration [h]	Storage Power [MWe]	Efficiency [%]	Cost [\$/kW _e]	Cost [\$/kWh _e]	LCOS	References
PTES	5.75	2	75	2990-6090	530-1080	0.20-0.65	[221]
PTES	10	1.6	52-72	-	-	0.08-0.12	[201]
ETES (EH-MS-ST)	10	100	37.5	3102-3622	310-362	0.11-0.18	(§ 6.4.1)
Joule-Brayton PTES ¹¹	10	100	56	1900-3100	190-310	0.10-0.16	[203]
sCO ₂ PTES ¹¹	10	100	53	3500-8300	400-960	0.16-0.32	[203]
Joule-Brayton PTES ¹²	10	100	63	1921-3425	200-336	0.10-0.16	[203]
sCO ₂ PTES ¹²	10	100	59	3763-10789	443-1271	0.17-0.40	[203]
LAES	4	12	31-55	1430-2730	350-670	0.14-0.46	[203]

¹¹ Using nitrate-based MS.

¹² Using chloride-based MS.

With regard to the roles and services of CBs, since there are a considerable number of possible configurations, a quite wide range of grid application (from local scale to large scale) could be expected (see Figure 43 for an overview of potential roles of CB with some integration examples).

Figure 43. Potential roles and applications of CB with some integration examples (retrieved from [208]).

It should be noted that, the ability to participate in a service will have to take into account, not only the inherent economic performance/revenues strategy and feasibility, but also the technical capabilities of the three before mentioned subsystems components behaviour, namely the **Power2Heat (P2H)**, **Thermal Energy Storage (TES)** and **Heat2Power (H2P)**.

Specific technical features are beneficial towards the power grid itself and the grid operators. These features range from how fast, how much and how long can a given technology provide the requested power and energy to be consumed and/or delivered, the minimum load attainable and the partial load performance implications, startup cost and startup time, ability to shift from charge mode to discharge mode rapidly enough for storing electricity at a moment and deliver it at a later moment (or simply stop discharging and proceed to charge mode), to capacity firming, spinning reserve, inertia, voltage and frequency stability, amongst others.

From the Power2Heat system and its components, as an example, resistive heating could be more advantageous since it is expected to have lower startup costs compared to heat pumps [203] and high modulating capabilities (faster response when charging, enabling not only steady but quick consumption variations through time), although heat pumps provide a COP higher than 1.

From the perspective of the Heat to Power system, as an example, in the case of Rankine steam cycles, which are identically to that of how happens in CSP plants, the start-up time could take roughly 30 mins, including an energy loss accounting for 20% of the rated output for one hour [203].

So far, literature has been pointing out that CBs are quite promising and could offer not only a fairly low-cost electricity storage for medium to large capacity (in terms of power and storage duration), as

well as the possibility of providing grid inertia and capacity [203]. CB based on available off-the-shelf technology composed of Electric Heater and nitrate-based MS using steam turbines, could present competitive LCOS when compared to Li-ion Batteries, even with roughly half the round-trip-efficiency [203]. The use of higher temperature MS (chloride-based) presents further efficiency improvements, although with an increased cost for assuring high temperature, media compatible and resistant components. A cost factor for higher temperature nickel alloys could be 2.5 more costly than stainless steel alloys and 5 times more compared to carbon steel. Even in this case, chloride-based MS TES systems (having higher TES CAPEX related costs) could enable a reduced LCOS compared to nitrate-based MS TES systems (if appropriate design and materials are employed) [203].

Further studies are needed for instance on off-design analysis (on the charge and the discharge side) which is not well understood [203]. Hence grid interaction (power system services and applications, with the inherent revenues) as well as experimental data gathering from existing systems, alongside with the outputs stemming from "Annex 36" will provide implementation targets and pathways, as well as identifying further R&D requirements from system to component level (such as heat exchangers efficiency improvement), and providing guidelines for technical and economic integration of such technologies (most likely by type and/or application niche) in the energy system .

The potential use of MS in the possible configurations of CB are immense, ranging from well-established systems (based on CSP nitrate-based MS thermal storage and steam Rankine power cycles, in this case by employing resistive heating or other type of electric heating system in stand-alone systems, as well as hybridised and/or retrofitted CSP plants, coal plants, etc.) to developing concepts (making use of reversible Brayton concepts, like MALTA, and chloride-based MS thermal energy storage, enabling to exploit higher temperature power cycles, like efficient supercritical CO₂ cycles) capable of offering a multitude of services, roles and sizes.

6.2 Prospective use of Molten Salt-driven stand-alone energy storage / inter-grid integrator solutions

6.2.1 Molten Salt as Heat Transfer and Storage Medium

The MS storage systems are widely used in CSP plants and CBs as storage materials, as they have been demonstrated to significantly increase the reliability of the plants and reduce the levelized cost of energy. The MS thermal properties and affordability make them ideal for storing energy at high temperatures.

The MS mixtures used in modern thermal storage systems are primarily based on nitrates, with the most common mixture being NaNO₃ (60 wt%) – KNO₃ (40 wt%), commonly referred to as "Solar Salt" due to its good chemical safety and material compatibility, allowing the use of standard stainless steels without high corrosion rates. This binary mixture has a melting point ranging from 221 °C to 238 °C and remains thermally stable in the liquid state up to approximately 565 °C, beyond which the salt starts decomposing [167,222].

In recent studies, the lower and upper-temperature thresholds are taken into account, and different compositions have been investigated involving Nitrate, Nitrites, Chloride, Fluoride, and Carbonate bases, yielding crystallization points below 97°C and certain combinations exhibit thermal stability in their liquid state above 700 °C (Table 1, Section 3).

Currently, the focus is on finding improved combinations of MS for higher temperature application. While chloride salts are favoured, they can pose corrosion challenges. Recent studies [223,224] have indicated that stainless steel can be a viable option when coupled with purification processes.

Promising chloride mixture compositions, notably $\text{MgCl}_2\text{-NaCl-KCl}$, have been selected by specialized research group at DLR, NREL and Australia.

In the context of the corrosion, it is crucial to understand that purifying the salt is essential for keeping the corrosion rates acceptable. Ni-base also were considered [36], but are not necessarily required. DLR work showed that stainless steel can have acceptable corrosion rate in chloride contact if salts are purified.

Testing new materials for compatibility or applying coatings is important in corrosion prevention. The coatings play a significant role in reducing corrosion, particularly those made from alloys forming Al_2O_3 or external coatings, but the purification stays preferable to coatings as a method of corrosion prevention.

6.2.2 Molten Salt Thermal Energy Storage Systems and Related Components

Cutting-edge thermal energy storage (TES) systems that utilize molten salt typically consist of two unpressurized tanks:

- The “cold” tank operates at approximately 290 °C;
- The “hot” tank can operate at either 400 °C or 560 °C.

Both tanks are equipped with a foundation, insulation, pumps, valves, electrical heaters and instrumentation to monitor essential parameters such as temperature, pressure, salt level, and flow.

In order to deliver the heat stored in the MS to the power cycle, heat exchangers are required. This already occurs in today's state of the art Generation 2 (Gen2) CSP power plants where a set of nitrate MS/water-steam heat exchangers are employed [225]. This contrasts with other possible CB configurations that utilises a gas as the working fluid in a Brayton power cycle (argon, air, N_2 , CO_2 , etc.) while using solid media (like rocks, ceramics, etc.) as the thermal storage media, avoiding the charge and discharge heat exchanger requirements (on the TES side) [226].

For liquid MS utilisation as the storage media, where the 2-tank concept is usually considered [226], heat exchangers are required either for the charging step (using a heat pump cycle- most likely with a gas working fluid) or for the discharging step (using a higher efficiency power cycle like a sCO_2 , argon or air Brayton power cycle). Besides, special attention to operating temperatures and material compatibility must be given.

According to [227], the most common heat exchanger options for the Steam Generator (SG) are the shell-and-tube, helical coil and printed circuit:

- Shell-and-tube heat exchangers have proven design, capable of simple inspections and maintenance, with long term operation and history in numerous applications, although they are large, heavy and costly;
- Helical coil heat exchangers have a proven design, long term operation history, have better heat transfer than conventional shell-and-tube design, provide a self-cleaning in most applications, although still expensive and large and heavy;
- Printed circuit heat exchangers can be 7 times more compact than a shell-and-tube design, with very high transfer area and efficiency and with lower cost than spiral and shell and tube designs (with significant effort for CO_2 Brayton cycle applications), although it is an unproven design in many applications, with difficult inspections and maintenance, with plugging risks.

Typical heat exchanger in the SG system in current CSP plants (nitrate-based MS up to 550 °C) are based on shell and tube heat exchangers [228], and include a preheater, evaporator, superheater, reheater, with the MS placed on the shell side and the steam/water on the tube side because of its high pressure. Several companies exist that can provide MS (up to 565 °C) heat exchanger solutions, for fluids like, thermal oil, water/steam and hot air, majorly linked to CSP developments (Aalborg, Alfa Laval, etc.).

When considering the next Generation 3 (Gen3) CSP power plants, the use of chloride-based MS TES systems and sCO₂ power cycles are part of the strategy to achieve higher temperature and higher efficiency power cycles [226]. This poses several challenges, where chloride MS to sCO₂ heat exchangers being a critical component of the overall system, due to the fact that it needs to withstand a high temperature corrosive environment on the salt side, and high pressures on the sCO₂ side, along with complex operational challenges [225].

According to [226], cost factors for heat exchanger materials are used in economic models (based on numerous sources in the literature), providing an indicative cost factor that can be applied to estimate different potential costs when using specific steel grades for different temperature ranges (see Table 19).

Table 19. Indicative cost factors for heat exchanger materials (source: [226]).

Temperature [°C]	Material	Cost factor
T < 400	Carbon steel	1
400 ≤ T ≤ 600	Stainless steel	2
T > 600	Nickel alloy	5

As mentioned in [226], compact heat exchangers are preferable in order to reduce this component cost (also enhancing heat transfer surface area), and in fact, for the chloride MS to sCO₂ heat exchanger, high nickel alloys such as Inconel 617 and Haynes 230 could be employed, using a printed circuit heat exchanger in the “CSP Gen3: Liquid-Phase Pathway to SunShot” [226], capable of withstanding high pressures and corrosive effects of the two fluids.

6.2.3 Molten Salt Storage Opportunities for grid and renewable energy sources integration

- The MS-driven stand-alone energy storage is gaining attention for their potential to transform the energy management system. They present potential uses and benefits in inter-grid integrator solutions, offering several prospective uses and advantages:
 - **Energy Storage:** MS stores large amounts of thermal energy, which can be released to generate electricity when needed. This capability makes it a promising storage material for storing renewable energy, such as solar or wind power, for use during times of low generation or high demand;
 - **Renewable Energy Sources Integration:** The MS storage systems can facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources into the grid by providing backup power during periods of low renewable generation. This integration enhances grid stability and ensures a consistent power supply;
 - **Long Duration Storage:** MS energy storage systems have the potential to offer long-duration storage capabilities. This is particularly valuable for supporting grid stability and reliability during prolonged periods of low renewable generation or high demand;

- **Grid Stability:** MS storage systems can help maintain grid stability by providing ancillary services like frequency regulation. With a rapid response time in minutes [229] and the ability to quickly deploy stored energy make MS storage systems an ideal technology for mitigating fluctuations caused by intermittent renewable sources. The MS storage systems are adaptable to various applications, essentially, serve to bridge power and energy management applications [230];
- **Grid Stability:** MS storage systems can help maintain grid stability by providing ancillary services like frequency regulation. With a rapid response time in minutes [229] and the ability to quickly deploy stored energy make MS storage systems an ideal technology for mitigating fluctuations caused by intermittent renewable sources. The MS storage systems are adaptable to various applications, essentially, serve to bridge power and energy management applications [230];
- **Off-Grid Applications:** In remote or off-grid areas, MS energy storage systems can serve as a reliable source of power;
- **Industrial Processes:** MS energy storage systems can also be used in industrial processes that require high-temperature heat, such as steel or cement manufacturing by providing a reliable and sustainable source of heat.

6.3 Beyond State-Of-Art Concept of Carnot batteries

A beyond State-of-Art (SoA) concept relies on the integration of electricity and gas grids. Into a broader perspective, a MS Carnot Battery can operate as an energy hub. On the charging side both electricity and heat might be used:

- Electricity: local or grid transported electricity from renewable (non-dispatchable) sources or from renewable gasses (e.g. green hydrogen via fuel cell) is converted into heat upon use of an electrical heater (resistive, inductive, microwave);
- Heat: heat from waste heat sources (possibly upgraded by means of a heat pump), concentrated solar thermal or by means of combustion of renewable fuels or gasses.

On the discharging side, the stored heat can be transformed (or used directly) as to deliver different energy vectors:

- Heat: direct or indirect (via a process HTF e.g. hot water, steam or air) use of heat to feed industrial processes (industrial process heat);
- Electricity: by using a power block (Rankine Cycle, Brayton Cycle, ORC, etc.) to produce electricity;
- Renewable fuels or gasses: with the combination of heat and/or electricity, feeding thermochemical processes for the production of renewable gasses (mainly, hydrogen and/or syngas).

By combining the various cases, P2X (Power-to-X) or H2X (Heat-to-X) solutions are obtained, where X can be Power, Heat or Fuels. This beyond SoA concept is illustrated in Figure 44.

Figure 44. A conceptual diagram of MS-TES/-Carnot Batteries as inter-grid integrator solutions to produce heat, electricity and fuels using electricity and heat stored in TES.

6.4 Techno-economic assessment/Impact of Carnot Batteries in the Portuguese Energy System

It is understood that storage capabilities in the power system is considered to be one of the key enablers for decarbonization of this sector which also includes the role of handling the demand from both dispatchable and non-dispatchable sources as well as possible provisioning of grid stabilization and flexibility through different services.

Looking at how economical and practical it would be to use CB technologies in specific situations, a technical-economic evaluation of CBs is considered focusing on two main contexts:

- Specific case for a 100 MW_e(net) CB a with certain boundary conditions and assumptions;
- Different CB technological options for an inevitable increase in electricity storage capacity in the Portugues power grid using the Artelys super Grid software.

Upon the use of this models, the following outputs will be sought in the ensuing period:

- technical economic assessment of SALTOpower “beyond SoA” concept in different technological combinations (e.g. with or without charging cycle);
- technical economic assessment of SALTOpower “beyond SoA” concept in different applications/operating temperature levels (e.g. for industrial or utility scale systems);
- technical economic assessment of SALTOpower “beyond SoA” concept in different commodity value scenarios (for power, hydrogen and/or fuels);
- assessment of energy system impacts in different production/load scenarios.

6.4.1 Evaluation of a 100 MWe(net) CB with certain conditions and assumptions:

The purpose of this section is to develop a CB model to perform an annual assessment on an hourly basis, that provides yield (among other parameters) as output based on specific operation mode and strategies, and in this way use these values in an economic assessment. As a first approach, an evaluation of a 100 MWe(net) CB was simulated and compared to another created model of a 100 MWe (AC equivalent) Li-ion BESS. The two technological configurations are:

- Carnot Battery (EH-MS-RC) - A Carnot Battery using nitrate MS as storage media coupled to a steam Rankine cycle, using an electric heater to convert electricity into heat (see Figure 45)- This configuration was chosen since more real data can be collected compared to other CB's configuration, paving the way for the creation of different other configurations;
- Li-ion BESS - A Lithium-ion Battery Electric Storage System using a bi-directional inverter (see Figure 46) - This configuration was chosen due to being broadly implemented globally to several applications and more robust real data sources.

Figure 45. Carnot Battery configuration selected: for the assessment Electric resistances heater (P2H) + MS “Solar Salts” (TES) + Rankine Cycle (H2P).

Figure 46. Li-ion BESS configuration selected.

The technical assessment is based on the annual performance of both plant configurations simulated under different sizing parameters (Charging multiple – Ch_m , and equivalent full load hours of energy storage – FLH). Simulations were performed in TRNSYS 18 with hourly resolution, backed by Python routines for parametric evaluation.

The CB simulation is based on an Electric Heater as a Power2Heat component, heating nitrate MS HTF and withstanding a maximum operating temperature of 565 °C to be stored in a thermal storage system based on a two-tank concept with the same fluid. The plant comprises a Steam Rankine power cycle (0.428 efficiency and 10% parasitic losses [231]) with a dry cooling system.

The Li-ion BESS is composed of a set of Lithium-ion battery packs and a bi-directional inverter and an energy management system, exchanging power in DC between them, while the whole system is able to charge or discharge AC power from or to the grid with a round-trip-efficiency of 85% [232].

Both plants operate with one charge/discharge cycle per day (365 per year), being able to charge for a 12-hour period and discharge for an equivalent period.

As for macroeconomic assumptions, a 25-year lifetime was considered, with a discount rate of 7.0% and an inflation rate of 4.0% (over OPEX costs and revenue), as well as a degradation rate of 1.55%/year for the Li-ion BESS, replacing them at year 13 [233]. A Summary of parametric parameters and assumptions for macroeconomic assessment is presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Specific case of a 100 MW_e(net) CB Parameters, Conditions and Assumptions.

Parameters	Value	Units	Comment
Project Lifetime	25	years	Assumed
Interest rate	7	%/year	Assumed
Inflation Rate	4	%/year	Assumed
Charging Multiple (Ch_m)	1:1:5	adim	Parametric variation adopted (CB only)
Full Load Hours (FLH)	1:1:24	adim	Parametric variation adopted
Charge / Discharge cycles per day	1	cycle / day	Assumed
Charge / Dispatch Acceptable period	12	hours / each	Assumed

For the economic assessment¹³, updated Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX) costs breakdown have been used for each system configuration. The cost model presented here follows a structure proposed by [234] for large sized CSP plants, and NREL values for Li-ion battery systems [234]. The component breakdown of EPC direct costs of CB and BESS systems is presented in Table 21.

Table 21. Component breakdown of EPC direct costs of CB and BESS systems.

CB	BESS	Component	Value	Unit ¹⁴	Ref.
x		Electrical heating	104.7	USD/kW _e	[235]
x		TES	28.16	USD/kWh _{th}	[166,231,234, 236–238]
x		BOP ¹⁵	288.75	USD/kW _e	[166,231,234, 236–238]
x		Power Block ¹⁵	1121.72	USD/kW _e	[166,231,234, 236–238]
	x	Li-ion BESS (Total installation costs included)	537 (2-hrs) 446 (4-hrs) 386 (6-hrs) 358 (8-Hrs) 338 (10-Hrs)	USD/kWh _e	[232]

The EPC indirect costs of both configurations' cases are shown in Table 22. It comprises EPC services, Profit margin and Contingencies, Owner's costs, and the Operation and Maintenance (O&M) costs that constitute the OPEX. CAPEX and OPEX results for different Charging multiple (Ch_m - applicable only to CB) and FLH (Full Load Hours).

¹³ An EUR to USD exchange rate of 1.1147 was considered when needed (mean value of the last 5 years), calculated by <https://www.exchange-rates.org/converter/eur-usd>.

¹⁴ USD means United States Dollars – values consider the accumulated inflation up to 2021 (USD = USD2021) calculated by <https://www.officialdata.org/us/inflation/>.

¹⁵ Based on steam turbine gross power.

Table 22. EPC Indirect costs, Owner's costs, and O&M costs.

EPC Indirect costs	Value	Unit	Ref.
EPC services	5.0	% of EPC direct costs	[234,238]
Profit Margin and Contingencies	10.0	% of EPC direct costs	[238]
Owner's costs	Value	Unit	Ref.
Project development	10.0	% of EPC (direct and indirect) costs	[238]
Additional Owner's cost	3.0	% of EPC (direct and indirect) costs	[234,238]
Infrastructure ¹⁶	6.86×10^6	USD (fixed cost)	[234,238]
O&M costs	Value	Unit	Ref.
CB	2.2	annual % of CAPEX	[238]
Li-ion BESS	2.5	annual % of specific CAPEX in [USD/kW _e]	[232]

After applying the above-mentioned costs, the overall plant costs, on an energy basis, are presented in Figure 47, highlighting the variation of the 100 MW_e(net) electricity storage system depending on the storage duration (FLH). In the CB case the cost tends to be more reduced for higher FLH since the fixed Power cycle associated costs are more diluted as the quantity of (low cost) energy storage increases.

Figure 47. Overall CAPEX expressed here with relation to number of equivalent full load hours (FLH) of storage) comparison between the selected Carnot Battery (with an electric heater multiplier of 3) and Li-ion Battery (considering or not adding the battery extra cost after substitution of the batteries) for different FLH.

The techno-economic comparison is made by using the LCOS [239] indicator for the above-mentioned conditions. Figure 48 presents the LCOS comparison between the two

¹⁶ High voltage grid connection, backup power supply grid connection, water connection, fuel connection, access road – project-specific cost, depending on constraints.

configurations depending on the FLH of storage. This highlights the competitiveness of this CB configuration within these conditions, indicating a favourable economics over Li-ion BESS technology after 4 hours of FLH, with the lowest LCOS with 13 FLH.

Figure 48. LCOS comparison between the selected Carnot Battery (with an electric heater multiplier of 3) and Li-ion Battery for different equivalent full load hours (FLH) of storage.

Further assessments can now be undertaken while using this model:

- Impact of charging cost on LCOS and limit boundary of competitiveness compared to Li-ion BESS;
- Impact of discharging on a limited period of time;
- Impact of using this system with more than one charge/discharge cycle per day, with the associated startup costs/energy losses;
- Impact of adding revenues by potential services and applications;
- Assess long duration storage competitiveness (more than 1 day);
- Off design analysis.

This model can serve as a basis to model different MS based CB configurations.

6.4.2 Analyse of CB technological options integration for the zero-carbon grid: the Portugal case

This assessment is based on various scenarios of competing technologies such as pumped hydro storage, and Carnot batteries considering an electricity production without carbon dioxide emission for the year 2030 in Portugal. In this scenario, the foreseeable load profile is also included which is an increase in the final energy consumption from residential, electric mobility or industrial electrification [240]. Additionally, the grid already processes storage capacity, mainly pumped hydro, leading to the determination of how much additional storage is required.

For this purpose, Artelys Crystal Super Grid is considered as the modelling tool for the electricity production distribution system. It's an independent software specialised in modelling, and optimisation, enabling to:

- Simulate the operational behaviour of energy systems;
- Assess the costs and benefits of infrastructure projects;
- Optimize investments in generation assets, grids and flexibility solutions;
- Evaluate the impacts of climate and energy policies;
- Plan the evolution of energy systems.

A study in Artelys gathers a set of power system configurations and specific parameter and indicator configurations dedicated to the study case (Figure 49).

Figure 49. Typical workflow of the Artelys model.

With reference to the Figure 50, the following terms can be defined:

- A **context** contains all the information required for simulation: portfolio parameters, physical and financial parameters, datasets, optimisation parameters, etc. Several test cases can be included in a context, to represent different weather scenarios;
- A **test case** is a variability dimension, which can cover weather variations or outages for thermal groups, for example. They impact demand, timeseries, renewable generation profiles, temperature-dependent parameters;
- An **asset** represents an entity modelled in a context, which may be a consumer, a producer, etc. Power generation and storage technologies assets available in Artelys are presented in Figure 51
- **Delivery Point (or Node):** Each asset is connected to one or several delivery points, where the supply and demand equilibrium is performed. Generally, a zone (e.g., a country) can be represented by a single delivery point (a national supply-demand equilibrium);
- **Interconnectors** allow for energy exchanges between nodes;
- Several energies can be modelled within a single context, allowing to properly assess gas/power/heat synergies for instance.

Figure 50. Important terms used in Artelys Crystal Super Grid.

Gas production	Heat production	Electricity production	Electricity production
Gas production Methanation	Biomass boiler Electric boiler Gas boiler	Biomass CHP Biomass fleet CCGT CCS fleet	Hydrogen OCGT Lignite fleet Nuclear fleet
Hydrogen production	Gas boiler CCS Geothermal heat Hydrogen boiler	CCGT fleet	OCGT fleet Oil CHP Oil fleet
Electrolysis	Electric heat pump Gas heat pump Solar thermal	Coal CHP Coal fleet CSP fleet	Other fleet
Storage		Decentralized thermal fleet Derived gasses fleet Fuel cell CHP Gas CHP	Other renewable fleet Other thermal fleet
CAES fleet Gas storage		Gas CHP CCS Geothermal fleet	Regulated coal fleet Regulated oil fleet
Generic storage		Hydro fleet	Solar fleet
Hydrogen storage		Hydro RoR Fleet	Waste CHP Waste fleet
Lithium ion battery fleet		Hydrogen CCGT Hydrogen CHP	Wind offshore fleet Wind onshore fleet
Pumped storage fleet			

Figure 51. Artelys physical assets for Power generation and storage technologies.

The assessment first context considers a baseline for the year 2023, which includes actual data on demand, generation, installed renewable energy (RE), and storage capacities as showed in Figure 52 depicts the electricity grid balance in Portugal for the year 2023. The data presented reflects real-time observations collected over a week in May, showcasing a scenario characterized by a low share of renewable energy sources (RES), substantial fossil fuel generation, and reliance on electricity imports. Sourced from the REN data hub [241], this visualization offers valuable insights into the composition of Portugal's energy mix and its operational dynamics during a specific period.

The assessment first context considers a baseline for the year 2023, which includes actual data on demand, generation, installed renewable energy (RE), and storage capacities. As shown in Figure 52, it presents the electricity grid balance in Portugal for the year 2023. The data presented reflects real-time observations collected over a week in May, showcasing a scenario characterized by a low

share of renewable energy sources (RES), substantial fossil fuel generation, and reliance on electricity imports [241]. In the second context, the 2030 scenario, projected capacities, and the CO₂ target (Table 23) specified in the PNEC [240] are considered and integrated into the model. Figure 53 presents a comparative analysis of electricity grid production, focusing solely on renewable energy sources (RES), versus load in Portugal for two working days in May. On the left side of the figure, the graph illustrates the actual RES generation data for the year 2023 [241], on the right side, the graph presents the estimated RES generation by the year 2030, based on RES installed capacity targets. These estimates take into account multipliers related to the 2023 RES production, with multipliers for solar set at 7.8, wind at 2.3, hydro at 1.0, and biomass at 2.0.

The National Energy and Climate Plan 2021-2030 (PNEC 2030) outlines ambitious goals for renewable energies integration:

1. Renewable Energy Targets:
 - a. The PNEC 2030 outlines ambitious goals for renewable energy integration. Portugal aims to significantly increase its renewable energy capacity during this decade;
 - b. Through competitive auctions, the plan seeks to double the solar energy capacity by 2030 (Table 24 and Table 25).
2. Hydrogen Focus:
 - a. The PNEC 2030 promotes the production and utilization of renewable gases, including hydrogen, as part of the energy transition, this includes installation of 5.5 GW of electrolyzers by 2030;
 - b. Efforts will be made to promote the production and utilization of hydrogen as a clean energy source.
3. Phasing Out Coal:
 - a. Portugal is committed to reducing its reliance on coal for electricity generation;
 - b. The plan sets clear deadlines: electricity production from coal will cease at the Pego power plant by 2021 and at the Sines power plant by 2023.
4. Sustainable Mobility:
 - a. The PNEC 2030 prioritizes sustainable transportation;
 - b. Measures will encourage modal shifts toward public transportation and electric mobility.

Table 23. Portugal's national targets for 2030.

National Targets	Emissions (Without LULUCF)	Energy Efficiency (Reduction In Primary Energy)	Renewables (In Gross Final Energy Consumption)	Renewable In Transport	Electrical Interconnections
PNEC 2030	-45% a -55%	35%	47%	20%	15%
Revision PNEC 2030	-55%	35%	49%	23%	15%

Table 24. Share of renewable energy in final energy consumption by sector for 2030.

Year	PNEC 2030			Revision PNEC 2030	
	2020	2025	2030	2025	2030
Electricity	60%	69%	80%	77%	85%
Heating and Cooling	34%	36%	38%	43%	47%
Transport	10%	13%	20%	10%	23%

Table 25. Installed and forecasting capacity, expressed in GW, for electricity production by technology in Portugal in 2030.

Energy	2025	2030
Hydro:	8.1	8.1
With pumping	3.6	3.9
Wind:	6.3	12.4
Onshore wind	6.3	10.4
Offshore wind	0.0	2.0
Solar Photovoltaic	8.4	20.4
Centralized	6.1	14.9
Decentralized	2.3	5.5
Concentrated Solar Power	0.0	0.6
Biomass/Biogas and waste	1.2	1.4
Geothermal	0.0	0.1
Waves	0.0	0.2
Natural gas	4.9	3.8
Oil products	0.6	0.4
Total	30	47

Figure 52. Electricity grid balance in Portugal for the year 2023, representing real data gathered from week in May with a low RES share, with high fossil generation and electricity import (data source: [241]).

Load vs RES Generation in Portugal between real 2023 data and 2030 estimation (based on PNEC2030 targets)

Figure 53. Electricity grid production (considering only RES) vs Load in Portugal for two working days in May: on the left, real RES generation in 2023 (data source: [241]); on the right, the estimated RES generation by 2030 (based on RES installed capacity targets - multipliers considered related to 2023 RES production: Solar 7.8; Wind 2.3; Hydro 1.0; Biomass 2.0), highlighting the excess peak power (MW) and cumulative energy (MWh) on the daily period and the undersupply peak power (MW) and cumulative energy (MWh) on the night period.

The actual status production and consumption of the Portuguese grid and the 2030 scenario were carried out.

The objective is to evaluate numerous potential combinations of CBs (Figure 36) to attain the set goals, using historical renewable production data on an hourly basis. This data-driven approach ensures a realistic understanding of renewable energy generation patterns and helps identify optimal solutions for the storage capacities integrated.

The assessment applies rational dispatch profiles to ensure efficient utilization of resources and minimization of curtailments. The outcome will present a suite of optimum solutions, considering both cost-effectiveness and curtailment mitigation.

Economic and technical impacts will be assessed, including response times and the levelized cost of storage, ensuring the feasibility and sustainability of proposed solutions.

Furthermore, the assessment quantifies the effects of integrating CBs into the system, analysing response times and the spectrum of services they can provide. This analysis provides insights into the added value and versatility of CBs in enhancing system resilience and performance.

The proposed approach involves defining a model for a CB, which could be implemented either directly or indirectly. By integrating additional storage capacity through CBs, it is intended to address the challenge of managing excess production from renewable sources effectively. Furthermore, it is foreseen to explore a scenario that excludes conventional production entirely, relying solely on renewable sources, with potential upgrades to renewable energy production capacity to meet demand.

Quantifying the impact of incorporating CBs into the energy system will be a critical aspect of our analysis, providing insights into their role in enhancing grid stability and facilitating greater utilization of renewable energy.

Moreover, the updated model will feature various delivery points distributed across Portugal region, allowing for a more granular examination of local production and consumption dynamics, which is essential for ensuring the reliability and efficiency of the energy system.

7 SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE

- [1] Bernagozzi M, Panesar AS, Morgan R. Molten salt selection methodology for medium temperature liquid air energy storage application. *Appl Energy* 2019;248:500–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.04.136>.
- [2] Myers PD, Goswami DY. Thermal energy storage using chloride salts and their eutectics. *Appl Therm Eng* 2016;109:889–900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APPLTHERMALENG.2016.07.046>.
- [3] Sau S, Corsaro N, Crescenzi T, D’Ottavi C, Liberatore R, Licoccia S, et al. Techno-economic comparison between CSP plants presenting two different heat transfer fluids. *Appl Energy* 2016;168:96–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.01.066>.
- [4] Wang Y, Zhu C, Zhang M, Zhou W. Molten salt reactors. *Nuclear Power Reactor Designs*, Elsevier; 2024, p. 163–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-99880-2.00009-6>.
- [5] Moir RW, Teller E. Thorium-Fueled Underground Power Plant Based on Molten Salt Technology. *Nucl Technol* 2005;151:334–40. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT05-A3655>.
- [6] Ignatiev V V., Feynberg OS, Zagnitko A V., Merzlyakov A V., Surenkov AI, Panov A V., et al. Molten-salt reactors: New possibilities, problems and solutions articles. *Atomic Energy* 2012;112:157–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10512-012-9537-2/METRICS>.
- [7] Elsheikh BM. Safety assessment of molten salt reactors in comparison with light water reactors. *J Radiat Res Appl Sci* 2013;6:63–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrras.2013.10.008>.
- [8] Faure B, Kooyman T. A comparison of actinide halides for use in molten salt reactor fuels. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 2022;144:104082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2021.104082>.
- [9] Roper R, Harkema M, Sabharwall P, Riddle C, Chisholm B, Day B, et al. Molten salt for advanced energy applications: A review. *Ann Nucl Energy* 2022;169:108924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2021.108924>.
- [10] Hu X, Hu Y, Xu Q, Wang X, Li G, Cheng H, et al. Molten salt-promoted Ni–Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst for methane decomposition. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2020;45:4244–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.11.209>.
- [11] Xie K, Kamali AR. Electrochemical production of hydrogen in molten salt. *Energy Convers Manag* 2022;251:114980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.114980>.
- [12] Fujiwara S, Inaba M, Tasaka A. New molten salt systems for high temperature molten salt batteries: Ternary and quaternary molten salt systems based on LiF–LiCl, LiF–LiBr, and LiCl–LiBr. *J Power Sources* 2011;196:4012–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2010.12.009>.
- [13] Li J, Xie Y, Zeng K, Flamant G, Yang H, Yang X, et al. Biomass gasification in molten salt for syngas production. *Energy* 2020;210:118563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118563>.
- [14] Mahinroosta M, Allahverdi A. Hazardous aluminum dross characterization and recycling strategies: A critical review. *J Environ Manage* 2018;223:452–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.06.068>.
- [15] Flandinet L, Tedjar F, Ghetta V, Fouletier J. Metals recovering from waste printed circuit boards (WPCBs) using molten salts. *J Hazard Mater* 2012;213–214:485–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2012.02.037>.
- [16] Zhu X, Sun M, Zhu X, Guo W, Luo Z, Cai W, et al. Molten salt shielded pyrolysis of biomass waste: Development of hierarchical biochar, salt recovery, CO₂ adsorption. *Fuel* 2023;334:126565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2022.126565>.

- [17] Xie K, Hu H, Cao J, Yang F, Liu H, Li A, et al. A novel method for salts removal from municipal solid waste incineration fly ash through the molten salt thermal treatment. *Chemosphere* 2020;241:125107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.125107>.
- [18] Bhatnagar P, Siddiqui S, Sreedhar I, Parameshwaran R. Molten salts: Potential candidates for thermal energy storage applications. *Int J Energy Res* 2022;46:17755–85. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.8441>.
- [19] Vignarooban K, Xu X, Arvay A, Hsu K, Kannan AM. Heat transfer fluids for concentrating solar power systems – A review. *Appl Energy* 2015;146:383–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2015.01.125>.
- [20] Collares-Pereira M, Canavarró D, Guerreiro LL. Linear Fresnel reflector (LFR) plants using superheated steam, molten salts, and other heat transfer fluids. *Advances in Concentrating Solar Thermal Research and Technology*, Elsevier; 2017, p. 339–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100516-3.00015-0>.
- [21] Laing D, Bauer T, Breidenbach N, Hachmann B, Johnson M. Development of high temperature phase-change-material storages. *Appl Energy* 2013;109:497–504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2012.11.063>.
- [22] Fiorucci LC, Goldstein SL, Fiorucci LC, Goldstein SL. Manufacture, distribution, and handling of nitrate salts for solar-thermal applications. *STIN* 1982;83:21625.
- [23] Bradshaw RW, Siegel NP. Molten Nitrate Salt Development for Thermal Energy Storage in Parabolic Trough Solar Power Systems. *ES2008*, 2008.
- [24] Jriri T, Rogez J, Bergman C, Mathieu JC. Thermodynamic study of the condensed phases of NaNO₃, KNO₃ and CsNO₃ and their transitions. *Thermochim Acta* 1995;266:147–61. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6031\(95\)02337-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6031(95)02337-2).
- [25] Bauer T, Pflieger N, Breidenbach N, Eck M, Laing D, Kaesche S. Material aspects of Solar Salt for sensible heat storage. *Appl Energy* 2013;111:1114–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2013.04.072>.
- [26] Wu Y ting, Li Y, Ren N, Ma C fang. Improving the thermal properties of NaNO₃-KNO₃ for concentrating solar power by adding additives. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2017;160:263–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2016.10.013>.
- [27] Bonk A, Sau S, Uranga N, Hernaiz M, Bauer T. Advanced heat transfer fluids for direct molten salt line-focusing CSP plants. *Prog Energy Combust Sci* 2018;67:69–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PECS.2018.02.002>.
- [28] Bradshaw RW, Meeker DE. High-temperature stability of ternary nitrate molten salts for solar thermal energy systems. *Solar Energy Materials* 1990;21:51–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1633\(90\)90042-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1633(90)90042-Y).
- [29] Raade JW, Padowitz D. Development of Molten Salt Heat Transfer Fluid With Low Melting Point and High Thermal Stability. *J Sol Energy Eng* 2011;133:031013. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4004243>.
- [30] Li X, Xie L. Experimental investigation and thermodynamic modeling of the LiNO₃-RbNO₃-AgNO₃ system and its subsystems. *J Alloys Compd* 2018;736:124–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JALLCOM.2017.11.071>.
- [31] Vallet C. Phase diagrams and thermodynamic properties of some molten nitrate mixtures. *J Chem Thermodyn* 1972;4:105–14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9614\(72\)80013-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9614(72)80013-2).

- [32] Bradshaw RW, Meeker DE. High-temperature stability of ternary nitrate molten salts for solar thermal energy systems. *Solar Energy Materials* 1990;21:51–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1633\(90\)90042-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1633(90)90042-Y).
- [33] Sau S, Corsaro N, Crescenzi T, D'Ottavi C, D'Ottavi C, Liberatore R, et al. Techno-economic comparison between CSP plants presenting two different heat transfer fluids. *Appl Energy* 2016;168:96–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2016.01.066>.
- [34] Bonk A, Sau S, Uranga N, Hernaiz M, Bauer T. Advanced heat transfer fluids for direct molten salt line-focusing CSP plants. *Prog Energy Combust Sci* 2018;67:69–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PECS.2018.02.002>.
- [35] Bauer T, Pflieger N, Laing D, Steinmann W-D, Eck M, Kaesche S. High-Temperature Molten Salts for Solar Power Application. *Molten Salts Chemistry*, Elsevier; 2013, p. 415–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-398538-5.00020-2>.
- [36] Ding W, Bauer T. Progress in Research and Development of Molten Chloride Salt Technology for Next Generation Concentrated Solar Power Plants. *Engineering* 2021;7:334–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENG.2020.06.027>.
- [37] Gomez JC. High-Temperature Phase Change Materials (PCM) Candidates for Thermal Energy Storage (TES) Applications 2011.
- [38] Misra AI, Daniel Whittenberger J, Philadelphia Aic, M AK. Fluoride salts and container materials for thermal energy storage applications in the temperature range 973 to 1400 K 1987.
- [39] Vidal JC, Klammer N. Molten chloride technology pathway to meet the U.S. DOE sunshot initiative with Gen3 CSP. *AIP Conf Proc* 2019;2126. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5117601/701454>.
- [40] Tripi V, Sau S, Tizzoni AC, Mansi E, Spadoni A, Corsaro N, et al. A general thermodynamic model for eutectics of phase change molten salts in concentrating solar power applications. *J Energy Storage* 2021;33:102065. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EST.2020.102065>.
- [41] Hosoya Y, Yoneoka T, Tanaka S, Terai T. Compatibility of structural materials with molten chloride mixture at high temperature. *Journal of Nuclear Materials* 1997;248:348–53.
- [42] An Investigation of Primary Circuit Materials in Molten Chloride Salts with the Design of High Temperature Corrosion Vessels — Research Explorer The University of Manchester n.d. <https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/an-investigation-of-primary-circuit-materials-in-molten-chloride-> (accessed March 19, 2024).
- [43] Kruiženga A. Corrosion mechanisms in chloride and carbonate salts. Albuquerque, NM, and Livermore, CA (United States): 2012. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1051732>.
- [44] Villada C, Ding W, Bonk A, Bauer T. Engineering molten MgCl₂–KCl–NaCl salt for high-temperature thermal energy storage: Review on salt properties and corrosion control strategies. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2021;232:111344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2021.111344>.
- [45] Huang Q, Lu G, Wang J, Yu J. Thermal decomposition mechanisms of MgCl₂·6H₂O and MgCl₂·H₂O. *J Anal Appl Pyrolysis* 2011;1:159–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAAP.2011.02.005>.
- [46] Yin H, Wang Z, Lai X, Wang Y, Tang Z. Optimum design and key thermal property of NaCl–KCl–CaCl₂ eutectic salt for ultra-high-temperature thermal energy storage. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2022;236:111541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2021.111541>.
- [47] Kruiženga AM, Andracka CE, Kolb WJ. *Molten Salt Technology*. 2016.

- [48] Mahboob K, Khan AA, Khan MA, Sarwar J, Khan TA. Comparison of $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-K}_2\text{CO}_3$, KCl-MgCl_2 and $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-KNO}_3$ as heat transfer fluid for different sCO_2 and steam power cycles in CSP tower plant under different DNI conditions. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering* 2021;13. https://doi.org/10.1177/16878140211011900/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_16878140211011900-FIG11.JPEG.
- [49] Prieto C, Fereres S, Ruiz-Cabañas FJ, Rodriguez-Sanchez A, Montero C. Carbonate molten salt solar thermal pilot facility: Plant design, commissioning and operation up to 700 °C. *Renew Energy* 2020;151:528–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RENENE.2019.11.045>.
- [50] Li Q, Li C, Du Z, Jiang F, Ding Y. A review of performance investigation and enhancement of shell and tube thermal energy storage device containing molten salt based phase change materials for medium and high temperature applications. *Appl Energy* 2019;255:113806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2019.113806>.
- [51] Sau GS, Tripi V, Tizzoni AC, Liberatore R, Mansi E, Spadoni A, et al. High-Temperature Chloride-Carbonate Phase Change Material: Thermal Performances and Modelling of a Packed Bed Storage System for Concentrating Solar Power Plants. *Energies* 2021, Vol 14, Page 5339 2021;14:5339. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN14175339>.
- [52] Dunlop TO, Jarvis DJ, Voice WE, Sullivan JH. Stabilization of molten salt materials using metal chlorides for solar thermal storage. *Scientific Reports* 2018 8:1 2018;8:1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-26537-8>.
- [53] Zavoico AB. Solar Power Tower Design Basis Document, Revision 0. Albuquerque, NM, and Livermore, CA: 2001. <https://doi.org/10.2172/786629>.
- [54] Boerema N, Morrison G, Taylor R, Rosengarten G. Liquid sodium versus Hitec as a heat transfer fluid in solar thermal central receiver systems. *Solar Energy* 2012;86:2293–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLENER.2012.05.001>.
- [55] Serrano-López R, Fradera J, Cuesta-López S. Molten salts database for energy applications. *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification* 2013;73:87–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2013.07.008>.
- [56] Raade JW, Padowitz D. Development of molten salt heat transfer fluid with low melting point and high thermal stability. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, Transactions of the ASME* 2011;133. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4004243/456229>.
- [57] Zhao CY, Wu ZG. Thermal property characterization of a low melting-temperature ternary nitrate salt mixture for thermal energy storage systems. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2011;95:3341–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2011.07.029>.
- [58] Siegel NP, Bradshaw RW, Cordaro JB, Kruienza AM. Thermophysical Property Measurement of Nitrate Salt Heat Transfer Fluids. *ASME 2011 5th International Conference on Energy Sustainability, ES 2011* 2012:439–46. <https://doi.org/10.1115/ES2011-54058>.
- [59] Wang T, Mantha D, Reddy RG. Thermal stability of the eutectic composition in $\text{LiNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3\text{-KNO}_3$ ternary system used for thermal energy storage. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2012;100:162–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2012.01.009>.
- [60] Coscia K, Nelle S, Elliott T, Mohapatra S, Oztekin A, Neti S. Thermophysical properties of $\text{LiNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3\text{-KNO}_3$ mixtures for use in concentrated solar power. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, Transactions of the ASME* 2013;135:1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4024069/379744>.

- [61] Roget F, Favotto C, Rogez J. Study of the $\text{KNO}_3\text{--LiNO}_3$ and $\text{KNO}_3\text{--NaNO}_3\text{--LiNO}_3$ eutectics as phase change materials for thermal storage in a low-temperature solar power plant. *Solar Energy* 2013;95:155–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLENER.2013.06.008>.
- [62] Peng Q, Ding J, Wei X, Jiang G. Thermodynamic Investigation of the Eutectic Mixture of the $\text{LiNO}_3\text{--NaNO}_3\text{--KNO}_3\text{--Ca(NO}_3)_2$ System. *Int J Thermophys* 2017;38:1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10765-017-2284-9/FIGURES/3>.
- [63] Jiang Z, Leng G, Ye F, Ge Z, Liu C, Wang L, et al. Form-stable $\text{LiNO}_3\text{--NaNO}_3\text{--KNO}_3\text{--Ca(NO}_3)_2$ /calcium silicate composite phase change material (PCM) for mid-low temperature thermal energy storage. *Energy Convers Manag* 2015;106:165–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2015.09.035>.
- [64] Cordaro JG, Rubin NC, Bradshaw RW. Multicomponent molten salt mixtures based on nitrate/nitrite anions. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, Transactions of the ASME* 2011;133. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4003418/444222>.
- [65] Wang T, Mantha D, Reddy RG. Novel low melting point quaternary eutectic system for solar thermal energy storage. *Appl Energy* 2013;102:1422–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2012.09.001>.
- [66] Li Y, Xu X, Wang X, Li P, Hao Q, Xiao B. Survey and evaluation of equations for thermophysical properties of binary/ternary eutectic salts from NaCl , KCl , MgCl_2 , CaCl_2 , ZnCl_2 for heat transfer and thermal storage fluids in CSP. *Solar Energy* 2017;152:57–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLENER.2017.03.019>.
- [67] Li P, Molina E, Wang K, Xu X, Dehghani G, Kohli A, et al. Thermal and Transport Properties of NaCl-KCl-ZnCl_2 Eutectic Salts for New Generation High-Temperature Heat-Transfer Fluids. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, Transactions of the ASME* 2016;138. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4033793/383681>.
- [68] Xu X, Wang X, Li P, Li Y, Hao Q, Xiao B, et al. Experimental Test of Properties of KCl-MgCl_2 Eutectic Molten Salt for Heat Transfer and Thermal Storage Fluid in Concentrated Solar Power Systems. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, Transactions of the ASME* 2018;140. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4040065/368304>.
- [69] Wei X, Song M, Wang W, Ding J, Yang J. Design and thermal properties of a novel ternary chloride eutectics for high-temperature solar energy storage. *Appl Energy* 2015;156:306–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2015.07.022>.
- [70] Du L, Tian H, Wang W, Ding J, Wei X, Song M. Thermal Stability of the Eutectic Composition in $\text{NaCl-CaCl}_2\text{-MgCl}_2$ Ternary System Used for Thermal Energy Storage Applications. *Energy Procedia* 2017;105:4185–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYPRO.2017.03.892>.
- [71] Du L, Ding J, Tian H, Wang W, Wei X, Song M. Thermal properties and thermal stability of the ternary eutectic salt $\text{NaCl-CaCl}_2\text{-MgCl}_2$ used in high-temperature thermal energy storage process. *Appl Energy* 2017;204:1225–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2017.03.096>.
- [72] Xu X, Dehghani G, Ning J, Li P. Basic properties of eutectic chloride salts NaCl-KCl-ZnCl_2 and NaCl-KCl-MgCl_2 as HTFs and thermal storage media measured using simultaneous DSC-TGA. *Solar Energy* 2018;162:431–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLENER.2018.01.067>.
- [73] Forsberg CW, Peterson PF, Zhao H. High-Temperature Liquid-Fluoride-Salt Closed-Brayton-Cycle Solar Power Towers. *J Sol Energy Eng* 2007;129:141–6. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2710245>.
- [74] Williams DF. Assessment of Candidate Molten Salt Coolants for the Advanced High Temperature Reactor (AHTR). Oak Ridge, TN: 2006. <https://doi.org/10.2172/885975>.

- [75] Jerden J. Molten Salt Thermophysical Properties Database Development: 2019 Update Chemical and Fuel Cycle Technologies Division. 2019.
- [76] An XH, Cheng JH, Su T, Zhang P. Determination of thermal physical properties of alkali fluoride/carbonate eutectic molten salt. *AIP Conf Proc* 2017;1850:70001. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4984415/616834>.
- [77] Giaconia A, Tizzoni AC, Sau S, Corsaro N, Mansi E, Spadoni A, et al. Assessment and Perspectives of Heat Transfer Fluids for CSP Applications. *Energies* 2021, Vol 14, Page 7486 2021;14:7486. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN14227486>.
- [78] Delise T, Tizzoni AC, Ferrara M, Corsaro N, D'Ottavi C, Sau S, et al. Thermophysical, environmental, and compatibility properties of nitrate and nitrite containing molten salts for medium temperature CSP applications: A critical review. *J Eur Ceram Soc* 2019;39:92–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2018.07.057>.
- [79] Kust RN, Burke JD. Thermal decomposition in alkali metal nitrate melts. *Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Letters* 1970;6:333–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-1650\(70\)80243-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-1650(70)80243-4).
- [80] Wang J, Jiang Y, Ni Y, Wu A, Li J. Investigation on static and dynamic corrosion behaviors of thermal energy transfer and storage system materials by molten salts in concentrating solar power plants. *Materials and Corrosion* 2019;70:102–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/maco.201810362>.
- [81] Delise T, Tizzoni AC, Menale C, Telling MTF, Bubbico R, Crescenzi T, et al. Technical and economic analysis of a CSP plant presenting a low freezing ternary mixture as storage and transfer fluid. *Appl Energy* 2020;265:114676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114676>.
- [82] IRENA. Renewable Energy Statistics 2018. The International Renewable Energy Agency 2018.
- [83] Bertuccioli L, Chan A, Hart D, Lehner F, Madden B, Standen E. Development of Water Electrolysis in the European Union. 2014.
- [84] Sattler C, Monnerie N, Houaijia A, Romero M, Gonzalez-Aguillar J, Reyes MA, et al. Final report on “Technology Roadmap for Solar Fuels.” 2017.
- [85] Compact Multifuel-Energy To Hydrogen converter | CoMETHy | Project | News & Multimedia | FP7 | CORDIS | European Commission n.d. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/279075/reporting> (accessed March 12, 2024).
- [86] FUEL CELLS AND HYDROGEN JOINT UNDERTAKING (FCH JU) Multi-Annual Work Plan. 2014.
- [87] Fujiwara S, Kasai S, Yamauchi H, Yamada K, Makino S, Matsunaga K, et al. Hydrogen production by high temperature electrolysis with nuclear reactor. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 2008;50:422–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PNUCENE.2007.11.025>.
- [88] Sunfire electrolyzers - Sunfire n.d. <https://www.sunfire.de/en/hydrogen> (accessed March 12, 2024).
- [89] Badwal SPS, Giddey SS, Munnings C, Bhatt AI, Hollenkamp AF. Emerging electrochemical energy conversion and storage technologies. *Front Chem* 2014;2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2014.00079>.
- [90] Safari F, Dincer I. A review and comparative evaluation of thermochemical water splitting cycles for hydrogen production. *Energy Convers Manag* 2020;205:112182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.112182>.
- [91] Liberatore R, Caputo G, Felici C, Spadoni A. Demonstration of Hydrogen Production by the Sulphur-Iodine Cycle: Realization of a 10 NL/h Plant. *Essen Schriften Des Forschungszentrums Jülich / Energy & Environment* n.d.;78.

- [92] Liberatore R, Lanchi M, Giaconia A, Tarquini P. Energy and economic assessment of an industrial plant for the hydrogen production by water-splitting through the sulfur-iodine thermochemical cycle powered by concentrated solar energy. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2012;37:9550–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2012.03.088>.
- [93] Prosini PP, Cento C, Giaconia A, Caputo G, Sau S. A modified sulphur–iodine cycle for efficient solar hydrogen production. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2009;34:1218–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2008.11.011>.
- [94] Lanchi M, Varsano F, Brunetti B, Murmura MA, Annesini MC, Turchetti L, et al. Thermal characterization of a cavity receiver for hydrogen production by thermochemical cycles operating at moderate temperatures. *Solar Energy* 2013;92:256–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLENER.2013.03.008>.
- [95] Parisi M, Giaconia A, Sau S, Spadoni A, Caputo G, Tarquini P. Bunsen reaction and hydriodic phase purification in the sulfur–iodine process: An experimental investigation. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2011;36:2007–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.11.039>.
- [96] Liberatore R, Ceroli A, Lanchi M, Spadoni A, Tarquini P. Experimental vapour–liquid equilibrium data of HI–H₂O–I₂ mixtures for hydrogen production by Sulphur–Iodine thermochemical cycle. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2008;33:4283–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2008.06.009>.
- [97] BARBAROSSA V, BRUTTI S, DIAMANTI M, SAU S, DEMARIA G. Catalytic thermal decomposition of sulphuric acid in sulphur–iodine cycle for hydrogen production. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2006;31:883–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2005.08.003>.
- [98] Giaconia A, Sau S, Felici C, Tarquini P, Karagiannakis G, Pagkoura C, et al. Hydrogen production via sulfur-based thermochemical cycles: Part 2: Performance evaluation of Fe₂O₃-based catalysts for the sulfuric acid decomposition step. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2011;36:6496–509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2011.02.137>.
- [99] Favuzza P, Felici C, Lanchi M, Liberatore R, Mazzocchia C V., Spadoni A, et al. Decomposition of hydrogen iodide in the S–I thermochemical cycle over Ni catalyst systems. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2009;34:4049–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2008.07.076>.
- [100] Lanchi M, Caputo G, Liberatore R, Marrelli L, Sau S, Spadoni A, et al. Use of metallic Ni for H₂ production in S–I thermochemical cycle: Experimental and theoretical analysis. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2009;34:1200–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2008.10.044>.
- [101] Varsano F, Padella F, Alvani C, Bellusci M, La Barbera A. Chemical aspects of the water-splitting thermochemical cycle based on sodium manganese ferrite. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2012;37:11595–601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2012.05.042>.
- [102] Liberatore R, Bassi A, Turchetti L, Venturin M. Multi-objective optimization of a hydrogen production through the HyS process powered by solar energy in different scenarios. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2018;43:8683–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2018.03.109>.
- [103] Liberatore R, Lanchi M, Turchetti L. Hydrogen production by the solar-powered hybrid sulfur process: Analysis of the integration of the CSP and chemical plants in selected scenarios. *AIP Conf Proc* 2016;1734:120006. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4949208/997420>.
- [104] Turchetti L, Liberatore R, Sau S, Tizzoni AC. Carbon-free production of hydrogen via the solar powered hybrid sulfur cycle: The SOL2HY2 project. *Chem Eng Trans* 2015;43:2179–84. <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1543364>.

- [105] Tizzoni AC, Corsaro N, D'Ottavi C, Licoccia S, Sau S, Tarquini P. Oxygen production by intermediate metal sulphates in sulphur based thermochemical water splitting cycles. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2015;40:4065–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2015.01.147>.
- [106] Taylor R, Davenport R, Talbot J, Herz R, Luc W, Genders D, et al. Status of the Solar Sulfur Ammonia Thermochemical Hydrogen Production System for Splitting Water. *Energy Procedia* 2014;49:2047–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYPRO.2014.03.217>.
- [107] Navarro RM, Peña MA, Fierro JLG. Hydrogen production reactions from carbon feedstocks: Fossil fuels and biomass. *Chem Rev* 2007;107:3952–91. https://doi.org/10.1021/CR0501994/ASSET/CR0501994.FP.PNG_V03.
- [108] Giaconia A, Turchetti L, Monteleone G, Morico B, Iaquaniello G, Shabtai K, et al. Development of a solar-powered, fuel-flexible compact steam reformer: The CoMETHy project. *Chem Eng Trans* 2013;35:433–8. <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1335072>.
- [109] Krishna BB, Biswas B, Bhaskar T. Gasification of Lignocellulosic Biomass. *Biomass, Biofuels, Biochemicals: Biofuels: Alternative Feedstocks and Conversion Processes for the Production of Liquid and Gaseous Biofuels* 2019:285–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-816856-1.00012-9>.
- [110] Yan M, Afxentiou N, Fokaides PA. The State of the Art Overview of the Biomass Gasification Technology. *Current Sustainable/Renewable Energy Reports* 2021;8:282–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40518-021-00196-2/METRICS>.
- [111] Jha S, Okolie JA, Nanda S, Dalai AK. A Review of Biomass Resources and Thermochemical Conversion Technologies. *Chem Eng Technol* 2022;45:791–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/CEAT.202100503>.
- [112] Qian K, Kumar A, Patil K, Bellmer D, Wang D, Yuan W, et al. Effects of Biomass Feedstocks and Gasification Conditions on the Physicochemical Properties of Char. *Energies* 2013, Vol 6, Pages 3972–3986 2013;6:3972–86. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN6083972>.
- [113] Wu Y, Yang W, Blasiak W. Energy and Exergy Analysis of High Temperature Agent Gasification of Biomass. *Energies* 2014, Vol 7, Pages 2107–2122 2014;7:2107–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN7042107>.
- [114] Liu B, Ji S. Comparative study of fluidized-bed and fixed-bed reactor for syngas methanation over Ni-W/TiO₂-SiO₂ catalyst. *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 2013;22:740–6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-4956\(13\)60098-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-4956(13)60098-4).
- [115] Li M, Luo N, Lu Y. Biomass Energy Technological Paradigm (BETP): Trends in This Sector. *Sustainability* 2017, Vol 9, Page 567 2017;9:567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU9040567>.
- [116] Benanti E, Braccio G, Colonna N, Motola V. Energia dalle biomasse Tecnologie e prospettive n.d.
- [117] Mandl C, Biedermann F, Obernberger I. Updraft fixed-bed gasification of softwood pellets: mathematical modelling and comparison with experimental data 2009.
- [118] Kruesi M, Jovanovic ZR, Steinfeld A. A two-zone solar-driven gasifier concept: Reactor design and experimental evaluation with bagasse particles. *Fuel* 2014;117:680–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUEL.2013.09.011>.
- [119] Mendonça M, Mantilla V, Patela J, Silva V, Resende F. Design and experimental tests of an Imbert type downdraft gasifier prototype and clean-up system for small-scale biomass-based power generation. *Renewable Energy and Environmental Sustainability* 2022;7:10. <https://doi.org/10.1051/REES/2021057>.
- [120] Biomass Gasification Technology for producing Electricity, Thermal Heat and Gas n.d.

- [121] Rodriguez Correa C, Kruse A. Supercritical water gasification of biomass for hydrogen production – Review. *J Supercrit Fluids* 2018;133:573–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUPFLU.2017.09.019>.
- [122] Reddy SN, Nanda S, Dalai AK, Kozinski JA. Supercritical water gasification of biomass for hydrogen production. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2014;39:6912–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2014.02.125>.
- [123] Pandey A, Larroche C, Ricke SC, Dussap C-G, Gnansounou E, editors. *Biofuels - Alternative Feedstocks and Conversion Processes*. Elsevier; 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2010-0-65927-X>.
- [124] Davda RR, Shabaker JW, Huber GW, Cortright RD, Dumesic JA. A review of catalytic issues and process conditions for renewable hydrogen and alkanes by aqueous-phase reforming of oxygenated hydrocarbons over supported metal catalysts. *Appl Catal B* 2005;56:171–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APCATB.2004.04.027>.
- [125] Osada M, Sato T, Watanabe M, Shirai M, Arai K. CATALYTIC GASIFICATION OF WOOD BIOMASS IN SUBCRITICAL AND SUPERCRITICAL WATER. *Combustion Science and Technology* 2006;178:537–52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00102200500290807>.
- [126] Elliott DC. Catalytic hydrothermal gasification of biomass. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining* 2008;2:254–65. <https://doi.org/10.1002/BBB.74>.
- [127] Matsumura Y, Minowa T, Potic B, Kersten SRA, Prins W, Van Swaaij WPM, et al. Biomass gasification in near- and super-critical water: Status and prospects. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2005;29:269–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMBIOE.2005.04.006>.
- [128] Chuntanapum A, Matsumura Y. Char formation mechanism in supercritical water gasification process: A study of model compounds. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 2010;49:4055–62. https://doi.org/10.1021/IE901346H/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/IE-2009-01346H_0004.JPEG.
- [129] Wang AG, Austin D, Song H. Catalytic Biomass Valorization. *Biomass Volume Estimation and Valorization for Energy*, InTech; 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5772/65826>.
- [130] Kim JS, Choi GG. Pyrolysis of Lignocellulosic Biomass for Biochemical Production. *Waste Biorefinery: Potential and Perspectives* 2018:323–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63992-9.00011-2>.
- [131] Müller FL. *Solar Reactor Development for Thermochemical Gasification and Calcination Processes*. ETH, 2018.
- [132] Wright MM, Satrio JA, Brown RC, Dugaard DE, Hsu DD. *Techno-Economic Analysis of Biomass Fast Pyrolysis to Transportation Fuels* 2010.
- [133] Seo MW, Lee SH, Nam H, Lee D, Tokmurzin D, Wang S, et al. Recent advances of thermochemical conversion processes for biorefinery. *Bioresour Technol* 2022;343:126109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2021.126109>.
- [134] Sánchez-Bastardo N, Schlögl R, Ruland H. Methane Pyrolysis for Zero-Emission Hydrogen Production: A Potential Bridge Technology from Fossil Fuels to a Renewable and Sustainable Hydrogen Economy. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 2021;60:11855–81. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.1c01679>.
- [135] Devi M, Rawat S, Sharma S. A comprehensive review of the pyrolysis process: from carbon nanomaterial synthesis to waste treatment. *Oxford Open Materials Science* 2020;1. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfmat/itab014>.
- [136] Brown RC. The Role of Pyrolysis and Gasification in a Carbon Negative Economy. *Processes* 2021;9:882. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9050882>.

- [137] Korányi TI, Németh M, Beck A, Horváth A. Recent Advances in Methane Pyrolysis: Turquoise Hydrogen with Solid Carbon Production. *Energies (Basel)* 2022;15:6342. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15176342>.
- [138] Fan Z, Weng W, Zhou J, Gu D, Xiao W. Catalytic decomposition of methane to produce hydrogen: A review. *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 2021;58:415–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2020.10.049>.
- [139] Molten-Salt Methane Pyrolysis Optimization Through in-situ Carbon Characterization and Reactor Design n.d.
- [140] Bhardwaj R, Frens W, Linders M, Goetheer E. PYROLYSIS TECHNOLOGY FOR HYDROGEN AND CARBON Ember n.d.
- [141] Giaconia A, Caputo G, Ienna A, Mazzei D, Schiavo B, Scialdone O, et al. Biorefinery process for hydrothermal liquefaction of microalgae powered by a concentrating solar plant: A conceptual study. *Appl Energy* 2017;208:1139–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.09.038>.
- [142] Raikova S, Wagner JL, Le CD, Ting VP, Chuck CJ. Towards an Aviation Fuel Through the Hydrothermal Liquefaction of Algae. *Biofuels for Aviation: Feedstocks, Technology and Implementation* 2016:217–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-804568-8.00009-3>.
- [143] Tzanetis KF, Posada JA, Ramirez A. Analysis of biomass hydrothermal liquefaction and biocrude-oil upgrading for renewable jet fuel production: The impact of reaction conditions on production costs and GHG emissions performance. *Renew Energy* 2017;113:1388–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2017.06.104>.
- [144] Blanco MJ, Santigosa LR. Advances in concentrating solar thermal research and technology. *Advances in Concentrating Solar Thermal Research and Technology* 2016:1–477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2014-0-04054-3>.
- [145] Sanz-Bermejo J, Muñoz-Antón J, Gonzalez-Aguilar J, Romero M. Optimal integration of a solid-oxide electrolyser cell into a direct steam generation solar tower plant for zero-emission hydrogen production. *Appl Energy* 2014;131:238–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2014.06.028>.
- [146] Monforti Ferrario A, Santoni F, della Pietra M, Rossi M, Piacente N, Comodi G, et al. A System Integration Analysis of a Molten Carbonate Electrolysis Cell as an Off-Gas Recovery System in a Steam-Reforming Process of an Oil Refinery. *Front Energy Res* 2021;9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FENRG.2021.655915>.
- [147] Frangini S, della Pietra M, della Seta L, Paoletti C, Pedro Pérez-Trujillo J. Degradation of MCFC Materials in a 81 cm² Single Cell Operated Under Alternated Fuel Cell/Electrolysis Mode. *Front Energy Res* 2021;9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FENRG.2021.653531>.
- [148] Roeb M, Thomey D, de Oliveira L, Sattler C, Fleury G, Pra F, et al. Sulphur based thermochemical cycles: Development and assessment of key components of the process. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2013;38:6197–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.01.068>.
- [149] Gorenssek MB, Corngale C, Summers WA. Development of the hybrid sulfur cycle for use with concentrated solar heat. I. Conceptual design. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2017;42:20939–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2017.06.241>.
- [150] Norman JH, Sharp R, Williamson D, Mysels KJ. Studies of the sulfur-iodine thermochemical water-splitting cycle. *Hep* 1981;1:257–75.
- [151] Kalyva AE, Vagia EC, Konstandopoulos AG, Srinivasa AR, T-Raissi A, Muradov N, et al. Hybrid photo-thermal sulfur-ammonia water splitting cycle: Thermodynamic analysis of the thermochemical steps. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2017;42:9533–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2017.01.104>.

- [152] Tizzoni AC, Mansi E, Sau S, Spadoni A, Corsaro N, Lanchi M, et al. Thermochemical cycle based on solid intermediates for hydrogen storage and on-demand production. *E3S Web of Conferences* 2022;334:01006. <https://doi.org/10.1051/E3SCONF/202233401006>.
- [153] Abanades S. Metal Oxides Applied to Thermochemical Water-Splitting for Hydrogen Production Using Concentrated Solar Energy. *ChemEngineering* 2019, Vol 3, Page 63 2019;3:63. <https://doi.org/10.3390/CHEMENGINEERING3030063>.
- [154] Padella F, Alvani C, la Barbera A, Ennas G, Liberatore R, Varsano F. Mechanochemistry and process characterization of nanostructured manganese ferrite. *Mater Chem Phys* 2005;90:172–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MATCHEMPHYS.2004.10.033>.
- [155] Sakurai M, Bilgen E, Tsutsumi A, Yoshida K. Solar UT-3 thermochemical cycle for hydrogen production. *Solar Energy* 1996;57:51–8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X\(96\)00034-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X(96)00034-5).
- [156] Doctor RD, Marshall CL, Wade DC. Hydrogen cycle employing calcium-bromine and electrolysis. 224th ACS National Meeting, Boston, MA (US), 08/18/2002--08/22/2002 2002.
- [157] Naterer GF, Suppiah S, Stolberg L, Lewis M, Wang Z, Rosen MA, et al. Progress in thermochemical hydrogen production with the copper–chlorine cycle. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2015;40:6283–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2015.02.124>.
- [158] Giaconia A, Iaquaniello G, Caputo G, Morico B, Salladini A, Turchetti L, et al. Experimental validation of a pilot membrane reactor for hydrogen production by solar steam reforming of methane at maximum 550 °C using molten salts as heat transfer fluid. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2020;45:33088–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2020.09.070>.
- [159] Angeli SD, Turchetti L, Monteleone G, Lemonidou AA. Catalyst development for steam reforming of methane and model biogas at low temperature. *Appl Catal B* 2016;181:34–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2015.07.039>.
- [160] Turchetti L, Murmura MA, Monteleone G, Giaconia A, Lemonidou AA, Angeli SD, et al. Kinetic assessment of Ni-based catalysts in low-temperature methane/biogas steam reforming. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2016;41:16865–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2016.07.245>.
- [161] Integrating National Research Agendas on Solar Heat for Industrial Processes | INSHIP | Project | Fact sheet | H2020 | CORDIS | European Commission n.d. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731287> (accessed January 17, 2024).
- [162] Zhang Y, Liang Y, Li S, Yuan Y, Zhang D, Wu Y, et al. A review of biomass pyrolysis gas: Forming mechanisms, influencing parameters, and product application upgrades. *Fuel* 2023;347:128461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUEL.2023.128461>.
- [163] Peters MS, Timmerhaus KD, West RE. *Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers* 5th edition. 2003.
- [164] Turton R. *Analysis, Synthesis, and Design of Chemical Processes* Fourth Edition. 2013.
- [165] *Chemical Engineering Magazine - Economic Indicator*. Chemical Engineering 2021.
- [166] Turchi CS, Boyd M, Kesseli D, Kurup P, Mehos M, Neises T, et al. *CSP Systems Analysis - Final Project*. Nrel/Tp-5500-72856 2019.
- [167] Starke AR, Cardemil JM, Bonini VRB, Escobar R, Castro-Quijada M, Videla Á. Assessing the performance of novel molten salt mixtures on CSP applications. *Appl Energy* 2024;359:122689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122689>.

- [168] Giaconia A, Iaquaniello G, Morico B, Salladini A, Palo E. Techno-economic assessment of solar steam reforming of methane in a membrane reactor using molten salts as heat transfer fluid. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2021;46:35172–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.08.096>.
- [169] PVGIS Online Tool ver. 5.2 n.d.
- [170] System Advisor Model (SAM) n.d. <https://sam.nrel.gov/> (accessed February 1, 2022).
- [171] Clean Hydrogen Partnership -Hydrogen cost and sales prices n.d. <https://h2v.eu/analysis/statistics/financing/hydrogen-cost-and-sales-prices> (accessed March 8, 2024).
- [172] Jovan DJ, Dolanc G. Can Green Hydrogen Production Be Economically Viable under Current Market Conditions. *Energies (Basel)* 2020;13:6599. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13246599>.
- [173] A portfolio of power-trains for Europe: a fact-based analysis The role of Battery Electric Vehicles, Plug-in Hybrids and Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles. n.d.
- [174] Olive oil - European Commission n.d. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/crop-productions-and-plant-based-products/olive-oil_en (accessed March 8, 2024).
- [175] Foti P, Romeo F V, Russo N, Pino A, Vaccaluzzo A, Caggia C, et al. Olive Mill Wastewater as Renewable Raw Materials to Generate High Added-Value Ingredients for Agro-Food Industries 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11167511>.
- [176] Morillo JA, Antizar-Ladislaio B, Monteoliva-Sánchez M, Ramos-Cormenzana A, Russell NJ. Bioremediation and biovalorisation of olive-mill wastes. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 2009;82:25–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00253-008-1801-Y>.
- [177] A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe. 2020.
- [178] Rocha C, Soria MA, Madeira LM. Steam reforming of olive oil mill wastewater with in situ hydrogen and carbon dioxide separation – Thermodynamic analysis. *Fuel* 2017;207:449–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2017.06.111>.
- [179] Rocha C, Soria MA, Madeira LM. Thermodynamic analysis of olive oil mill wastewater steam reforming. *Journal of the Energy Institute* 2019;92:1599–609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joei.2018.06.017>.
- [180] Carvalho J, Nogueira A, Castro-Silva S, Rocha C, Madeira LM. Process simulation and techno-economic analysis of olive oil mill wastewater steam reforming. *Energy* 2023;278:127895. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127895>.
- [181] Varbanov PS, Wang Q, Zeng M, Seferlis P, Ma T, Klemeš JJ, et al. Economic Analysis of Syngas Production by Coupling Coal Gasification Wastewater Treatment and Solid Oxide Cell System. *Chem Eng Trans* 2020;81:2020. <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET2081189>.
- [182] Song G, Zhao S, Wang X, Cui X, Wang H, Xiao J. An efficient biomass and renewable power-to-gas process integrating electrical heating gasification. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering* 2022;30:101735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2021.101735>.
- [183] Cui X, Song G, Yao A, Wang H, Wang L, Xiao J. Technical and Economic Assessments of a novel biomass-to-synthetic natural gas (SNG) process integrating O₂-enriched air gasification. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 2021;156:417–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2021.10.025>.
- [184] Krummenacher P, Muster B. Solar process heat for production and advanced applications: Methodologies and software tools for integrating solar heat into industrial processes. 2015.

- [185] Pardo GNicolas, Vatopoulos Konstaninos, Krook-Riekkola Anna, Moya Rivera JAntonio, Perez Lopez Alicia. Heat and cooling demand and market perspective. Publications Office of the European Union; 2012.
- [186] Kumar L, Hasanuzzaman M, Rahim NA. Global advancement of solar thermal energy technologies for industrial process heat and its future prospects: A review. *Energy Convers Manag* 2019;195:885–908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.05.081>.
- [187] Farjana SH, Huda N, Mahmud MAP, Saidur R. Solar process heat in industrial systems – A global review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2018;82:2270–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.08.065>.
- [188] Sharma AK, Sharma C, Mullick SC, Kandpal TC. Solar industrial process heating: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2017;78:124–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.04.079>.
- [189] D’Auria M, Lanchi M, Liberatore R. Selezione delle configurazioni di sistemi solari a concentrazione idonei alla fornitura di calore di processo per diversi settori applicativi industriali ed elaborazione di schemi concettuali di integrazione. Report Rds/PTR(2019)/088. 2019.
- [190] D’Auria M, Lanchi M, Liberatore R. Determinazione del costo del kWh termico a scale di impianto e livelli termici differenti. 2021.
- [191] Liang T, Vecchi A, Knobloch K, Sciacovelli A, Engelbrecht K, Li Y, et al. Key components for Carnot Battery: Technology review, technical barriers and selection criteria. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2022;163:112478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112478>.
- [192] Energy Storage-Underpinning a decarbonised and secure EU energy system n.d. <https://doi.org/10.2833/333409>.
- [193] European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy, Hoogland O, Fluri V, Kost C, et al. Study on energy storage 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2833/333409>.
- [194] He Y, Guo S, Zhou J, Wu F, Huang J, Pei H. The quantitative techno-economic comparisons and multi-objective capacity optimization of wind-photovoltaic hybrid power system considering different energy storage technologies. *Energy Convers Manag* 2021;229:113779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2020.113779>.
- [195] EASE - European Association for Storage of Energy. Energy Storage Targets 2030 and 2050: Ensuring Europe’s Energy Security in a Renewable Energy System n.d. <https://ease-storage.eu/publication/energy-storage-targets-2030-and-2050/> (accessed March 18, 2024).
- [196] European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy. Terms of reference - Energy storage 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2833/59559>.
- [197] Directive - 2019/944 - EN - EUR-Lex n.d. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/944/oj> (accessed March 18, 2024).
- [198] DOE Global Energy Storage Database n.d. <https://sandia.gov/ess-ssl/gesdb/public/statistics.html> (accessed March 18, 2024).
- [199] Augustine C, Blair N. Storage Futures Study: Storage Technology Modeling Input Data Report 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1785959>.
- [200] How rapidly will the global electricity storage market grow by 2026? – Analysis - IEA n.d. <https://www.iea.org/articles/how-rapidly-will-the-global-electricity-storage-market-grow-by-2026> (accessed March 18, 2024).

- [201] Smallbone A, Jülich V, Wardle R, Roskilly AP. Levelised Cost of Storage for Pumped Heat Energy Storage in comparison with other energy storage technologies. *Energy Convers Manag* 2017;152:221–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2017.09.047>.
- [202] Kebede AA, Kalogiannis T, Van Mierlo J, Berecibar M. A comprehensive review of stationary energy storage devices for large scale renewable energy sources grid integration. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2022;159:112213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2022.112213>.
- [203] McTigue JD, Farres-Antunez P, White AJ, Markides CN, Martinek J, Jorgenson J, et al. Integrated Heat Pump Thermal Storage and Power Cycle for CSP: Final Technical Report 2022.
- [204] International Energy Agency, Technology collaboration programme, Energy Storage - Task 36: Carnot Batteries n.d. <https://iea-es.org/task-36/> (accessed March 18, 2024).
- [205] Frate GF, Ferrari L, Desideri U. Rankine Carnot Batteries with the Integration of Thermal Energy Sources: A Review. *Energies (Basel)* 2020;13:4766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13184766>.
- [206] Carnot Batteries: A new Annex proposal within the International Energy Agency (IEA) Energy Conservation through Energy Storage ECES TCP Motivation n.d.
- [207] Vecchi A, Knobloch K, Liang T, Kildahl H, Sciacovelli A, Engelbrecht K, et al. Carnot Battery development: A review on system performance, applications and commercial state-of-the-art. *J Energy Storage* 2022;55:105782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.105782>.
- [208] Novotny V, Basta V, Smola P, Spale J. Review of Carnot Battery Technology Commercial Development. *Energies (Basel)* 2022;15:647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15020647>.
- [209] White MT, Bianchi G, Chai L, Tassou SA, Sayma AI. Review of supercritical CO₂ technologies and systems for power generation. *Appl Therm Eng* 2021;185:116447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APPLTHERMALENG.2020.116447>.
- [210] Stein WH, Buck R. Advanced power cycles for concentrated solar power. *Solar Energy* 2017;152:91–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLENER.2017.04.054>.
- [211] Spelling J, Gallo A, Romero M, González-Aguilar J. A High-efficiency Solar Thermal Power Plant using a Dense Particle Suspension as the Heat Transfer Fluid. *Energy Procedia* 2015;69:1160–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYPRO.2015.03.191>.
- [212] Siemens Energy. Industrial steam turbines – tailor-made and flexible n.d. <https://www.siemens-energy.com/global/en/home/products-services/product/industrial-steam-turbines.html#Technical-Data-and-Typical-Applications-tab-3> (accessed March 26, 2024).
- [213] Bertrand A, Menacho ÁJH, Badillo BL. Waste heat-to-power with steam and organic Rankine cycles: Potentials and feed-in tariffs in the EU27+UK. *Energy Reports* 2022;8:12552–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYR.2022.09.075>.
- [214] Gage SH, Kesseli D, Dupree J, Kimbal C, Rigby J, Yates J, et al. Technical and economic feasibility of molten chloride salt thermal energy storage systems. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2021;226:111099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2021.111099>.
- [215] Ding W, Bonk A, Bauer T. Corrosion behavior of metallic alloys in molten chloride salts for thermal energy storage in concentrated solar power plants: A review. *Front Chem Sci Eng* 2018;12:564–76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11705-018-1720-0/METRICS>.
- [216] Balliet H, McLaughlin L, Ma Z, Glusenkamp K. Technology Strategy Assessment: Findings from Storage Innovations 2030 Thermal Energy Storage. Idaho Falls, ID (United States): 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1998552>.

- [217] Heat Pump Centre. ANNEX 58 - High-Temperature Heat Pumps, Task 1 – Technologies, Task Report. 2023. <https://heatpumpingtechnologies.org/annex58/task1/> (accessed March 26, 2024).
- [218] Zühlsdorf B, Lecompte S, Poulsen JL. Decarbonizing process heating with high-temperature heat pumps How to exploit the potential?, 2023.
- [219] Innovation Gaps – Analysis - IEA n.d. <https://www.iea.org/reports/innovation-gaps> (accessed March 26, 2024).
- [220] Klute S, Budt M, van Beek M, Doetsch C. Steam generating heat pumps – Overview, classification, economics, and basic modeling principles. *Energy Convers Manag* 2024;299:117882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2023.117882>.
- [221] Georgiou S, Shah N, Markides CN. A thermo-economic analysis and comparison of pumped-thermal and liquid-air electricity storage systems. *Appl Energy* 2018;226:1119–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2018.04.128>.
- [222] Caraballo A, Galán-Casado S, Caballero Á, Serena S. Molten Salts for Sensible Thermal Energy Storage: A Review and an Energy Performance Analysis. *Energies (Basel)* 2021;14:1197. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14041197>.
- [223] Gong Q, Shi H, Chai Y, Yu R, Weisenburger A, Wang D, et al. Molten chloride salt technology for next-generation CSP plants: Compatibility of Fe-based alloys with purified molten MgCl₂-KCl-NaCl salt at 700 °C. *Appl Energy* 2022;324:119708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2022.119708>.
- [224] Gong Q, Hanke A, Kessel F, Bonk A, Bauer T, Ding W. Molten chloride salt technology for next-generation CSP plants: Selection of cold tank structural material utilizing corrosion control at 500 °C. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2023;253:112233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOLMAT.2023.112233>.
- [225] Shingledecker J, De Barbadillo J, O'Donnell D, McCoy S, Baker B, Coryell S. Materials improvements for improved economy of high-temperature components in future gen 3 CSP systems. *AIP Conf Proc* 2019;2126. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5117512/701566>.
- [226] Turchi C, Gage S, Martinek J, Jape S, Armijo K, Coventry J, et al. CSP Gen3: Liquid-Phase Pathway to SunShot. Golden, CO (United States): 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1807668>.
- [227] Moore R, Siegel N, Kolb G, Vernon M, Ho C. Design considerations for concentrating solar power tower systems employing molten salt. Albuquerque, NM, and Livermore, CA (United States): 2010. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1008140>.
- [228] González-Gómez PA, Gómez-Hernández J, Briongos J V., Santana D. Transient thermo-mechanical analysis of steam generators for solar tower plants. *Appl Energy* 2018;212:1051–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2017.12.128>.
- [229] Five Steps to Energy Storage - Innovation Insights Brief. 2020.
- [230] Krishan O, Suhag S. An updated review of energy storage systems: Classification and applications in distributed generation power systems incorporating renewable energy resources. *Int J Energy Res* 2019;43:6171–210. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ER.4285>.
- [231] Turchi CS, Heath GA. Molten Salt Power Tower Cost Model for the System Advisor Model (SAM). Golden, CO (United States): 2013. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1067902>.
- [232] Utility-Scale Battery Storage | Electricity | 2023 | ATB | NREL n.d. https://atb.nrel.gov/electricity/2023/utility-scale_battery_storage (accessed March 19, 2024).

- [233] Gräf D, Marschewski J, Ibing L, Hückebrink D, Fiebrandt M, Hanau G, et al. What drives capacity degradation in utility-scale battery energy storage systems? The impact of operating strategy and temperature in different grid applications. *J Energy Storage* 2022;47:103533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EST.2021.103533>.
- [234] Yildiz E, Hustig-Diethelm F, Heide S, Kretschmann J. CSP Bankability Project Report Draft for an Appendix O-Cost Structures to the SolarPACES Guideline for Bankable STE Yield Assessment. 2017.
- [235] Giuliano S, Puppe M, Noureldin K. Power-to-heat in CSP systems for capacity expansion. *AIP Conf Proc* 2019;2126. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5117589/701617>.
- [236] Turchi C. Parabolic Trough Reference Plant for Cost Modeling with the Solar Advisor Model (SAM). Golden, CO (United States): 2010. <https://doi.org/10.2172/983729>.
- [237] Glatzmaier G. Developing a Cost Model and Methodology to Estimate Capital Costs for Thermal Energy Storage. Golden, CO (United States): 2011. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1031953>.
- [238] Dieckmann S, Dersch J, Giuliano S, Puppe M, Lüpfer E, Hennecke K, et al. LCOE reduction potential of parabolic trough and solar tower CSP technology until 2025. *AIP Conf Proc* 2017;1850:160004. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4984538/616904>.
- [239] Belderbos A, Delarue E, Kessels K, D'haeseleer W. Levelized cost of storage — Introducing novel metrics. *Energy Econ* 2017;67:287–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERCO.2017.08.022>.
- [240] ROADMAP FOR CARBON NEUTRALITY 2050 (RNC2050) LONG-TERM STRATEGY FOR CARBON NEUTRALITY OF THE PORTUGUESE ECONOMY BY 2050. 2019.
- [241] REN DATA HUB - Electricity Daily Balance n.d. <https://datahub.ren.pt/en/electricity/daily-balance/> (accessed March 19, 2024).

RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Project Handbook

The *Project Handbook* establishes the high-level approach for implementing the project goals, which includes required documentation, standards to be considered and the high level summary of the quality and configuration management approach. It also captures any training needs for the project team members. The location of this artefact is found in the Appendix 1.

Communications Management Plan

The *Communications Management Plan* helps to ensure that all project stakeholders have the information they need to perform their roles throughout the project. It defines and documents the communication items content, format, frequency, the audience and expected results. The location of this artefact is found in the Appendix 1.

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in the Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resources requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Data Management Plan

The *Data Management Plan* describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in a project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located in DLR server, in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. Project Core Team (PCT), will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to remaining ones. Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders and finally, Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest pdf and word versions of each document will be available and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Legal_documents/Grant_Agreement/101079303_Annex%201%20-%20Description%20of%20the%20action%20(part%20A).pdf
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Legal_documents/Grant_Agreement/101079303_Annex%201%20-%20Description%20of%20the%20action%20(part%20B).pdf
4	Participants Portal	EC Portal https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home
5	Contacts List <Contact_List_SALTOPower.pdf.>	Project Folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Quality_Assurance_and_Risk_Management
6	Roles and Responsibilities list <Roles_and_responsibilities_list>	Project Folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Quality_Assurance_and_Risk_Management
7	Deliverables acceptance plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SALTOPOWER.14-02-2023.v0.1>	Project Folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Quality_Assurance_and_Risk_Management
8	Deliverables acceptance note	Project Folder

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
	<[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SALTOPOWER.10-02-2023.v1.0- Worksheet D#ANote>	https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Quality_Assurance_and_Risk_Management
9	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SALTOPOWER.10-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Quality_Assurance_and_Risk_Management
10	Project Handbook <NOT YET AVAILABLE. UNDER DEFINITION>	NOT YET AVAILABLE
11	Data Management Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_21-04-2023_v_1>	Project Folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/DEC_Plan
12	PowerPoint Presentations <SALTOpower_WP1>	Project Folder https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Presentation.pptx?d=w2ba57b87dfe7423486140bf65932a23f
13	Scientific Publications NOT YET AVAILABLE. UNDER DEFINITION	NOT YET AVAILABLE